

A gravitational interaction potential unifies gravity with other forces: The cornerstone of Theory of Everything

Michael Y.T. Hwang
University Square, E. Palo Alto, CA, 94303, USA
MichaelYTHwang@gmail.com

In this paper, I postulate a quantized-singularity gravitational potential named matter warped E-space potential (MWEP) and a gravitational interaction potential named E-space interdomain interaction potential (EIDIP). That the resulting EIDIP framework unifies gravity with other forces previously understood as fundamental and accounts for numerous phenomena previously thought to be anomalies is supported by the 10+ three-variable computational EIDIP effects phenomenological tests (EEPTs) based on the plain EIDIP effects equations and publicly available empirical data. The simplest two-body interaction EIDIP equation is a single-shaping-parameter nonlinear function of distance; the derivation of the EIDIP equation has revealed that gravity and other fundamental forces have *parent-child* relationships in contrast to the *peer-to-peer* relationship assumption of conventional unify models; i.e., gravity is the only fundamental force to date. The 10+ EEPTs have shown that, without conventional form factors, the EIDIP effects can describe a wide range of physical phenomena and anomalies: interquark strong force, internucleon potential, interatomic covalent forces, nuclear binding energy of known nuclei, Bohr radius, effective couplings (electric, magnetic, residual-strong, and strong) and the related fine structure constant and Planck constant, subatomic neutron and proton charge distributions, astronomical Pioneer 10/11 and Milky Way rotation curve anomalies, etc. The null hypothesis testing nodes extracted from these phenomenological tests indicate that nulling the EIDIP's existence has a 5+ sigma significance level. With additional insights gained from these phenomenological tests, the EIDIP framework can provide coherent first-order rationales for additional physical phenomena beyond the Newtonian limit: dark matter, dark energy, gravity wave, black hole, gravitational frame dragging, quantum entanglement, gravitoelectromagnetism, near-Earth-fly-by anomalies, etc. With the EIDIP framework's intuitive simplicity, unifying capabilities, plain EIDIP effects equations, and high statistical confidence, taken together, these results suggested that the EIDIP can be the cornerstone of the Theory of Everything and the EIDIP framework is worthy of further developments.

Keywords: Theory of Everything, grand unified theory, gravity, strong interaction, weak interaction, effective coupling, Pioneer anomaly, galaxy rotation curve anomaly, galaxy formation, nuclear binding energy, elementary particle, neutron and proton charge distributions, residual-strong force, Newtonian limit, covalent force, dark energy, dark matter, black hole, quantum entanglement, gravitoelectromagnetism, gravity wave, standard model, and general relativity, MWEP, EIDIP, IDGIP.

I. INTRODUCTION

General relativity (GR) is a theoretical framework that focuses on the gravitational force in an astronomical scale whereas quantum field theory (QFT) is a theoretical framework that focuses on three non-gravitational forces in atomic and subatomic scales. QFT successfully implemented the Standard Model (SM) and unified the three non-gravitational fundamental forces. However, GR and QFT are mutually incompatible, and they cannot both be correct. To resolve this conflict, a theoretical framework revealing a deeper underlying reality, unifying gravity with the other fundamental forces, must be discovered to form a Theory of Everything that, in principle, is capable of describing all phenomena [1].

In this paper, I postulate a quantized-singularity gravitational potential named matter warped E-space potential (MWEP) and a gravitational interaction produced potential named E-space interdomain interaction potential (EIDIP).¹ The resulting EIDIP framework unifies gravity with other forces previously understood as fundamental and accounts for numerous phenomena previously thought to be anomalies.

This paper includes more than ten (10+) computational EIDIP effects phenomenological tests (EEPT)² based on the plain EIDIP effects equations and publicly available empirical data computed to validate the EIDIP framework. The EIDIP function underlying these EEPTs is a *single-shaping-parameter nonlinear* function of distance. With additional distance and magnitude scalars, these *three-variable* EEPTs have shown that the EIDIP effects can describe or explain a wide range of physical phenomena and anomalies from subatomic to astronomic without conventional form factors:

- (1) The strong force's asymptotic and conformal behaviors, and its short interaction range;
- (2) The distance-dependent repulsive-attractive behaviors of internucleon nuclear force and interatomic covalent force;
- (3) The neutron and proton charge distributions;
- (4) The effective electric, magnetic, strong, and residual-strong couplings; and the relationship between EIDIP effects and these physical constants: Coulomb's constant, elementary charge, the fine structure constant, and Planck constant;
- (5) The atomic Bohr radius;

¹ Vs. the singularity-at-origin Newtonian gravitational potentials. To preview the MWEP function, refer to equation (13) and (14), and FIG. 6;

to preview the EIDIP function, refer to equation (19), and FIG. 8 and FIG. 9.

² Aka EIDIP effects phenomenological fits (EEPF) in my prior papers.

- (6) The gravitational constant and the large deviation between the Newtonian gravitational constant measurements;
- (7) The phenomena of the weak interaction without the contradiction of electroweak unification;
- (8) The upper bound of the nuclear binding energy for almost all known nuclei;
- (9) The nuclear charge radii of heavy and light nuclei;
- (10) The Pioneer 10/11 sunward acceleration anomalies;
- (11) The Milky Way rotation curve anomalies.

In short, the 10+ EEPTs have shown that the EIDIP framework can reduce a wide range of physical phenomena and anomalies to more basic EIDIP effects without the conventional form factors. Because the EIDIP effects engender other fundamental forces, the gravitational potential to the EIDIP equation derivation has revealed their *parent-child* relationships in contrast to the conventional *peer-to-peer* relationship assumption.

That the 10+ EEPTs are based on the empirical data or figures constructed from conventional models has indicated the EIDIP framework can describe the physical phenomena's behaviors that are consistent with relevant conventional models' descriptions; i.e., the accumulated knowledge of the disparate conventional models has helped not hindered the EIDIP framework's development.

Because the three-variable EEPTs can yield insights into areas where high-variable count conventional models cannot, they have produced a long list of falsifiable predictions and uncanny null hypothesis testing nodes (NHTN).³ Assuming each NHTN is artificially assigned with a conservative 50% probability that the underlying EIDIP does not exist, based on the 35+ primary NHTNs alone, nulling the EIDIP (does exist) already has a 5+ sigma significant level.

Furthermore, with the single shaping-parameter set, the nonperturbative nonlinear EIDIP effects functions have rigid shapes such that they can gain additional information from the distance and magnitude scalers of, and the commonalities between, these EEPTs. With the gained insights, the EIDIP framework can also provide coherent first-order rationales for additional physical phenomena beyond the Newtonian limit: e.g., particle-wave duality, proton spin crisis, neutron electric dipole moment problem, photon antibunching, dark matter, dark energy, accelerating expansion of the universe, galaxy formation, astrophysical and hadron jets, gravitational lensing and frame-dragging, gravitational time dilation measurement, quantum decoherence, quantum entanglement, astronomical gravitoelectromagnetism, black hole structure, gravity wave, and near-Earth flyby anomaly.⁴

With the EIDIP framework's intuitive simplicity, unifying capabilities, and plain EIDIP effects equations, taken together, they have suggested that the EIDIP can be the cornerstone of the Theory of Everything and the EIDIP framework is worthy of further developments.

The following is a section summary of this paper. Because of the unorthodox nature of the EIDIP framework,

readers are encouraged to browse the plain MWEP and EIDIP equations,¹ and these phenomenological tests in sections: V to VIII first.

- (1) Section II describes the MWEP and EIDIP equations, and MATLAB numerical- and symbolic-integration EIDIP generation methods;
- (2) Section III describes the normalized two-body system-EIDIP and derived functions;
- (3) Section IV describes MWEP and EIDIP effects induced forces;
- (4) Section V contains these EEPTs: nuclear binding energy and nuclear charge radius;
- (5) Section VI contains these EIDIP-gradient effects phenomenological tests (gradient-EEPTs): interatomic covalent force, gravitational constant measurement deviation, and nuclear force (neutron-neutron potential);
- (6) Section VII contains these angular EIDIP effects phenomenological tests (angular-EEPTs): Bohr radius, strong force, and Pioneer 10/11 sunward acceleration anomaly;
- (7) Section VIII contains these composite-EEPTs: proton and neutron charge distributions, effective couplings (strong, residual-strong, electrostatic, and magnetic) and Milky Way rotation curve anomalies;
- (8) Section IX contains a distance and magnitude formulas summary table, the commonalities between the 10+ EEPTs, the feasibility of the EIDIP effects, and explanatory hypotheses;
- (9) Section X contains the EIDIP framework's scientific method, 5+ sigma significant level computation, and future development proposals for additional physical phenomena beyond the Newtonian limit;
- (10) Section XI contains discussion and the conclusion that the EIDIP can be the cornerstone of the Theory of Everything and the EIDIP framework is worthy of further developments;
- (11) Appendix sections contain abbreviation description tables, inter-domain MWEP derivations, neutron electric dipole moment problem and proton spin crisis are likely OEIAs discussion, EIDIP effects can unify EM and weak interaction without the contradiction of electroweak unification discussion, RAVE-DR2 MW stars' positions and velocities distributions figures and implications, and EIDIP generation MATLAB programs to assist the 10+ EEPTs reproduction.

³ Refer to section X.B for the NHTN lists.

⁴ Refer to section X.D for details.

II. MATTER-WARPED E-SPACE POTENTIAL (MWEP) AND E-SPACE INTER-DOMAIN INTERACTION POTENTIAL (EIDIP)

A. Defined constant R_0

The first idea I had was that space (vacuum) possesses isotropic energy (E-space) such that the energy grid (resolution) of E-space should be related to the speed of light (in a vacuum) and gravitational constant. Furthermore, because a point mass induced potential grid is spherical in nature, if my hypothesis was in the right direction, the factor between gravitational constant and the speed of light should have a simple value and include the spherical-centric term π . I discovered a constant named R_0 that met the requirements closely and has been widely used in the 10+ EEPTs.

In the EIDIP framework, the R_0 is a defined *unit-less* constant

$$R_0 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} 1/(32\pi c), \quad (1)$$

with c as the speed of light in the SI base units. An inverse constant $H_0 = 1/R_0$ is used in this paper to simplify formulas. Note that, $2R_0$ value equals 99.43% of the 2014 CODATA-recommended gravitational constant value [2].

B. Isotropic E-space membrane contractive and expansive transformation hypothesis

Besides the E-space hypothesis, the EIDIP framework further hypothesizes that E-space contains isotropic membrane tension of which the strength is related to the speed of light and gravitational constant. An isotropic E-space membrane can ripple because of internal or external dynamics; if the disturbance is large enough, it can warp the E-space membrane into matter with a spherical shell structure through an E-space contractive and expansive transformation (ESCX or MWEP transformation hypothesis).⁵ To illuminate that, equation (1) can be reformulated in meter unit as

$$[(32\pi R_0) \times c]_{m^2} = [1^2]_{m^2}; \quad (2)$$

which represents a one square meter isotropic E-space membrane (IEM) (blue square, FIG. 1) that can be transformed into $[c]_m$ (expansive transformation in the radial direction) by $[2 \times 8\pi(2R_0)]_m$ (contractive transformation into spherical shell gradient) of warped E-space (purple square, FIG. 1) with a post-transformation residual membrane tension (RMT) energy,

$$E_{RMT} = c/(32\pi R_0) = c^2, \quad (3)$$

⁵ The spherical shell structure hypothesis concurs with objects tend to have spherical natural forms and nuclei have shell structures based on the mass-number-quadratic, instead of the mass-number-cubic, nuclear charge radius semi-empirical formula I have developed (refer to section V.B and [41]).

the same as the energy to mass factor $E/m = c^2$.

FIG. 1. (Color online) Isotropic E-space membrane to matter transformation figure.⁶

C. Matter-Warped E-space Potential (MWEP)

From the Nyquist–Shannon sampling theorem, we know that in signal reconstruction, the fidelity of the reconstructed result depends on the density of the original samples [3]; and that truncation in one domain causes ringing artifacts in the other domain [4]. E.g., a reconstructed box shape signal from bandwidth limited (Fourier transformed) frequency components does not have vertical edges like the original box; instead, depending on the sampling frequency (energy resolution), it has a boxlike center and ringing artifacts that extend over the original box shape boundary (leakage-field) (FIG. 2, reproduced from [5]).

FIG. 2. Square wave reconstructed from various degrees of Fourier expansion sine wave (frequency) terms figure (reproduced from [5]); reconstructed square waves with higher frequency (energy) terms have less ringing: the first one term (black line), four terms (blue line), and sixteen terms (red line).

As to a limited bandwidth reconstructed box signal that

⁶ A simplified two-dimensional figure to show the energy conservative contractive and expansive transformation hypothesis, $[32\pi R_0]_m = [2 \times 8\pi(2R_0)]_m$ represents the surface gradient of the spherical shell structure shown in FIG. 3.

has a boxlike center and an external ringing leakage-field, the ESCX transformation leaves behind a spheroidal core (like the boxlike center) and an external field (like the ringing leakage-field); this is because 1) the energy resolution (frequency) underlying the ESCX transformation is limited by nature, 2) the absolute zero distance does not exist in nature,⁷ and 3) the spherical form requires the least energy to maintain (most stable).⁸ Hence, the ESCX transformation produces matter with a *spheroidal* energy structure comprising an inner core and an external residual tension field. The inner core behaves like a fermion (E-fermion), and the external residual tension field behaves like a boson (E-boson). I called this post-ESCX-transformation energy structure the matter-warped-E-space potential (MWEP).⁹

Note that, in contrast to Newtonian at-origin-singularity gravitational potential, the MWEP has a quantized singularity at the E-fermion border. Because the E-fermion core exhibits the particle characteristics, and the E-boson field exhibits the wave characteristics, the MWEP possesses the wave-particle duality. The 10+ EEPTs presented in later sections reveals that all forms of energy entities, including photon and matter, possess the MWEP.¹⁰

1 Post ESCX transformation residual tensions

The EIDIP framework posits that an isotropic E-space contains energy in a tension-equilibrium state. Because the E-space energy density decreases when stretched and increases when compressed, the E-space tensile stress also changes. Note that stretching (or compressing) in the orthogonal direction also decreases (or increases) the in-direction energy density and tensile stress.

The ESCX transformation leaves behind a spherical energy structure with two *angular isotropic* (stable intensity per steradian) residual tensions (AIRT):

- (1) An ortho-radial E-space contractive transformation residual tension (ECTRT);¹¹
- (2) A radial E-space expansive transformation residual tension (EXTRT).

To illustrate the ESCX transformation with an explanatory model, let's imagine that a meter square of E-space worldsheet first transforms into a thick spherical shell embedded with the radial EXTRT and ortho-radial ECTRT (FIG. 3).¹² With that, equation (1) can be written to include these AIRTs

$$\begin{aligned} [4\pi(2R_0)^2]_{m^2} [2R_0]_{m/s^2}^{EXTRT} [c]_{m/s^2}^{ECTRT} \\ = [1^2]_{m^2} [R_0^2]_{m^2/s^4}^{IEMT} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

⁷ In log-polar coordinates, the radial axis has an infinite negative range; i.e., the absolute zero does not exist in this *log*-scale radial-axis.

⁸ Surface tension can be interpreted as the energy cost of creating an additional surface area. A spherical shape requires least surface area to enclose a set volume; hence, it requires least energy input to overcome surface tensile forces before it reaches the equilibrium.

⁹ The name MWEP is kept for its backward compatibility with my older papers. More accurately, matter does not warp an E-space to form a

with $[4\pi(2R_0)^2]_{m^2}$ as the contractive E-fermion (cE-fermion) sphere surface, $[2R_0]_{m/s^2}$ as the radial EXTRT, $[c]_{m/s^2}$ as the ortho-radial ECTRT, and $[R_0^2]_{m^2/s^4} [1^2]_{m^2}$ as the isotropic E-space membrane tension (IEMT) per meter square. Note that $2R_0$ value equals 99.43% of the 2014 CODATA-recommended gravitational constant value [2].

FIG. 3. (Color online) Explanatory ESCX transformation model figure: 2D E-space worldsheet (blue square) to 3D spherical thick shell energy structure (light blue region shows the cross cut) with *angular isotropic* radial EXTRT (orange arrow) and ortho-radial ECTRT (blue arrow).

This explanatory ESCX transformation model shows how a three-dimensional (3D) MWEP (matter) can be transformed from a two-dimensional (2D) isotropic E-space worldsheet. Real-world ESCX transformations are 3D to 3D transformations; e.g., from a stack of isotropic E-space worldsheets (FIG. 4(a)) to an angular isotropic MWEP (FIG. 4(b)) transformation.

2 Natural length unit

In the EIDIP framework, a natural length unit (NLU) ℓ is defined as that $[1]_{\ell}$ of isotropic linear E-space contains $[1]_{\ell^2/s^2}$ linear energy (IELE) and $[1]_{\ell^2}$ of isotropic E-space membrane (IEM) contains $[1^2]_{\ell^4/s^4}$ membrane energy (IEME). Because tension is identical to energy per unit area (density), the E-space also contains $[1]_{\ell/s^2}$ isotropic E-space linear tension (IELT) and $[1^2]_{\ell^2/s^4}$ IEM tension (IEMT).

With that, equation (2) can be rewritten to express that $[H_0^2]_{\ell^2}$ isotropic E-space, which contains $[1^2]_{\ell^2/s^4}$ IEMT, can be transformed into a spherical energy structure with $[2]_{\ell/s^2}$ ECTRT on the sphere surface $[4\pi 2^2]_{\ell^2}$ and $[c/R_0]_{\ell/s^2}$ EXTRT,

$$\begin{aligned} [4\pi 2^2]_{\ell^2} [2]_{\ell/s^2}^{ECTRT} [cH_0]_{\ell/s^2}^{EXTRT} = \\ [H_0^2]_{\ell^2} [1^2]_{\ell^2/s^4}^{IEMT} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

MWEP; rather matter comes with a MWEP through the ESCX transformation, i.e., a post-ESCX-transformation residual potential (PCXP).

¹⁰ Refer to section IX.D for the argument that matter and energy entities possess MWEP regardless of their size.

¹¹ More accurately, it is a compressive or negative tension.

¹² The nuclear charge radius (NCR) EEPT presented in the later section affirms that heavy nuclei have a spherical shell structure.

Compared to equation (4), we can derive that the $[R_0]_m$ is an NLU.

3 Post ESCX transformation cE- and xE- fermion radii

The following three sections contain the summary of the explanatory ESCX transformation model and MWEF equation derivations detailed in Appendix II.

From equation (5), we can derive the formulas of the normalized radial EXTRT intensity (EXTRTI), ortho-radial ECTRT intensity (ECTRTI), ECTRT radial gradient intensity (ECTRTGI), and radial spherical surface gradient tension intensity (SSGTI) shown in TABLE I and FIG. 4.

With that, some of the post-ESCX transformation (expansive and contractive) residual energy induced radial EXTRTI and ECTRTGI, and ortho-radial ECTRTI are in equilibrium and harmonize with the radial SSGTI at the cE-fermion shell radius $[2]_\ell$ (aka cE-wavelength) where the residual energy accumulates to form matter. Some residual energy is also in equilibrium and harmonize with the radial SSGTI at the radius $[2]_{\ell_x}$ (aka xE-wavelength, $[2]_{\ell_x} = [cH_0]_\ell$ in this example) to form the expansive E-fermion (xE-fermion) shell shown in FIG. 4(b).

TABLE I. Post-ESCX transformation SSGTI, ECTRTI, EXTRTI, and ECTRTGI table.¹³

Radius	r	$[2]_\ell$	$[2]_{\ell_x}$
SSGTI	$(2/r)$	$[1]_{\ell/s^2}$	$[1]_{\ell_x/s^2}$
ECTRTI	$(2/r)^2$	$[1]_{\ell/s^2}$	$[1]_{\ell_x/s^2}$
EXTRTI	$(2/r)^2$	$[1]_{\ell/s^2}$	$[1]_{\ell_x/s^2}$
ECTRTGI	$(2/r)^3$	$[1]_{\ell/s^2}$	$[1]_{\ell_x/s^2}$

FIG. 4. (Color online) (a) ambient isotropic E-space worldsheet has uniform IEMT in Cartesian space; (b) post ESCX transformation *angular isotropic* MWEPs with EXTRT (dark yellow horizontal arrow) and ECTRT (blue vertical arrows), ECTRTG (green vertical arrows), ECTRTI (blue arrows), ECTRTGI (light purple horizontal arrows) on a volume angle and radius plane figures.

4 Normalized MWEF function

Because there is no residual energy within the cE-fermion, the potential within the cE-fermion remains constant. Because the cE- and xE-fermions operate in different energy resolutions, the xE-fermion also has a constant potential. The normalized cE- and xE-fermions have unit potentials.

The potential in the E-boson region is an inverse distance function because the residual tensions are angular isotropic.¹⁴ The E-boson potential is the divergence of the AIRT; i.e., the E-boson potential is $P_M^b = \nabla \cdot [2/r^2]_{\ell/s^2}$. To conform with the unit potential of the normalized E-fermion at the radius $[2]_\ell$, the normalized E-boson potential is, ignoring the sign (refer to Appendix II.A.2 for details),

$$[P_M^b]_{\ell^2/s^2} = \int \left[\frac{2}{r^2} \right]_{\ell/s^2} dr = \left[\frac{2}{r} \right]_{\ell^2/s^2}. \quad (6)$$

Combining the normalized E-fermion and E-boson potentials, a normalized MWEF is

¹³ Note that the $[2]_\ell$ column intensities reference the $[1^2]_{\ell^2}$ unit area whereas the $[2]_{\ell_x}$ column intensities reference the $[1^2]_{\ell_x^2} = [(cH_0)^2]_{\ell^2}$ unit area.

¹⁴ The inverse distance function in this paper refers to the function's value is inversely proportional to the inter-object distance.

$$P_M(r) = \begin{cases} \frac{[2]_{\ell^3/s^2}}{[r]_{\ell}}, r \geq [2]_{\ell}; \\ [1]_{\ell^2/s^2}, r < [2]_{\ell} \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

with $[2]_{\ell}$ as the E-fermion core radius (the singularity location of the MWEP), $[1]_{\ell^2/s^2}$ as the normalized fermion potential, and $[2]_{\ell^3/s^2}$ as the E-boson interaction coupling constant.

5 Generic MWEP function

Real-world objects can have complex structures and various innate energy resolutions. a generic MWEP function is

$$P_M(r) = \begin{cases} \left[\frac{\alpha^b}{r} \right]_{\ell^2/s^2}, r \geq [R^m]_{\ell} \\ [\alpha^m]_{\ell^2/s^2}, r < [R^m]_{\ell} \end{cases}; \quad (8)$$

with R^m as the E-fermion or singularity radius, α^b and α^m as the interaction coupling functions for E-boson and E-fermion regions respectively. Note that both the α^b and the α^m can be complex functions in some higher-than-two-body (few-body) interaction systems.

D. Multiple E-domain pairs

Real-world ESCX transformations can involve multiple energy resolutions; each produces a pair of MWEPs embedded with complementary contractive and expansive energy resolutions; hereafter referred to as the energy domain, E-domain, or cE- and xE-domains respectively. The EIDIP framework posits that all energy entities, including matter, can possess multiple pairs of complementary xE- and cE-domain MWEPs; hereafter referred to as the multiple E-domain pairs (MEP) hypothesis.

1 E-domain spatial unit

Because an E-domain has an energy resolution limit, it has a quantized domain spatial unit (DSU), aka the NLU of that E-domain. Because paired cE- and xE-domains have complementary innate energy resolutions, they also have complementary DSUs. The higher the order of an E-domain, the shorter its cE-domain DSU and the longer its xE-domain DSU.

Moreover, because MWEPs are spherical and can be extrapolated from equation (1),¹⁵ their DSUs should relate to their E-fermion radii $[2]_{\ell}$, and the 32π term should be part of their compositions. With that, the EIDIP framework

¹⁵ Refer to Appendix II for details.

¹⁶ The 10+ EEPT presented in later sections affirms this DSU composition hypothesis. Note that $(32\pi)^{\#}c/2 \times R_0/(32\pi)^{\#} = 1/(64\pi)$. Because the speed of light is a physical constant from which the SI length unit meter is defined, these DSUs are also constants.

¹⁷ Subscript f and t denote reference- and target-centric respectively.

hypothesizes that the DSU formulas are $[(32\pi)^{\#}c/2]_m$ for xE-domain and $[R_0/(32\pi)^{\#}]_m$ for cE-domain with $\#$ as the E-domain order number, starting with zero (TABLE II).¹⁶ Note that the product of the complementary E-domains' DSUs is constant for all orders of E-domains

$$[2]_{Dc\#} \times [2]_{Dx\#} = 1/(16\pi). \quad (9)$$

From the IEMT term of equation (4), we can derive the zero-order cE-domain DSU $[1]_{\ell} = [R_0]_m$. Note that the E-domain order can have a fractional number; e.g., $[1]_{Dx2.5} = [(32\pi)^{2.5}c/2]_m$ shown in TABLE II.

Note that the higher the E-domain, the higher its post-MWEP-transformation residual membrane tension (RMT) energy:

$$E_{RMT}^{\#} = [2]_{Dx\#}/[(32\pi)_{Dc\#}] = (32\pi)^{2\#}c^2. \quad (10)$$

TABLE II. E-domain spatial unit example table.

E-domain	Domain Spatial Unit (DSU) in meter
D_{x5}	$[1]_{Dx5} = [(32\pi)^5c/2]_m$
$D_{x2.5}$	$[1]_{Dx2.5} = [(32\pi)^{2.5}c/2]_m$
D_{x2}	$[1]_{Dx2} = [(32\pi)^2c/2]_m$
D_{x0}	$[1]_{Dx0} = [c/2]_m$
D_{c0}	$[1]_{Dc0} = [R_0]_m$
D_{c2}	$[1]_{Dc2} = [R_0/(32\pi)^2]_m$
$D_{c2.5}$	$[1]_{Dc2.5} = [R_0/(32\pi)^{2.5}]_m$
D_{c5}	$[1]_{Dc5} = [R_0/(32\pi)^5]_m$

2 Inter-domain transfer coupling

The matter under measurement (target) and measuring apparatus (reference) can possess different MWEPs with different innate energy resolutions (IER); which can not only define the E-domains they operate in but also affect the measurements. If they operate in different E-domains, the target will appear to have a different spatial magnitude from the apparatus' point of view. I.e., the inter-domain DSU ratio, hereafter referred to as the inter-domain transfer coupling (IDTC or $T_c = \ell_t/\ell_f$ ¹⁷), affects the measurements.

3 cE- and xE-MWEPs

The ESCX transformation produces a pair of cE- and xE-MWEPs that operate in complementary energy resolutions. Because of the IDTC effect, the paired cE- and xE-bosons share the same *effective* coupling constant;¹⁸ i.e., they have the same gradient but not.¹⁹ Note that, although the xE-fermion overlaps with the cE-MWEP, the potential of the xE-fermion is still constant because cE- and

¹⁸ With reference to the same unit area; refer to Appendix II.C.1 for details.

¹⁹ The overlapped cE- and xE-MWEPs in FIG. 5 are meant to show the same gradient, but they are not to scale.

xE-MWEPs operate in different energy resolutions magnitude (FIG. 5).

Although the zero- and high- orders cE-bosons operate in different energy resolutions, they also have the same *effective* coupling constant because of the IDTC effect.²⁰ Hence, in theory, the high-order cE-bosons can extend the limit of the zero-order cE-boson (into the zero-order cE-fermion region). However, the higher the cE-MWEP order of matter, the higher its mass defect, and the lower its innate mass to induced gravity. Hence, the merged cE-boson could have magnitude singularity at the cE- fermion borders. Ditto for the merged xE-bosons.

The paired cE- and xE-MWEPs can independently interact with other MWEPs to produce EIDIPs that are orderly in long-range and turbulent around the singularities of underlying MWEPs. E.g., the strong force and covalent force are the turbulent EIDIP effects around the singularities of the quarks and atoms' cE-MWEPs; whereas the astronomical gravitational anomalies and gravitoelectromagnetism are the xE-EIDIP effects produced by the astronomical objects' xE-MWEPs.²¹

FIG. 5. (Color online) cE- and xE-MWEPs figure: cE-MWEP (orange line) comprising cE-fermion and cE-boson regions; xE-MWEP (blue dotted curve) comprising xE-fermion and xE-boson regions.¹⁹

4 E-domain speed limits and coupling constants

Paired cE- and xE-MWEPs have different E-boson couplings $[2]_{Dc\#^3/s^2}$ and $[2]_{Dx\#^3/s^2}$ respectively but both have the same $[2]_{Dx\#/s}$ speed limit (TABLE III); this is because the paired cE- and xE-MWEPs are interlocked, the speed of the paired MWEPs and derived EIDIP effects are limited by the domain EXRTT $[2]_{Dx\#/s}$. Hence, although the zero-order MWEP and EIDIP effects obey the speed of light axiom, the high-order MWEPs and EIDIP effects can

²⁰ With reference to the same unit area; Refer to Appendix II.C.2 for details.

²¹ Refer to the EEPTs in later sections.

²² Refer to the QG-MWRC EEPT presented in section VIII.F.4.

²³ The fast-than-light gravity speed $> [2 \times 10^{10}c]_{m/s}$ is purely based on observed Newtonian central forces of the solar system and binary stars; i.e., the speed calculations do not include the EIDIP effects. Hence, the calculated speeds contain omitting EIDIP effect induced artifacts (OEIAs)

travel faster than light at $[(32\pi)^\#c]_{m/s}$.

TABLE III. cE- and xE-MWEP speed and E-boson coupling table.

	E-boson coupling	Speed limit
cE-MWEP	$[2]_{Dc\#^3/s^2}$	$[2]_{Dx\#/s}$
xE-MWEP	$[2]_{Dx\#^3/s^2}$	$[2]_{Dx\#/s}$

In the EIDIP framework, gravitational potential comprises multiple orders of cE- and xE-MWEPs. The Newtonian gravitational potential comprises mostly the zero-order cE-MWEP with $[2R_0]_{m^3/s^2}$ gravitational constant and low intensity zero-order cE-EIDIP effects; both travel at the speed of light $[c]_{m/s}$. However, the higher the order of a gravitational potential, the lower its gravitational constant $[R_0/(32\pi)^\#]_{m^3/s^2}$, and the higher its speed limit $[(32\pi)^\#c]_{m/s}$.

Furthermore, the speed limits are also applicable to their domain harmonics. E.g., the fifth-order harmonic xE-EIDIP effects underlying the anomalous Milky Way rotation curve can travel at the fifth-order E-domain speed limit $[2]_{Dx^5/s} = [(32\pi)^5c]_{m/s} \approx [10^{10}c]_{m/s}$; ²² which compares to the observed faster-than-light gravity speed $> [2 \times 10^{10}c]_{m/s}$ [6].²³

E. Energy resolution dependent MWEP measurement

Although generic MWEP functions can be complex, this paper only deals with the simplest two-body interaction systems that employ MWEPs with a single shaping-parameter T_c . Because the matter under measurement (target-MWEP) and the measuring apparatus (reference-MWEP) can operate in different E-domains, the IDTC between them affects the MWEPs' measurements.

1 Inter-domain MWEP functions

Although a MWEP does not have a discontinuity singularity, a MWEP measured from different E-domains, inter-domain MWEP measurements, can have magnitude discontinuity singularity because the IDTC affects the inter-domain energy measurements.²⁴

Equation (7) can be rewritten to include the IDTC effect ($T_c = \ell_t/\ell_f$) for a *reference-centric* (in reference-DSU) target-MWEP as

$$P_M^t(r) = \begin{cases} [\frac{2T_c}{r}]_{\ell_f^2}, r \geq [2T_c]_{\ell_f} \\ [T_c]_{\ell_f^2}, r < [2T_c]_{\ell_f} \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

which could explain the approximately doubled magnitude deviation. Note that, the author of [6] stated that although the observed "absence of gravitational aberration" supports the observed faster-than-light gravity speed, it can be explained by the velocity-dependent interactions (aka gravitoelectromagnetic effect) hypothesis of general relativity.

²⁴ Refer to Appendix II.B for the inter-domain MWEP magnitude-discontinuity singularity derivation.

and reference-MWEP as

$$P_M^f(r) = \begin{cases} \left[\frac{2}{r} \right]_{\ell_f^2} \frac{\ell_f^2}{s^2}, & r \geq [2]_{\ell_f} \\ [1]_{\ell_f^2}, & r < [2]_{\ell_f} \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Equation (7) can be rewritten to include the IDTC effect for a *target*-centric (in target-DSU) target-MWEP as²⁵

$$P_M^t(r) = \begin{cases} \left[\frac{2}{r} \right]_{\ell_t^2} \frac{\ell_t^2}{s^2}, & r \geq [2]_{\ell_t} \\ [T_c]_{\ell_t^2}, & r < [2]_{\ell_t} \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

and reference-MWEP

$$P_M^f(r) = \begin{cases} \left[\frac{2}{T_c \times r} \right]_{\ell_f^2} \frac{\ell_f^2}{s^2}, & r \geq \left[\frac{2}{T_c} \right]_{\ell_t} \\ [1]_{\ell_f^2}, & r < \left[\frac{2}{T_c} \right]_{\ell_t} \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

The EEPTs presented in later sections employ target-centric EIDIP effects functions produced by the target-centric MWEP functions because the target-centric EIDIP functions produced magnitude scaling formulas show the commonalities between EEPTs more clearly.

Note that for both (reference- and target-centric) cases, there is a discontinuity singularity in the target-MWEP at $[2]_{\ell_t} = [2T_c]_{\ell_f}$ whereas the reference-MWEP has no magnitude-discontinuity at the singularity; this is because MWEPs interactions are at-point operations such that both target- and reference-MWEPs reference the same unit area. Hence, only the EXTRT portion of the target-coupling needs to be scaled with the IDTC; i.e., $[1]_{\ell^2} [2]_{\ell_t}^{EXTRT} = [1]_{\ell^2} [2T_c]_{\ell_f}^{EXTRT} / s^2$.

FIG. 6 depicts a pair of reference-centric inter-domain MWEPs for a $T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$ case. Note that the target-MWEP (blue line) has a magnitude-discontinuity singularity at $[2]_{\ell_t}$ whereas the reference-MWEP (red line) has no magnitude-discontinuity at the singularity. These singularities give the MWEP applications salient signatures.

FIG. 6. (Color online) $T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$ reference (red line) and target (blue line) MWEPs figure.^{26,27}

2 Intra-domain MWEP functions

In contrast to inter-domain MWEPs, intra-domain target- and reference-centric MWEPs share the same gravitational constant and NLU but differ in their E-fermion radii:²⁸ an intra-domain reference-centric target-MWEP function is

$$P_M^t(r) = \begin{cases} \left[\frac{2}{r} \right]_{\ell^2} \frac{\ell^2}{s^2}, & r \geq [2T_c]_{\ell} \\ [1]_{\ell^2}, & r < [2T_c]_{\ell} \end{cases}; \quad (15)$$

and reference-MWEP function is

$$P_M^f(r) = \begin{cases} \left[\frac{2}{r} \right]_{\ell^2} \frac{\ell^2}{s^2}, & r \geq [2]_{\ell} \\ [1]_{\ell^2}, & r < [2]_{\ell} \end{cases} \quad (16)$$

FIG. 7 depicts a pair of reference-centric intra-domain MWEP for a $T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$ case. Note that the target-MWEP magnitude ratio is T_c between the inter- and intra-domain cases. Hence, an inter-domain MWEP interactions can be treated as an intra-domain operation but with an additional T_c magnitude scaler term.

²⁵ The same as the generic MWEP function (equation (8)) with these parameters: $|\alpha_f^b| = |R_f^m| = 2/T_c$, $|\alpha_t^b| = |R_t^m| = 2$, $|\alpha_f^m| = 1$, and $|\alpha_t^m| = T_c$; subscripts *t* and *f* denote target- centric and reference-centric respectively.

²⁶ X-axis: radius in the target-DSU; Y-axis: magnitude in a normalized arbitrary unit [A.U.].

²⁷ Note that this figure only shows a half sphere of these MWEPs: the target-MWEP resides at origin whereas the reference-MWEP resides at $[15]_{\ell}$ on the radius axis.

²⁸ The same as the generic MWEP function (equation (8)) with these parameters: $|\alpha_f^m| = |\alpha_f^b| = 1$, $R_t^m = 2T_c$, $R_f^m = 2$, and $|\alpha_f^b| = |\alpha_t^b| = 2$; subscripts *t* and *f* denote target- centric and reference-centric respectively.

FIG. 7. (Color online) Reference-centric *Intra-domain* $T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$ reference- and target-MWEPs figure.²⁶

F. Normalized EIDIP function

Although generic MWEP functions can be complex, this paper only deals with the simplest two-body interaction systems that employ MWEPs with a single parameter T_c . In such a system, the interaction energy imbalance between these MWEPs produces a potential, named E-space inter-domain (intra-domain) interaction potential (EIDIP).²⁹

Per customary coordinate systems in physics,³⁰ FIG. 8 depicts a two-body interaction system in Cartesian and spherical coordinates such that the target-object is at the origin and the reference-object is on the polar axis (or the positive Z-axis). In such a system, the target- and reference-centric EIDIPs are the interaction energy difference between the left- and right-atmospheres of the target- and reference-MWEPs respectively.³¹ Note that the target- and reference-centric EIDIPs are different; i.e., EIDIPs are object-centric.³²

Because MWEPs are at-point (divergence of a point) spherical potentials, the interaction between them is also an at-point operation such that the dual-sphere volume integral element is reduced to $dV = drd\theta d\varphi$; this is because the volume element $r^2 \sin \theta$ is neutralized by the at-point region element limit $1/|r^2 \sin \theta|$ (refer to equation (83) in Appendix II.A.2 for details). With that, the dual-sphere volume integral of the target-centric EIDIP is simplified to

$$P_E(r_o) = \iiint_{\theta=0}^{\theta=\pi/2} \left\{ \left[P_M^{t \times f} \right]_{Z>0} - \left[P_M^{t \times f} \right]_{Z<0} \times f(\hat{z}) \right\} d\theta d\varphi dr_t; \quad (17)$$

²⁹ The name EIDIP is kept for its backward compatibility with my older papers. More accurately, it is a warped E-space inter-domain interaction potential (WEIDIP) or inter-domain gravitational interaction potential (IDGIP).

³⁰ A spherical coordinate system commonly used in physics (ISO convention): radial distance r , polar angle θ , and azimuth angle φ which commonly convert to Cartesian coordinates as: $x = r \sin \theta \cos \varphi$, $y = r \sin \theta \sin \varphi$, and $z = r \cos \theta$.

with r_o as the radial offset distance between the target and reference objects, $P_M^{t \times f} = P_M^f(r_f) \times P_M^t(r_t)$, r_t and r_f as the target- and reference-centric radius, and $f(\hat{z})$ as the dual-sphere interaction coupling (DSIC) function.³³ The simplest DSIC function is $f(\hat{z}) = \cos \theta$.³⁴ With that, because $\cos \theta$ is negative in the $\theta(\pi/2; \pi)$ range (i.e., $Z<0$ region), equation (17) can be rewritten with full range $\theta(0; \pi)$ as

$$P_E(r_o) = \iiint \left\{ P_M^f(r_f) \times P_M^t(r_t) \times \cos \theta \right\} d\theta d\varphi dr_t. \quad (18)$$

Because both the target- and the reference-MWEPs are angular isotropic, the interaction energy between them is symmetric about the Z-axis (FIG. 8). I.e., the azimuth angle φ integral can be replaced by the azimuth angle range 2π . Hence, equation (18) can be simplified to a Cartesian-grid-like 2D integral

$$P_E(r_o) = 2\pi \iint \left\{ P_M^f(r_f) \times P_M^t(r_t) \times \cos \theta \right\} d\theta dr_t. \quad (19)$$

G. Numerical integration EIDIP generation method

The EIDIP function (equation (19)) can be implemented by MATLAB numerical integral functions. To take advantage of shared math terms between the polar angle $\theta(0; \pi/2)$ and $\theta(\pi/2; \pi)$ regions (i.e., between the positive and negative Z regions), the EIDIP numerical integration formula used in this paper is

$$P_E(r_o) = 2\pi \iint_{\theta=0}^{\theta=\pi/2} \left[P_t(r_t) \times (P_f^p(r_f^p) - P_f^n(r_f^n)) \cos \theta \right] d\theta dr_t \quad (20)$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} P_t(r_t) &= \frac{\alpha_t^b}{r_t} (r_t \geq R_t^m) + \alpha_t^m (r_t < R_t^m), \\ P_f^p(r_f^p) &= \frac{\alpha_f^b}{r_f^p} (r_f^p \geq R_f^m) + \alpha_f^m (r_f^p < R_f^m), \\ P_f^n(r_f^n) &= \frac{\alpha_f^b}{r_f^n} (r_f^n \geq R_f^m) + \alpha_f^m (r_f^n < R_f^m), \\ r_f^p &= \sqrt{r_t^2 - 2r_t r_o \cos \theta + r_o^2}, \\ r_f^n &= \sqrt{r_t^2 + 2r_t r_o \cos \theta + r_o^2}; \end{aligned}$$

³¹ I.e., between the $Z<0$ ([L] in FIG. 8) and the $Z>0$ ([C]+[R]) regions for the target-centric EIDIP and between the [L]+[C] and [R] regions for the reference-centric EIDIP.

³² Because the interaction energy differs between the [R] and [L] regions, the interaction energy imbalances are different between the [L]+[C]-[R] and [R]+[C]-[L] regions.

³³ Aka Z-axis interaction coupling (ZAIC).

³⁴ The EIDIP is a differential potential in the Z-axis; hence, only the interaction energy projected on the Z-axis can affect the EIDIP; hence, $f(\hat{z}) = \cos \theta$.

with these parameters shown in FIG. 8,³⁵

- (1) r_t : target-centric radius (the integral radius to the target MWEP origin, range $(0, \infty)$);³⁶
- (2) 2π : target-centric azimuth angle integral factor because the EIDIP is symmetric with respect to the azimuth angle;
- (3) θ : target-centric polar angle, range $(0, \pi/2)$;
- (4) r_o : distance offset between target and reference objects (the distance variable of the EIDIP function);
- (5) r_f^p, r_f^n : reference-centric radii between the integration points I_p and I_n , and the reference MWEP origin at $Z = r_o$;
- (6) R_t^m, R_f^m : target and reference-centric E-fermion border radii;
- (7) α_t^m, α_f^m : target and reference-centric couplings of E-fermion regions (yellow disk regions);
- (8) α_t^p, α_f^p : target and reference-centric couplings of E-boson regions.

FIG. 8. (Color online) EIDIP numerical integration parameter diagram in spherical and Cartesian coordinates figure. [L], [C], [R] denote left ($Z < 0$, yellow-brown), center ($0 \leq Z < r_o$, light green), and right ($Z > r_o$, gray-green) interaction zones respectively.

H. Hybrid numerical and symbolic integration EIDIP generation method

To implement equation (20) in the MATLAB platform involves a long-range integral. However, a straightforward long-range numerical integral implementation could run for days and the results still not usable because of the

overwhelming errors accumulated from the long-range MATLAB numerical integration. Hence, symbolic integrations are preferred implementations because of computation time and accuracy especially for producing long-range EIDIP functions.

However, generating the symbolic integration formula for equation (20) is beyond the capability of MATLAB symbolic engine.³⁷ By necessity, I developed a hybrid numerical and symbolic integration method that could produce reasonably accurate EIDIP functions.

The normalized EIDIP functions used in this paper are generated by this dynamic dual-zone integral method: one inner numerical integration zone that covers *both* the target and the reference E-fermions (overlapped or not) and one outer symbolic integration zone that covers the rest where it only has the reference and target E-bosons. Furthermore, the zone boundary moves dynamically with the inter-object distance R_{oft} such that the symbolic integration zone always has the E-bosons only. Because the symbolic integration zone³⁸ only has to deal with the E-bosons' inverse distance functions,⁴⁵ equation (20) can be simplified for as

$$P_E^{sym}(r_o) = 2\pi\alpha_t^p\alpha_f^p \oint \left[\frac{\cos\theta}{r_t} \left(\frac{1}{r_f^p} - \frac{1}{r_f^n} \right) \right] d\theta dr_t; \quad (21)$$

which has a symbolic integral formula:³⁹

$$\begin{aligned} P_E^{sym}(r_o) &= -2\pi\alpha_t\alpha_f \int_0^{\pi/2} \left[\frac{\cos\theta}{r_o} \right. \\ &\times \left(\operatorname{atanh} \frac{-r_o + R_s \cos\theta}{\sqrt{r_o^2 - 2r_o R_s \cos\theta + R_s^2}} \right. \\ &+ \operatorname{atanh} \frac{r_o + R_s \cos\theta}{\sqrt{r_o^2 + 2r_o R_s \cos\theta + R_s^2}} \\ &- \operatorname{atanh} \frac{-r_o + R_e \cos\theta}{\sqrt{r_o^2 - 2r_o R_e \cos\theta + R_e^2}} \\ &\left. \left. - \operatorname{atanh} \frac{r_o + R_e \cos\theta}{\sqrt{r_o^2 + 2r_o R_e \cos\theta + R_e^2}} \right) \right] d\theta \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

with R_s, R_e as the symbolic integration starting and ending radii.⁴⁰ Note that the symbolic integral formula was produced by the MATLAB 2007b edition that has a built-in MAPLE math engine.⁴¹

polar angle integration zone partition MATLAB function code, refer to Appendix VII.A.

³⁹ For symbolic radial and numerical polar angle integration MATLAB function code, refer to Appendix VII.C.

⁴⁰ In the MATLAB programs used by this paper to generate the EIDIP, R_e is assigned with a large 10^{128} value to emulate an infinite radius because the *inf* assignment produced errors. Refer to Appendix VII.A.

⁴¹ The later MATLAB editions that use a MuPAD engine cannot produce the symbolic formula with the same MATLAB program shown in Appendix VII.D.

³⁵ Aka: $r_t = r$, $r_o = R_{oft}$, $r_f^p = R_f^p$, and $r_f^n = R_f^n$ in my older papers and the MATLAB program shown in Appendix VII.D.

³⁶ Because computation power limitation, in the MATLAB simulations, the upper range is set to 10^{16} for the numerical integration only method; the upper range is extended to 10^{128} for the hybrid numerical and symbolic integration method presented in the next section.

³⁷ Referring to MATLAB 2007 to 2010 editions.

³⁸ The numerical-symbolic integration zones' border is $Max(R_t^m, R_{oft} + R_f^m) + margin$; for the symbolic radial and numerical

III. NORMALIZED TWO-BODY INTERACTION SYSTEM EIDIP AND DERIVED EFFECTS

A. Normalized two-body system single parameter nonlinear EIDIP function

This paper employs the simplest normalized EIDIP with the following presets:

$$\begin{cases} |\alpha_f^p| = 2/T_c, & |\alpha_t^b| = 2 \\ |\alpha_f^m| = 1, & |\alpha_t^m| = T_c \\ |R_f^m| = 2/T_c, & |R_t^m| = 2, \end{cases} \quad (23)$$

with T_c as the shaping-parameter. With them, equation (20) can be rewritten with the inter-object distance r_o and shaping-parameter T_c as⁴²

$$P_E(r_o, T_c) = 2\pi \oint_{\theta=0}^{\theta=\frac{\pi}{2}} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \cos \theta \left[\frac{2}{r} (r \geq 2) + T_c (r < 2) \right] \\ \left(\frac{2}{T_c r_f^p} (r_f^p \geq \frac{2}{T_c}) + (r_f^p < \frac{2}{T_c}) \right) \\ - \left(\frac{2}{T_c r_f^n} (r_f^n \geq \frac{2}{T_c}) + (r_f^n < \frac{2}{T_c}) \right) \end{array} \right\} d\theta dr. \quad (24)$$

The normalized EIDIP function P_E is a nonlinear function of distance and the T_c is the only parameter that affects the shapes of P_E functions (FIG. 9).

FIG. 9. (Color online) Short-range target-centric EIDIP functions figure.^{26,43}

In a log-log graph (FIG. 10), the ascending P_E^+ functions

⁴² Refer to Appendix VII.B for the MATLAB numerical integration program used in this paper. Note that $r_t \rightarrow r$ and $r_o \rightarrow R_{oft}$ in the MATLAB program.

⁴³ $T_c = 32\pi$ (blue line), $T_c = (32\pi)^{1/2}$ (green line), $T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$ (red line), and $T_c = 1$ (black dot-dashed line).

⁴⁴ Slope value between two magenta vertical dashed lines in the figure below: 1.0000 for $T_c = 32\pi$, 1.0000 for $T_c = (32\pi)^{1/2}$, 1.0001 for $T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$, 1.0023 for $T_c = 1$ cases; MATLAB error tolerance= 10^{-8} .

for various T_c are linear functions all with gradients of approximately one;⁴⁴ which indicate these P_E^+ can be approximated by linear functions⁴⁵

$$P_E^+ \propto r. \quad (25)$$

FIG. 10. (Color online) Ascending segment P_E^+ are linear functions in a log-log plane all with gradients of approximately one figure.^{26,43,44,46}

In a log-log graph (FIG. 11), the long-range (conformal region) EIDIP P_E^∞ functions for various T_c are also linear functions all with gradients of negative one approximately;⁴⁷ which indicate these P_E^∞ can be approximated by inverse distance functions:

$$P_E^\infty \propto r^{-1}. \quad (26)$$

⁴⁵ The monomials relationship of the form $y = ax^b$ appear as straight lines in a log-log graph, with the power and constant terms corresponding to the slope and intercept of the lines [48].

⁴⁶ "Slp: value" in the figure legend denotes the linear slope between two magenta vertical dotted lines.

⁴⁷ Slope value between two magenta vertical dotted lines: -1.00000001710 for $T_c = 32\pi$, -1.00000016566 for $T_c = (32\pi)^{1/2}$, -1.00000048437 for $T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$, -1.00000318504 for $T_c = 1$ case; MATLAB error tolerance= 10^{-22} .

FIG. 11. (Color online) Long-range P_E^∞ are linear functions in a log-log plane all with gradients of negative one approximately figure.^{26,43,46,48}

1 Asymmetric target- and reference-centric EIDIP functions near singularity

In contrast to conventional models, the short-range near-singularity EIDIPs, apart from $T_c = 1$ case, are object-asymmetric because the target-centric EIDIP: [R+C]-[L] differ from the reference-centric EIDIP: [L+C]-[R] (FIG. 8).³² I.e., the reference-centric T_c have inverted values from the corresponding target-centric T_c such that they produce different EIDIPs shown in FIG. 12 (FIG. 9).⁴⁹

FIG. 12. (Color online) Short-range reference-centric EIDIP functions figure.^{26,43}

2 Long-range EIDIP are object-symmetric

Although short-range EIDIPs are object-asymmetric, long-range EIDIPs are object-symmetric; hence, long-range target- and reference-EIDIP can be approximated by inverse distance functions (FIG. 11: target-centric, FIG. 13: reference-centric).

FIG. 13. (Color online) Long-range reference-centric P_E^∞ are linear functions in a log-log plane figure.

Note that the short-range object-asymmetric and long-range object-symmetric characteristics of the EIDIPs apply to the EIDIPs derived effects.

3 System-differential-EIDIP

The deviation between a target-centric and corresponding reference-centric EIDIP is a system-differential-EIDIP (SDEP, or $P_{E[D]}$); i.e., with reference to FIG. 8, the SDEP is the [R-L] potential.⁵⁰ Note that the potential difference between the [R] and [L] zones is turbulent at short distances and close to zero at long distances (FIG. 14).⁵¹

FIG. 14. (Color online) Short-range system-differential-EIDIP ($P_{E[D]}$) functions figure.^{26,43}

⁴⁸ Note that, although these various T_c long-range P_E^∞ have a different magnitude in the *target*-DSU X-axis grid presentation of FIG. 11, they are *aligned*, i.e., have the same magnitude, in a *reference*-DSU X-axis grid presentation.

⁴⁹ Note that, apart from $T_c = 1$ case, the other three reference-centric EIDIPs have maxima at the $[2]_{DSU}$, the same as the target-centric EIDIPs shown in FIG. 9.

⁵⁰ The target-centric EIDIP is [R+C-L] potential whereas the reference-centric EIDIP is [L+C-R] potential; hence, the SDEP is [2R-2L] potential normalized by one-half, [R-L].

⁵¹ Note that, apart from $T_c = 1$ case (black dot-dashed line, FIG. 14), these SDEP functions have minima of $1.4/\sqrt{T_c}$ to $1.5/\sqrt{T_c}$ approximately at $[2]_{DSU}$.

4 System-core-EIDIP

The inter-object region ([C] of FIG. 8) EIDIP is a system-core-EIDIP (SCEP, or $P_{E[C]}$). FIG. 15 depicts SCEP functions for various T_c as examples.⁵²

FIG. 15. (Color online) Short-range system-core-EIDIP ($P_{E[C]}$) functions figure.^{26,43}

5 Long-range EIDIP effects are orderly, but short-range EIDIP effects are turbulent

Because of MWEPs' quantized-singularities, short-range EIDIPs and derived effects (EIDIP effects) are turbulent near the MWEPs' singularities $[2]_{DSU}$ and can even change signs in these regions, hereafter referred to as the near-singularity turbulent EIDIP effect (NSTEE) region.⁵³ However, long-range (conformal region) EIDIP effects are orderly and can be approximated by various power functions.

B. Normalized two-body system single shaping-parameter nonlinear EIDIP-gradient function

The gradient of the EIDIP,

$$P_d \equiv d(P_E)/dr, \quad (27)$$

is a single shaping-parameter T_c nonlinear function of inter-object distance. Hence, P_d functions have rigid shapes when their T_c are set (FIG. 16 for various T_c as examples).⁵⁴ Note that P_d functions have multiple singularities, one near $[2]_{DSU}$ (target-centric) and one in the positive region. The multi-singularity signature provides a definitive falsifiability for P_d applications.

⁵² Note that, apart from $T_c = 1$ case, the SCEP have maxima at $[2]_{DSU}$; and that the higher the T_c , the higher and the shaper are the peaks.

⁵³ In this paper, the NSTEE can be a noun (e.g., "the NSTEEs induce these phenomena") or adjective (e.g., "in the NSTEE regions"). The "short-range" is in term of DSU and relative; e.g., in the $D \times 5$ -domain, a short-range in the R_{x5} -DSU, e.g., $[2]_{R_{x5}} = [(32\pi)^5 c]_m$, is a large distance.

⁵⁴ Note that only one of them, $T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$ (red), is used in the EEPTs presented in this paper.

FIG. 16. (Color online) Short-range target-centric EIDIP-gradient P_d functions figure.^{26,43,55}

Because of long-range $P_E^\infty \propto r^{-1}$ (equation (26)), a long-range EIDIP-gradient P_d^∞ can be approximated by an inverse distance square (IDS) function⁵⁶

$$P_d^\infty = \alpha_c \times r^{-2} \quad (28)$$

with α_c as the coupling (of an IDS force) function. With that,

$$P_{dR2} \equiv P_d \times r^2; \quad (29)$$

and a long-range P_{dR2}^∞ can be approximated by a constant

$$P_{dR2}^\infty \propto r^0. \quad (30)$$

However, NSTEE region P_{dR2} are not constant (FIG. 17). Such behaviors give clues why conventional constant coupling models need additional form factors or different models to describe the turbulent physical behaviors in the NSTEE regions.⁵⁷

⁵⁵ Note that the differential operator is approximated by the MATLAB gradient function to generate the data in this figure.

⁵⁶ The IDS function in this paper refers to the function's value is inversely proportional to the square of the inter-object distance.

⁵⁷ E.g., the long-range constants electric and magnetic couplings models require separate effective strong and residual-strong couplings models to describe their turbulent behaviors in the NSTEE regions; refer to the effective coupling EEPTs in section VIII.E.

FIG. 17. (Color online) Short-range *target-centric* P_{dR2} functions figure.^{26,43}

FIG. 19. (Color online) Short-range system-differential-EIDIP-gradient $P_{d[D]}$ functions figure.^{26,58,43}

1 Asymmetric reference-centric EIDIP-gradient functions

Because short-range EIDIPs are object-asymmetric, short-range EIDIP-gradient functions are also object-asymmetric. FIG. 18 depicts the reference-centric EIDIP-gradient functions for various T_c which differ from the target-centric EIDIP-gradient functions (FIG. 16).

FIG. 18. (Color online) Short-range reference-centric P_d functions figure.^{26,58,43}

2 System-differential-EIDIP-gradient

FIG. 19 depicts system-differential-EIDIP-gradient (SDEPG, or $P_{d[D]}$) functions for various T_c . Note that, apart from $T_c = 1$ case, which is a flat line function as expected, $P_{d[D]}$ functions change signs at two locations, one is at $[2]_{DSU}$ and one is at less than $[2]_{DSU}$.

⁵⁸ Function magnitudes have been scaled with $1/T_c$ to show details.

3 System-core-EIDIP-gradient

FIG. 20 depicts the system-core-EIDIP-gradient (SCEPG, or $P_{d[C]}$) functions for various T_c . Note that, apart from $T_c = 1$ case, these $P_{d[C]}$ functions change signs at $[2]_{DSU}$ (target-centric) and have multiple minimum and maximum locations.

FIG. 20. (Color online) Short-range system-core-EIDIP-gradient $P_{d[C]}$ functions figure.^{26,58,43}

C. Normalized two-body system single shaping-parameter nonlinear Angular EIDIP function

An angular EIDIP (P_r) per radian is

$$P_r \equiv \frac{2\pi r}{2\pi} P_E = r P_E, \quad (31)$$

a single shaping-parameter T_c nonlinear function of distance. Hence, P_r functions have rigid shapes when their T_c are set (FIG. 21).⁵⁴

FIG. 21. (Color online) Short-range target-centric P_r functions figure.^{26,43}

Note that P_r functions are asymptotic at short distances and conformal at long distances. This signature provides definitive falsifiability for P_r applications. Because the ascending-segment P_E^+ functions are linear functions (equation (25)), the ascending-segment P_r^+ are quadratic power functions:

$$P_r^+ \propto r^2. \quad (32)$$

Furthermore, because both the target- and the reference-centric long-range P_E^∞ are inverse distance functions (equation (26)), long-range P_r^∞ are constant functions:

$$P_r^\infty \propto r^0. \quad (33)$$

1 Asymmetrical reference-centric angular EIDIP functions

Because short-range EIDIPs are object-asymmetric, short-range angular EIDIP functions are also object-asymmetric. Shown in FIG. 22 are reference-centric angular EIDIP functions for various T_c which differ from the target-centric angular EIDIP functions shown in FIG. 21. Note that the higher the T_c of angular EIDIP functions, the higher and the sharper their spikes at $[2]_{DSU}$ inter-object distance.

FIG. 22. (Color online) Short-range reference-centric P_r functions figure.^{26,43}

2 Angular system-differential-EIDIP

FIG. 23 depicts angular system-differential-EIDIP (ASDEP, or $P_{r[D]}$) functions for various T_c . Note that, apart from $T_c = 1$ case, these $P_{r[D]}$ functions have minima at $[2]_{DSU}$ and the higher the T_c , the deeper the dips.

FIG. 23. (Color online) Short-range angular system-differential-EIDIP $P_{r[D]}$ functions figure.^{26,43}

3 Angular system-core-EIDIP

FIG. 24 depicts angular system-core-EIDIP (ASCEP, or $P_{r[C]}$) functions for various T_c . Note that, apart from $T_c = 1$ case, $P_{r[C]}$ functions have maxima at $[2]_{DSU}$, and the higher the T_c of $P_{r[C]}$ functions, the higher their peaks.

FIG. 24. (Color online) Short-range angular system-core-EIDIP $P_{r[C]}$ functions figure.^{26,43}

D. Higher order EIDIP function examples

An angular EIDIP-gradient,

$$P'_r \equiv \frac{d(P_E \times r)}{dr} = P_d \times r + P_E, \quad (34)$$

is a second-order EIDIP function. To depict an inverse distance potential $P'_r \equiv \alpha_c/r$, the coupling function

$$\alpha_c = rP'_r = P_d r^2 + P_r, \quad (35)$$

is a second-order EIDIP coupling (SEPC) function with $P_{dR2} = P_d r^2$ as the irrotational coupling component and P_r as the rotational coupling component.

FIG. 25 and FIG. 26 depict target and reference-centric SEPC functions respectively for various T_c . Note that, although short-range rP'_r functions are turbulent, long-range rP'_r values diminish with distance. Although long-range $P_d r^2$ and P_r settle to similar strength constants with opposite signs, the sum of them is an inverse distance function based on MATLAB simulations;⁵⁹ i.e., the long-range $rP'_r \propto r^{-1}$ (FIG. 56).

FIG. 25. (Color online) Short-range *target*-centric SEPC rP'_r functions figure.^{26,43}

FIG. 26. (Color online) Short-range *reference*-centric SEPC rP'_r functions figure.^{26,43,58}

1 Second-order angular system-EIDIPs

Second-order angular system-EIDIPs include a second-order angular system-differential-EIDIP (SASDE, or $rP'_{r[D]}$; FIG. 27) and second-order angular system-core-EIDIP (SASCE, or $rP'_{r[C]}$; FIG. 28). Note that, apart from $T_c = 1$ case, both the $rP'_{r[D]}$ and the $rP'_{r[C]}$ change sign at $[2]_{DSU}$.

⁵⁹ Refer to FIG. 56 in section VIII.E.5 for details.

FIG. 27. (Color online) Short-range SASDE ($rP'_{r[D]}$) functions figure.^{43,58}

FIG. 28. (Color online) Short-range SASCE $rP'_{r[C]}$ functions figure.^{43,58}

IV. MWEP AND EIDIP EFFECTS INDUCED FORCES

In the EIDIP framework, apart from the gravitational acceleration, the interaction between objects produced two types of first order accelerations:

- (1) G_{MGA} : MWEP (gravitational potential) gradient induced acceleration (MGA) and coupling (MGC); i.e., various orders gravitational accelerations are MGAs and gravitational couplings are MGCs;
- (2) G_{PGA} : EIDIP-gradient induced acceleration (PGA) or coupling (PGC), an *irrotational* component of MWEP interaction; e.g., interatomic covalent forces are PGAs whereas the effective residual-strong coupling is a PGC;
- (3) G_{APA} : Angular EIDIP induced acceleration (APA) or coupling (APC), a *rotational* component of the

interaction; e.g., the strong force and Pioneer 10/11 sunward anomalous accelerations are APAs whereas the effective strong coupling is an APC.

These forces can be described by inverse distance square laws with these coupling functions

$$\begin{aligned} G_{MGC} &= G_{MGA} \times r^{-2}, \\ G_{PGC} &= G_{PGA} \times r^{-2}, \\ G_{APC} &= G_{APA} \times r^{-2}. \end{aligned} \quad (36)$$

Note that some long-range EIDIP effects are already described by classical couplings (e.g., Newton's and Coulomb's constants); this is because, although these couplings can be distance-variant and object-asymmetric in NSTEE regions, they are stable (approximately constant) and object-symmetric at long distances.

1 Source of gravity

The EIDIP framework posits that gravitational potential comprises various orders of MWEPs and the Newtonian gravitational potential comprises mostly the Dc0-domain MWEP; each MWEP has a quantized (nonzero) singularity instead of an at-origin-singularity of the Newtonian gravitational potential. I.e., the Newtonian gravitational acceleration is mostly the Dc0-domain G_{MGA} with a coupling constant $G_{MGC} = [2]_{Dc0^3/s^2} = [2R_0]_{m^3/s^2}$, the gravitational *constant* of the EIDIP framework (MGC hypothesis); i.e., the true constant portion of the Newtonian gravitational “constant”. With that, the MWEP equation (7) can be rewritten for the gravitational potential in SI base units as⁶⁰

$$P_M(r) = \begin{cases} \frac{[2R_0]_{m^3/s^2}}{r}, & r \geq [2R_0]_m, \\ [1]_{m^2/s^2}, & r < [2R_0]_m \end{cases} \quad (37)$$

with $[2R_0]_m = [2]_{Dc0}$ as the Dc0-fermion core radius. Note that $[2R_0]_{m^3/s^2} = [2R_0]_{m/s^2} [1]_{m^2}$ reveals the relationship between the gravitational constant and the isotropic E-space linear tension (IELT) $[R_0]_{m/s^2}$.

Note that $[2R_0]_{m^3/s^2}$ equals 99.43% of the 2014 CODATA-recommended gravitational constant value $[2]$, and the remaining 0.57% Newtonian gravitational constant deviation (NGCD) can be filled by the EIDIP effects couplings; e.g., the long-range inter-atomic covalent force coupling.⁶¹

In the EIDIP framework, matter possesses multiple orders of MWEPs or gravitational potentials and the higher the order, the faster the speed. I.e., the high order gravities can travel faster than light. E.g., the Dx5-harmonic gravitational interaction effects underlying the anomalous Milky Way rotation curve (MWRC) travel at the speed of $[2]_{Dx5/s} = [(32\pi)^5 c]_{m/s} \cong [10^{10} c]_{m/s}$;²² which compares to the observed faster-than-light gravity speed >

⁶⁰ Refer to Appendix II.C.3 for the gravitational potential derivation.

⁶¹ Refer to the NGCD EEPT in section Newtonian gravitational constant and $[2R_0]_{m^3/s^2}$ deviation source VI.B.

$[2 \times 10^{10} c]_{m/s}$ [6].²³

Another way to derive the gravitational potential is from a volume angle point of view. As the sound pressure is a *local pressure deviation* from the *ambient*, the gravitational potential is the *local tension deviation* between the angular isotropic residual tensions (AIRT) flux and *ambient* isotropic E-space tension. Refer to Appendix II.C.3 for details.

B. EIDIP-gradient induced acceleration

Although the long-range EIDIP-gradient induced accelerations have constant couplings $G_{PGC}^{\infty} \propto r^{-2} P_d^{\infty} \cong \text{cnst}$ (equation (30)), the NSTEE region G_{PGC} can be attractive, repulsive, and change signs (FIG. 17).

Note that the $T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4} G_{PGA}$ underlies various physical phenomena; e.g., internucleon residual-strong force, interatomic covalent force, and meter-range G_{PGC}^{∞} contributes to the Newtonian gravitational constant measurements.⁶² The $T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4} G_{PGA}$ induced force has these characteristics (FIG. 29):

- (1) At less than $[1.145]_{DSU}$ distance, it is repulsive (positive region) and saturates around $[0.63]_{DSU}$ instead of reaching infinity at the origin;
- (2) At longer than $[1.145]_{DSU}$ distance, it is attractive (negative region) and highly attractive between $[1.25]_{DSU}$ and $[4]_{DSU}$;
- (3) The long-distance G_{PGA} can be approximated by an inverse distance square function because of the $G_{PGC}^{\infty} \cong \text{cnst}$.

FIG. 29. (Color online) Short-range G_{PGA} for $T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$ case figure.

C. Angular EIDIP induced acceleration

As the angular momentum of inertia (MOI) depends on the objects' spin axes configurations, the types of angular

⁶² Refer to the EIDIP-gradient effect phenomenological tests presented in section VI.

⁶³ Refer to the NCD EEPT in section VIII.A.

⁶⁴ Refer to the PSAA EEPT in section VII.C.

EIDIP effects also depend on the interaction moments of inertia (IMOI) of involved objects. E.g., in neutron charge distribution measurements, angular EIDIP effects P_r appear as a *coupling function* $G_{APC}(P_r)$.⁶³ Whereas in the Pioneer 10/11 spacecraft's sunward acceleration anomalies, the angular EIDIP effect P_r appears as a *force function* $G_{APA}(P_r)$.⁶⁴

1 Angular EIDIP effect induced force G_{APA}

Angular EIDIP induced accelerations G_{APA} are asymptotic at short distances and conformal at long distances.

Note that the $T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4} G_{APA}$ underlies various physical phenomena; e.g., interquark strong force, interplanetary Pioneer 10/11 spacecraft's sunward anomalous acceleration, and interstellar Milky Way rotation curve anomalies.⁶⁵ The $T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4} G_{APA}$ induced forces have these characteristics (FIG. 30):

- (1) At less than $[2.16]_{DSU}$ distances, the G_{APA} decreases with distance; at less than $[1]_{DSU}$ distances, the G_{APA} exhibits an *asymptotic* behavior and can be approximated by a quadratic power function;⁶⁶
- (2) Further from the acme at $[2.16]_{DSU}$, the G_{APA} exhibits an energy leaky *color confinement* behavior: descends slowly first and then settles to a constant.⁶⁷

FIG. 30. (Color online) Short-range $G_{APA}(P_r)$ for $T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$ figure.

2 Angular EIDIP effect induced coupling G_{APC}

The second-order EIDIP coupling (SEPC) function (Equation (35)), can be reformulated to represent an inverse distance square force function

$$\alpha_c/r^2 = P_d + P_E/r, \quad (38)$$

⁶⁵ Refer to the angular EEPTs in section VII.

⁶⁶ Refer to equations (32) and (60).

⁶⁷ Refer to equations (33) and (61).

with P_d as the irrotational component $G_{PGA}(P_d) \leftarrow G_{PGC}(r^2 P_d)$ and P_E/r as the rotational component $G_{APA}(P_E/r) \leftarrow G_{APC}(P_r)$.

Note that the $T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4} G_{APC}(P_r)$ produced various physical phenomena of the 10+ EEPs presented in later sections; e.g., the internucleon effective strong coupling.⁶⁸ The forces induced by $T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4} G_{APA}(P_E/r)$ have these characteristics (FIG. 31):

- (1) It saturated at approximately $[0.65]_{DSU}$ instead of reaching the singularity at the origin;
- (2) It is approximately an inverse distance square function at a long distance.⁶⁹

FIG. 31. (Color online) Short-range $G_{APA}(P_E/r)$ for $T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$ figure.

3 Angular EIDIP axis-asymmetric nudging effect

For a pair of orbiting or spinning objects, their system IMOJ composition (e.g., orbital plane inclination angles or angle between spin axes) complicates the calculation of their angular EIDIP effects.

For example, in a two-body system (FIG. 32) where a reference object is spinning around the X-axis and a static target object with an inclination angle δ ,⁷⁰ the interaction energy is asymmetrical to the Y-Z plane in the original frame (black axes, FIG. 32) which complicates P_E calculations. However, with a rotated Z-axis that passes through both objects, polar- and azimuth-angle interaction energies are symmetrical in this rotated frame (green axes, FIG. 32) and complexities of P_E integration are reduced.

FIG. 32. (Color online) G_{APA} strength with an inclination angle δ figure (black axes depict the original frame whereas green axes depict the rotated frame).

In such a system, the complexity of the inter-object P_E integration in the rotated frame (green arrow, FIG. 32) is the same as the non-inclined case but with a stretched inter-object distance r_δ :

$$P_E(r_\delta) = 2\pi \iint_{\theta_\delta=0}^{\theta_\delta=\pi} \{P_M^f \times P_M^t \times \cos \theta_\delta\} dr_\delta d\theta_\delta. \quad (39)$$

From which we can infer an on-rotation-plane $G_{APA}^p(r, \delta) \propto P_E(r_\delta) r_\delta \cos \delta \times \cos \delta$ (blue arrow, FIG. 32) and ortho-rotation-plane $G_{APA}^o(r, \delta) \propto r_\delta \cos \delta P_E(r_\delta) \times \sin \delta$ (dark green arrow, FIG. 32) with δ as the inclination angle and $r = r_\delta \cos \delta$ as the ortho-rotation-axis radius.⁷¹ I.e., in this example,

$$\begin{aligned} G_{APA}^p(r, \delta) &\propto G_{APA}(r_\delta) \times \cos \delta^2, \\ G_{APA}^o(r, \delta) &\propto G_{APA}(r_\delta) \times \sin 2\delta; \end{aligned} \quad (40)$$

with $G_{APA}(r_\delta) = r_\delta P_E(r_\delta)$. Because the conformal region G_{APA}^∞ is distance-invariant, i.e., the $G_{APA}^\infty(r_\delta) \cong G_{APA}^\infty(r) \cong \text{cnst}$, these formulas can be rewritten for the conformal region as

$$\begin{aligned} G_{APA}^p(r, \delta) &\propto G_{APA}^\infty(r) \times \cos \delta^2, \\ G_{APA}^o(r, \delta) &\propto G_{APA}^\infty(r) \times \sin 2\delta. \end{aligned} \quad (41)$$

In the examples above, the angular EIDIP effects are *axis-asymmetric*; i.e., although the effect of the inter-object distance is neglectable in the long-range conformal G_{APA}^∞ region, the inclination angle effects on their G_{APA}^p and G_{APA}^o

⁶⁸ Refer to the section VIII.E.

⁶⁹ Because of $P_E^\infty \propto r^{-1}$ (equation (26)).

⁷⁰ Or the reference object orbiting around the static target object with an inclination angle δ .

⁷¹ Like the normalized P_r is in radian unit, these normalized G_{APA}^p and G_{APA}^o are also in radian unit; i.e., the angular velocity effect is excluded from their calculations. Note that in the extreme case where $\delta = \pi/2$, i.e., both objects are on the spin axis, both the G_{APA}^p and the G_{APA}^o are zero.

However, the relative angular velocity ω should have an additional twisting effect on the inter-object EIDIP, the twisting EIDIP effects, e.g., $P_T \propto \omega G_{APA}^p$, that needs further research.

⁷² Note that these formulas presume point mass models; for distance-variant mass models, different spin configurations, or ortho-radial velocity applications, they could have different formulas; refer to equation (78) in section VIII.G.3 for example.

components are not neglectable.

These axis-asymmetric angular EIDIP effects can nudge the reference object's inclination angle to a preferred position. E.g., in the first example where the $G_{APA}^o(r, \delta) \propto \sin 2\delta$, the gradient of G_{APA}^o has opposite signs for $\delta \geq \pi/4$ and $\delta < \pi/4$ regions; i.e., the effect of which can nudge the inclination angle up or down depending on its initial position. These nudging effects are angular EIDIP axis-asymmetric nudging (AEAAN) effects examples.

Energy conservation can also induce some AEAAN effects. Note that some angular EIDIP effects, e.g., $G_{APA}(P_r)$, are energy-leaky; i.e., they consume energy to maintain their settle-to-constant behaviors. Hence, in a passive interaction system that lacks new energy injection, the energy leaky $G_{APA}(P_r)$ could nudge system IMO to a less energy-leaky kind, a passive AEAAN effect, and in the process, appear as relativistic *dragging* effects (e.g., the *frame dragging* effects of a rotating gravitating mass). Whereas, in an active interaction system that is able to acquire kinetic energy, the AEAAN effect could nudge the system IMO to absorb the extra kinetic energy.

The AEAAN effect can also produce quantum behaviors; this is because AEAAN effects can nudge inclination angles between the energy field directions of measurement apparatuses and the spin directions of the target particles to preferred directions. I.e., the AEAAN effects can coerce the physical possibilities of the test particles (a range of spin directions) into a single possibility (e.g., the preferred inclination angle direction) locally and gives the appearance of the local quantum decoherence and entanglement measurements in the distance (refer to section X.D.18 more details).

D. Object- and systemic-EIDIPs preferred distances misalignment induced effects

In a two-body interaction system composed of similar mass and mobility (SMM-system) objects, its systemic-EIDIP effects are more visible than a high mass ratio system (HMR-system) such that the much heavier object is relatively immobile because of the much closer center-of-mass. In the SMM system, the effects of the object- and systemic- EIDIPs' preferred inter-object distances (OSPD) misalignments are more notable.

1 OSPD misalignment induced oscillation in an irrotational interaction system

In a two-body irrotational interaction system, especially an SMM-system, objects tend to stay apart at the distance where the irrotational system-core-EIDIP-gradient ($P_{d[C]}$) is minimum (the most attractive distance; note that there are multiple local minima locations as shown in FIG. 20). Concurrently, these objects also tend to stay apart at the distance where the irrotational system-differential-EIDIP-gradient ($P_{d[D]}$) is zero (the most balanced distance; note

that there are multiple zero-crossing locations, most with steep local gradients, as shown in FIG. 19). If these two distances are not aligned, the inter-object distance may oscillate between the preferred locations because of internal or external dynamics and disturbances; hereafter referred to as the *irrotational* part of the OSPD-misalignment oscillation (OSPDMO) hypothesis.

2 OSPD misalignment induced oscillation in a rotational interaction system

In a two-body rotational interaction system, especially an SMM-system, objects tend to stay apart at the distance where the rotational angular system-core-EIDIP ($P_{r[C]}$) is maximum (most attractive distances for most of T_c are at $[2]_{DSU}$ as shown in FIG. 24). Concurrently, the objects also tend to stay apart at the distance where the rotational angular system-differential-EIDIP ($P_{r[D]}$) is zero (most balanced distance for most of T_c are at less than $[2]_{DSU}$ as shown in FIG. 23). If these two distances are not aligned, the inter-object distance may oscillate radially between these preferred locations while rotating and induces an orbital-radial oscillation (ORO) because of internal or external dynamics and disturbances; hereafter referred to as the *rotational* part of the OSPDMO hypothesis.

3 High energy OSPDMO induced effects

The second-order angular system-EIDIP effects (FIG. 27 and FIG. 28) are more visible in high-momentum-swing-by interactions; in which the inter-object distances are time-varying, and the large momentum of the swing-by can amplify the OSPDMO.⁷³ E.g., the amplified OSPDMO can radiate energy as gravity waves detectable across astronomical distances because of the inherent large energy injected by the astronomical swing-by and faster-than-light of high-order EIDIP effects underlying these gravity waves.⁷⁴

4 Multiple OSPDs induced tunneling effect

In a two-body irrotational interaction system, especially an SMM-system, the OSPDs induced multiple local-stable inter-object locations (e.g., the local minimum locations in FIG. 20). Hence, if internal or external dynamics and disturbances are large enough to overcome the local (EIDIP effects) barriers, the objects can "tunnel" between these local-stable locations.

The tunneling could produce some strange quantum phenomena. E.g., under some circumstances, entangled particles, which form an SMM system, can tunnel between local-stable locations; some of these tunneling events can be interpreted as cold-to-hot heat transfer quantum phenomena which require the reverse-arrow-of-time

⁷³ E.g., the inherent large momentum of swing-by galaxies or projectiles in high-energy scatterings.

⁷⁴ Especially the nondecaying portion of the EIDIP effects despite their energy-leaky nature; refer to section X.D.21 for details.

explanation under conventional models.⁷⁵

V. EIDIP EFFECT PHENOMENOLOGICAL TESTS

This section contains two EIDIP effects phenomenological tests (EEPTs)²: an internucleon EIDIP based nuclear binding energy (NBE) model and nuclei's nuclear charge radius (NCR) semi-empirical formulas (SEF) for heavy and light nuclei based on the physical parameters deducted from the NBE and other EEPTs. The accuracies of these EIDIP effects based NBE- and NCR-SEFs are comparable to, if not more accurate than, the conventional NBE- and NCR-SEFs. Taken together, these results suggest that the NBE EEPT is unlikely to be just coincidental.⁷⁶

A. Nuclear binding energy produced by internucleon EIDIP

That a $T_c = 32\pi$ EIDIP curve can be scaled to trace the periodic-table-element NBEs was one of the figurative EEPTs I have discovered in the early stage of the EIDIP framework development.⁷⁷ To discern whether the fit is coincidental or the NBE is truly related to the EIDIP, I developed an EIDIP based NBE semi-empirical formula (SEF) based on the scaled EIDIP curve as the reference NBE (BE_{ref}) for all known nuclei. Because the deviation between the NBEs of all known nuclei and the BE_{ref} is a parabola function (Fig. 34), this simple relationship contributed to the simpler and more accurate NBE-SEF than the liquid-drop based Bethe-Weizsäcker NBE-SEF formula [7], refer to section V.A.3 for details.

1 Reference nuclear binding energy BE_{ref}

The reference nuclear binding energy BE_{ref} is a normalized EIDIP with this magnitude scaling formula

$$BE_{ref} = [P_E \times 2H_{MC}^0 / (32\pi)^3]_{MeV}, \quad (42)$$

with

$$H_{MC}^0 = [4\pi 10^4]_{MeV/c^2} = [125.664]_{GeV/c^2} \quad (43)$$

⁷⁵ Researchers of [35] reported a reverse-arrow-of-time phenomenon that heat can spontaneously flow from a cold quantum particle to a hotter one under certain conditions.

⁷⁶ The normalized EIDIP function underlying these EEPTs was numerically generated by the MATLAB based on the EIDIP function equation (23) in dual columns (position and magnitude) look-up table (LUT) format; they were then case-dependently scaled in distance and magnitude to fit the physical phenomena.

⁷⁷ I discovered the figurative Bohr radius EEPT (refer to section VII.B) prior 2007 first. The summary of these early figurative EEPTs: Bohr radius, nuclear binding energy (NBE), neutron-neutron potential (NNP, refer to section VI.C), and Pioneer spacecraft 10/11 anomalies (refer to section VII.C) were published to internet on 2011/9 [52] after I decided to develop the EIDIP framework full time on 2010 because of the

as the Higgs-boson-like mass defect;⁷⁹ and this internucleon distance to nuclei mass number A conversion formula

$$A = [r \times [1]_{Dc2}]_m \times [c^2]_{A/m}. \quad (44)$$

With these, the BE_{ref} curve (purple line, FIG. 33) traces periodic table elements (black dots) and with few exceptions, sets the NBEs' upper bound for those 2438 nuclei with experimental NBEs (green circles) listed in the 2012 Atomic Mass Evaluation table (AME2012e).⁸¹

FIG. 33. (Color online) AME2012e NBE (green circle), periodic table elements NBE (black dots) vs. EIDIP ($T_c = 32\pi$) based BE_{ref} (purple line) figure; (subfigure) enlarged to show the alignment details of the BE_{ref} curve and periodic table elements' NBEs.

Note that, because the magnitude ratio between the *inter- P_E* and corresponding *intra- P_E* (P_E^{ita}) is T_c (section II.E.2), $T_c = 32\pi$ in this case, equation (42) can be rewritten with *intra- P_E^{ita}* as

$$BE_{ref} = [P_E^{ita} \times 2H_{MC}^0 R_0^2 \times c^2]_{MeV}, \quad (45)$$

with the isotropic E-space membrane energy (IEME) density R_0^2 and mass defect $[P_E^{ita} \times 2H_{MC}^0 R_0^2]_{MeV/c^2}$ terms.

discoveries of these figurative EEPTs. I also posted my initial NBE EEPT with empirical data result later on 2012/12 [56].

⁷⁸ Alternative formula: $[P_E \times (2H_{MC}^0 c^2) \times R_0^2 / (32\pi)]_{MeV}^{BE_{ref}}$ because of $32\pi R_0 c = 1$.

⁷⁹ Note that the $H_{MC}^0 = [125.664]_{GeV/c^2}$ is within the range of the ATLAS $[126 \pm 0.8]_{GeV/c^2}$ [8] and the CMS $[125.3 \pm 0.9]_{GeV/c^2}$ [9], and that the H_{MC}^0 was renamed and updated from an similar mass defect term, named interaction mass unit $iMu = [(32\pi)^2 10^{-54} H_0^5 / 2]_{GeV/c^2} = [125.653]_{GeV/c^2} = 0.99991 \times H_{MC}^0$, used in my NBE EEPT papers prior to the Higgs boson discovery on 2012.

⁸⁰ The r has a normalized unit and the $[1]_{Dc2} / [1]_m = R_0 / (32\pi)^2$ is the $[1]_{Dc2}$ to meter conversion factor.

⁸¹ From the Atomic Mass Data Center (AMDC). The Postfix "e" of the AME2012e represents those nuclei with "experimental" NBEs.

2 Lower bound internucleon distance

Because the BE_{ref} sets the NBEs' upper bound for known nuclei with few exceptions, it represents the binding energy of those nuclei with the lower bound inter-particle distance (LBID). The LBID can be deduced from equation (44) as

$$[r]_m = A/c^2 = A \times R_u, \quad (46)$$

with $R_u = [1/c^2]_m$ as the quantized LBID.⁸²

3 Deviation between all known nuclei NBEs and BE_{ref} is approximately a parabola function

Apart from few exceptions, the deviation between the known nuclei NBEs and BE_{REF} is approximately a parabola function (Fig. 34). This simple relationship contributed to a simpler and more accurate EIDIP based NBE-SEF (ENBE-SEF). With reference to the experimental NBEs of the 2438 nuclei listed in the AME2012 table, the NBEs produced by the ENBE-SEF have a lower 0.094 standard deviation than the 0.415 standard deviation produced by the liquid-drop model Bethe-Weizsäcker NBE-SEF [7].⁸³

Fig. 34. (Color online) Deviation between the AME2012-NBE and BE_{ref} is a parabola function figure (only shows the low mass number region).

4 EIDIP based Higgs-boson-like mass in SI unit formula

Note that the EIDIP based Higgs-boson-like mass $H_{MC}^0 = [125.664]_{GeV/c^2}$ (equation (43)) is within the

⁸² Note that the R_u is about 1/60 of the maximum neutron-neutron attraction potential radius $R_{NNP}^{max} = [0.673836]_m$ revealed in the NNP EEPT (refer to section VI.C); which indicates the LBID represents the finer inter-quark or inter-elementary-particle distance.

⁸³ Refer to [7] for details. The ENBE-SEF is $BE(A) = [BE_{ref}(A) + BE_{NRP} - (BE_{NSP}(A))^2 + \delta_E(A)]_{MeV}$ with $BE_{NSP}(N_a, Z_a) = k_w(k_f((Z_a + 3)/(N_a + 3) - (N_a + 3)/(Z_a + 3)))^2 + k_c$ as the nucleon spherical shell packing adjustment, $BE_{NRP} = [(BE_{REF}/4 -$

range of the ATLAS $[126 \pm 0.8]_{GeV/c^2}$ [8] and the CMS $[125.3 \pm 0.9]_{GeV/c^2}$ [9]. The Higgs-boson-like mass in kilogram unit (H_{kg}^0) is

$$H_{kg}^0 = [H_{MC}^0 \times k_{kg/Mc}]_{kg}, \quad (47)$$

with $k_{kg/Mc} = 1.7826 \times 10^{-30}$ as the standard MeV/c^2 to kilogram conversion factor. Note that $k_{kg/Mc} \cong (16\pi)R_0^3/1.03$. In the EIDIP framework, the MeV/c^2 to kilogram conversion *approximation* factor is

$$k_{kg/Mc}^{EIDIP} = 16\pi R_0^3 \cong k_{kg/Mc} \times 1.03. \quad (48)$$

With that, alternative EIDIP based Higgs-boson-like masses in kilogram (H_{ykg}^0) and MeV/c^2 (H_{yMc}^0) are

$$H_{ykg}^0 = [H_{MC}^0 \times k_{kg/Mc}^{EIDIP}]_{kg} \quad (49)$$

$$H_{yMc}^0 = [H_{kg}^0 / k_{kg/Mc}^{EIDIP}]_{MeV/c^2}.$$

These Higgs-boson-like masses are widely used in the 10+ EEPTs' magnitude formulas (TABLE V). They can simplify the magnitude formulas and reveal connections even between the SI and electronvolt (eV) base unit magnitude formulas. E.g., the BE_{ref} (equation (42)) can be reformulated in the SI base units as

$$BE_{ref} = [P_E \times H_{ykg}^0 R_0^2 \times 1_{Dc2}]_{Nm}^{BE_{ref}}, \quad (50)$$

or approximately as

$$BE_{ref} \cong [P_E \times H_{kg}^0 R_0^2 \times 1_{Dc2}]_{Nm}^{BE_{ref}}; \quad (51)$$

which reveals the connection between the NBE, isotropic E-space membrane energy (IEME) density R_0^2 , and Dc2-domain (1_{Dc2}) where the NBE operates.⁸⁴

B. EEPT parameters based nuclear charge radius semi-empirical formulas (EPNCR-SEF)

If the NBE EEPT presented in the last section were merely coincidental, their parameters (e.g., H_{MC}^0 and R_u) would not be applicable to other physical phenomena. I.e., if the subatomic parameters deduced from the NBE EEPT are not coincidental, they can also be significant parameters in other subatomic physical phenomena like the nuclear charge radius (NCR).

To cross check the NBE EEPT, I also developed several

$2)^2]_{MeV}$ as nucleon radical packing adjustment, $N_a = R_{NZ} \times \sin(\theta_a)$ and $Z_a = R_{NZ} \times \cos(\theta_a)$ as the radius differential adjusted proton and neutron number with $\theta_a = \tan^{-1}(N/Z) - \sqrt{R_{NZ}/2960}$ and $R_{NZ} = \sqrt{N^2 + Z^2}$, and $\delta_E(A) = \pm 9.748/\sqrt{A}$ (positive: both N and Z are even numbers, negative: both N and Z are odd numbers) or $\delta_E(A) = 0$ for other cases. The 0.094 standard deviation is based on these parameter values: $k_w = 0.95025$, $k_f = 1.92175$, and $k_c = -0.073$.

⁸⁴ Note that the 1_{Dc2} also appears in the NBE EEPT's distance scaler equation (44).

EEPT-parameters based NCR semi-empirical formulas (EPNCR-SEF) that comprised the physical parameters deduced from the NBE and other EEPTs presented in later sections. It turned out that the quantized LBID unit R_u deduced from the NBE EEPT, the maximum strong force (SF) radius R_{SF}^{max} deduced from the SF EEPT (section VII.A.1), and the maximum attractive neutron-neutron potential (NNP) radius R_{NNP}^{max} deduced from the NNP EEPT (section VI.C) are significant parameters of the EPNCR-SEFs, especially prominent in the light nuclei EPNCR-SEFs (Fig. 38 and TABLE IV).

1 Spheroidal-shell-nucleus-structure NCR baseline curve

The conventional liquid drop nucleus model assumes nuclei have spheroidal *volume* structures such that its simplest heavy nuclei NCR SEF is a cubic root function of the mass number $\sqrt[3]{A}$. Whereas the EIDIP framework assumes heavy nuclei have spheroidal *shell* structures such that the NCRs' baseline is approximately a square root function of the mass number \sqrt{A} .

The EPNCR-SEF hypothesizes that, because of the swing-by action of test projectiles in NCR measurements, the maximum strong force radius R_{SF}^{max} should be part of measured NCRs. Furthermore, because it takes a certain number of nucleons to form a structure that resembles a spheroidal *shell*, the spheroidal-shell-structure based EPNCR-SEF only works for those nuclei that have enough nucleons (e.g., $A \geq 4$). Therefore, the EPNCR-SEF baseline function (brown dotted curve, Fig. 35) includes a fitted offset R_{oft}^b to account for the light nuclei base radius and a preferred swing-by radius R_{SF}^{max} ,

$$R_b = R_q \sqrt{A} + R_{oft}^b. \quad (52)$$

The best-fit $A = 4$ NCR offset $R_{oft}^{A=4}$ is 1.858 femtometers which is only about 10% higher than the tetrahedron-form Helium-4 NCR listed in the 2013 Atomic Data and Nuclear Data (ADND13) [10]. Note that the LBID unit R_u is also the unit of the baseline NCR curve slope $R_q = 24R_u$; and that the preferred internucleon distance R_{NNP}^{max} and test projectiles swing-by radius R_{SF}^{max} are part of the R_{oft}^b compositions of those light nuclei EPNCR-SEFs described in later section V.C.

2 Deviations between empirical and EPNCR-SEF produced NCRs

Because the goal of EPNCR-SEF development was not to develop the most accurate NCR SEF but to crosscheck the findings of the NBE and other EEPTs, the EPNCR-SEF was developed in about a year and has room for

improvement. However, the accuracy of the EPNCR-SEF was comparable to the Skyrme-Hartree-Fock-Bogoliubov and Weizsacker-Skyrme mass model produced semi-empirical NCR formula (SWNCR-SEF) of [11], hereafter referred to as the SWNCR-SEF.

With reference to those 885 nuclei NCR (blue dots, Fig. 35; mass number ≥ 16) listed in the ADND13 Table (ADND13-A16),⁸⁵ 47.8% of the EPNCR-SEF produced NCRs (red dots, Fig. 35) are within the uncertainties vs. the 35.5% of the SWNCR-SEF produced NCRs.⁸⁶ The EPNCR-SEF's deviation also yielded a $r.m.s. = [0.0199]_{fm}$ vs. the SWNCR-SEF's $r.m.s. = [0.0218]_{fm}$.⁸⁷

Fig. 35. (Color online) EPNCR baseline function (brown dots), EPNCR-SEF produced NCR (red dots) and ADND13-A16 NCR (blue dots) figure.

The main reason why the EPNCR-SEF has this level of accuracy is that the EPNCR-SEF includes this $3R_u$ sub-shell formation radius (SSFR) adjustment. During the EPNCR-SEF development, I discovered that with reference to the ADND13-NCR, for approximately every 100 mass-number, there is a $3R_u$ deviation jump in the pre-adjusted EPNCR-SEF produced NCRs (Fig. 36); the first deviation jump is clearly shown around $A=100$ whereas the second one, around $A=200$, is less obvious.⁸⁸ Fig. 37 shows the post-SSFR adjustment NCR deviations.

⁸⁵ Among them, 811 nuclei NCRs are measured and 74 nuclei NCRs are estimated.

⁸⁶ Refer to [41]; note that the EPNCR-SEF and SWNCR-SEF of this paper are renamed from the ENSEF and WSSEF of [41].

⁸⁷ The $r.m.s. = [0.0218]_{fm}$ is based on the SWNCR-SEF produced NCRs provided by Dr. Ning Wang on July 2013.

⁸⁸ Probably because there are more nucleon cluster structure options available in the second-to-third-subshell transition.

Fig. 36. (Color online) EPNCR-SEF deviations without sub-shell LBID $3R_u$ adjustment figure (dot-dashed horizontal line grid unit is $3R_u$).

Fig. 37. (Color online) EPNCR-SEF deviations with sub-shell LBID $3R_u$ adjustment figure.

One way to judge a model is how good it handles new data; i.e., its *sustaining* accuracy over a newer dataset. The EPNCR-SEF, which was originally constructed based on an older 2003 empirical NCR dataset, has sustained its accuracy against a newer ADND13 dataset. The sustaining accuracy of the EPNCR-SEF affirms that the R_{SF}^{max} , R_{NNP}^{max} , and R_u , deduced from other EEPTs, are less likely to be coincidental because they are applicable to other subatomic physical phenomena.

C. EEPT parameter based semi-empirical nuclear charge radii formulas for light nuclei

Because light nuclei have unique structures deviate from spheroidal forms, the spherical shell based EPNCR-SEF would not work for light nuclei that require individual NCR-SEFs. As the heavy nuclei EPNCR-SEF, the light nuclei EPNCR-SEFs' compositions reveal the underlying nuclear structures that the preferred swing-by radius R_{SF}^{max} and inter-nucleon radius R_{NNP}^{max} are also part of the measured light nuclei NCRs.

⁸⁹ $R_q = 24R_u$ is the slope of the EPNCR-SEF baseline function (equation (52)).

⁹⁰ Note that $3R_u$ is also the sub-shell thickness in the heavy nuclei EPNCR-SEF.

⁹¹ With the R_c^μ and R_c^e as the muon and electron core radii respectively. The EIDIP framework hypothesizes that the Standard Model (SM)

1 EPNCR-SEFs for proton, neutron, hydrogen isotope and Helium-4

From the light nuclei EPNCR-SEFs I have discovered, they suggested that the measured light nuclei NCRs include the preferred swing-by or orbiting radius R_{SF}^{max} between the test projectile (or orbiting electrons) and target nuclei, the preferred internucleon distance R_{NNP}^{max} within the nucleus core radius of multi-nucleon light nuclei, and the electron or muon core radius. I.e., light nuclei NCRs comprise these components:

- (1) Proton core radius: $R_c^P = (R_q + R_q^-)/2 = [0.134846]_{\text{fm}}$ with $R_q^- = R_q/(32\pi)$;⁸⁹
- (2) Neutron core radius: $R_c^N = 2(R_q + R_u) + R_q^- + 3R_u = [0.592361]_{\text{fm}}$;
- (3) Electron core radius: $R_c^e = 3R_u = [0.0333795]_{\text{fm}}$ or muon core radius $R_c^\mu = R_c^e/(32\pi)$;^{90,91}
- (4) The preferred internucleon distance: $R_{NNP}^{max} = [0.673836]_{\text{fm}}$;¹⁰⁵
- (5) The preferred flyby or orbiting radius: $R_{SF}^{max} = [0.707056]_{\text{fm}}$.¹²²

Fig. 38 and TABLE IV show the EPNCR-SEF compositions of these light nuclei: proton (muonic and electronic), neutron, and deuteron. All these light nuclei EPNCR-SEFs produced NCRs matched the recommended values of the CODATA and ADND13 and other empirical measurements.^{92,93,94,95} Note that the deuteron EPNCR-SEF comprises the same neutron and proton cores radii as the proton and neutron EPNCR-SEFs with an additional preferred internucleon distance R_{NNP}^{max} between the cores. These components can also be used to construct the helium-4 isotope EPNCR-SEF. Assuming the Helium-4 has a regular tetrahedron structure, the Helium-4 EPNCR-SEF produced NCR is just $[0.00186]_{\text{fm}}$ outside of the CODATA 2010 Helium-4 NCR $[1.6755 \pm 0.0028]_{\text{fm}}$ even with such a simplified structure.

particle generations represent the same type of particles operate in different E-domains, hereafter referred to as the elementary particle generation (EPG) hypothesis. A muon operates in a higher cE-domain with $1/(32\pi)$ shorter DSU than an electron; therefore, the muon has a $1/(32\pi)$ shorter core radius; i.e., $R_c^\mu = R_c^e/(32\pi)$.

Fig. 38. (Color) Light nuclei EPNCR-SEF compositions figure: (A) muonic proton NCR; (B) Electronic proton NCR; (C) Neutron NCR; (D) Deuteron NCR.

TABLE IV. Proton (muonic and electronic), neutron, and deuteron EPNCR-SEF compositions table

Cases	Magnitude formula
Proton	$R_P^\mu = R_c^P + R_{SF}^{max} + R_c^\mu$ (muonic) ⁹²
	$R_P^e = R_c^P + R_{SF}^{max} + R_c^e$ (electronic) ⁹³
Neutron	$R_N = R_c^N - R_{SF}^{max}$ ⁹⁴
Deuteron	$R_{De} = R_{NP} + R_{SF}^{max} + R_c^e$ ⁹⁵
	$R_{NP} = R_c^N + R_{NNP}^{max} + R_c^P$
Helium-4	$R_{H4} = k_{cr}(R_{NP} + R_q/2) + R_{SF}^{max} + R_c^e$ ⁹⁶

VI. EIDIP-GRADIENT EFFECT PHENOMENOLOGICAL TESTS

This section contains these EIDIP-gradient phenomenological tests (gradient-EEPTs)²: interatomic covalent force (IACF), gravitational constant deviation (NGCD), and neutron-neutron potential (NNP).⁹⁷ The EIDIP-gradient effects induced accelerations G_{PGA} can trace the repulsive/attractive behaviors of the internucleon nuclear force (aka neutron-neutron potential and residual-strong force) and interatomic covalent force (IACF); the conformal coupling $G_{PGC}^\infty = G_{PGA}^\infty \times r^2$ of the IACF also contributes to the Newtonian gravitational constant measurements.

A. Interatomic covalent force

Interatomic covalent forces (IACF) are G_{PGA} induced forces. The two IACF gradient-EEPTs presented in this section are based on the IACF figure 3 of [12]; which depicts two IACF curves from two tip setups: a blunter tip-1 and a shaper tip-2.⁹⁸ These subfigures are reproduced separately in FIG. 39 (tip-1) and FIG. 40 (tip-2).

Even though the IACF measurement setups are inherently few-body interaction systems, the two-body interaction EIDIP-gradient curves still fit both cases

⁹² This proton muonic EPNCR-SEF yielded $[0.842234]_{fm}$ which compares to the muonic hydrogen NCR measurement of $[0.84184 \pm 0.00067]_{fm}$.

⁹³ This proton electronic EPNCR-SEF yielded $[0.872816]_{fm}$ which compares to the CODATA 2006 proton charge radius $[0.8768 \pm 0.0069]_{fm}$, the CODATA 2010 proton charge radius $[0.8775 \pm 0.0051]_{fm}$, $[0.879 \pm 0.015]_{fm}$ of [51], and $[0.8737 \pm 0.0075]_{fm}$ of [50].

⁹⁴ Including the R_{SF}^{max} deduction, the neutron EPNCR-SEF yielded $[-0.114695]_{fm}$ which matches the negative neutron NCR $[-0.1149 \pm 0.0027]_{fm}$ listed in the ADND13 table.

⁹⁵ This deuteron EPNCR-SEF yielded $[2.141478]_{fm}$ which compares to the CODATA 2010 Deuteron NCR $[2.1421 \pm 0.0021]_{fm}$.

⁹⁶ This EPNCR-SEF assumes the Helium-4 has a regular tetrahedron structure and $k_{cr} = 0.612372$ is the tetrahedron circumsphere radius to edge ratio. This Helium-4 EPNCR-SEF yielded $[1.680158]_{fm}$ which is approximately $[0.00186]_{fm}$ outside of the CODATA 2010 Helium-4 NCR $[1.6755 \pm 0.0028]_{fm}$.

closely. However, because these tips have different shapes, their magnitude and distance scalars differ. With these magnitude formulas

$$G_{PGA}^{IACF} = P_d \times (2H_{kg}^0 c^3)/24 \text{ (tip1)} \quad (53)$$

$$G_{PGA}^{IACF} = P_d \times (2H_{kg}^0 c^3)/4 \text{ (tip2)}$$

and distance scalars: $k_x = [4]_{Dc0}$ (tip-1) and $k_x = [2]_{Dc0}$ (tip-2), these $T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4} P_d$ curves trace both fitted IACF mean black curves of [12] reproduced in FIG. 39 and FIG. 40; which depict these P_d based IACF curves (blue line) overlaid on the tip-1 and 2 subfigures of [12] respectively.⁹⁹

Note that if we assume the effective mass involved in these IACF measurements is approximately $M_{kg}^{IACF} = [1/(32\pi)^3]_{kg}$,¹⁰⁰ ignoring case dependent scaling factors, equation (53) can be rewritten as

$$G_{PGA}^{IACF} = P_d \times M_{kg}^{IACF} \times 2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3; \quad (54)$$

which includes the $2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3$ term common among the magnitude scalar formulas of gradient-EEPTs. This formula also reveals the connection between the IACF, EIDIP gradient effect, isotropic E-space membrane energy (IEME) density $R_0 = 1/H_0$, and internucleon mass defect H_{kg}^0 .

Both IACF EEPTs having integer Dc0-DSU distance scalars ($[2]_{Dc0}$ and $[4]_{Dc0}$) are likely not coincidental by themselves; in addition, the integer DSU distance scalars are also common among the 10+ EEPTs presented in this paper (TABLE V).

⁹⁷ The normalized EIDIP function underlying the EIDIP-gradient phenomenological tests was numerically generated by the MATLAB based on the EIDIP function equation (23) in dual columns (position and magnitude) look-up table (LUT). They were then numerically translated through the MATLAB built-in *gradient* function into the EIDIP-gradient function LUT and case-dependently scaled in distance and magnitude to fit the physical phenomena. Note that the MATLAB gradient function approximates a differential operator.

⁹⁸ The data was obtained by subtracting the long-range van-der-Waals background. Note that, in these subfigures, the distance axes include some unknown offset “for the fact that the absolute zero of the distance axes are unknown” and were rescaled to account for the “the relaxation of the outermost tip atoms” [12].

⁹⁹ For detailed empirical figure phenomenological test procedure, refer to Appendix VI.

¹⁰⁰ Excluding the case-dependent magnitude scaling factors of 1/24 and 1/4 for tip1 and tip-2 respectively. The effective mass $M_{kg}^{IACF} \approx [1/(32\pi)^3]_{kg}$ can be treated as an EIDIP framework prediction or a NHTD.

FIG. 39. (Color online) G_{PGA} ($T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$) based interatomic covalent force (IACF) curve (blue line) shifted by $[-7.18]_{Am}$ (green vertical dashed line depicts the original Y-axis) overlaid on tip-1 IACF figure of [12].

FIG. 40. (Color online) G_{PGA} ($T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$) based interatomic covalent force (IACF) curve (blue line) shifted by $[-9.35]_{Am}$ (green vertical dashed line depicts the original Y-axis) overlaid on tip-2 IACF figure of [12].

Note that, although the P_d based IACF curve (blue curve in FIG. 40) traces the tip-2 IACF curve (black curve in FIG. 40), the tip-1's IACF curves exhibit some deviation in the -4 to 0 angstrom region (FIG. 39). This is probably because of the blunter the tip (tip-1), the higher the interacting body-count; hence, the higher the deviation from the two-body interaction based P_d curve.

B. Newtonian gravitational constant and $[2R_0]_{m^3/s^2}$ deviation source

In the EIDIP framework, the Newtonian gravitational constant measurements comprise at least two components: a Dc0-domain MWEP coupling constant $G_{MGC}^{Dc0} = [2R_0]_{m^3/s^2}$ (the gravitational constant of the EIDIP framework) and an irrotational Dc0-domain EIDIP effect coupling G_{PGC}^{Dc0} .¹⁰¹ The G_{MGC}^{Dc0} covers 99.43% of the 2014

¹⁰¹ Ignoring the rotational Dc0-domain EIDIP effect coupling.

CODATA recommended gravitational constant value $[6.67408(31) \times 10^{-11}]_{m^3/(kg s^2)}$ [2] and the remaining 0.57% Newtonian gravitational constant deviation (NGCD) can be mostly covered by the G_{PGC}^{Dc0} .¹⁰²

With a G_{PGC}^{NGCD} magnitude formula, which has the same $2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3$ term as the G_{PGA}^{IACF} magnitude formula (equation (54)), and a distance squared term $(r^2)_{\ell^2} (R_0^2)_{(m/\ell)^2}$ to form the $G_{PGC} = G_{PGA} \times r^2$, the

$$G_{PGC}^{NGCD} = [P_d^\infty 2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3]_N^{PGA} [(r^2)_{\ell^2} (R_0^2)_{(m/\ell)^2}]_{m^2} r^2 \quad (55)$$

yields a meter-range $[3.36716 \times 10^{-13}]_{Nm^2}$ (FIG. 41). With that, $G_{MGC}^{Dc0} + G_{PGC}^{NGCD} = [6.67001 \times 10^{-11}]_{m^3/(kg s^2)}$ covers 99.93% of the 2014 CODATA recommended gravitational constant value [2].

FIG. 41. (Color online) G_{PGC}^{Dc0} coupling ($T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$) fluctuates in interatomic range (green dashed box) and settles to constant at a distance figure.

1 IACF coupling contribution to Newtonian gravitational constant measurements

With an effective-mass unit of $M_{kg}^{NGCD} = [1]_{kg}$, the PGA portion of equation (55) can be rewritten as

$$G_{PGA}^{NGCD} = [P_d \times M_{kg}^{NGCD} \times 2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3]_N^{PGA} \quad (56)$$

which has the same $2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3$ magnitude scaler term as the IACF EEPTs and the NNP EEPTs described in the later section. The shared term affirms that the IACF coupling does contribute to the Newtonian gravitational constant measurements and that the result of the NGCD phenomenological test is likely *not* a coincidence.

¹⁰² Aka gravitational coupling constant deviation (GCCD).

2 IACF EEPTs affirm gravitational potential has a quantized singularity

Because interactions between two MWEPs produce EIDIPs, the IACF EEPTs affirm that matter (atom and molecular) does possess the quantized singularity MWEPEP (gravitational potential). Furthermore, the distance scalers: 4_{Dc0} (tip-1) and 2_{Dc0} (tip-2) show that the IACFs are induced by the interactions of Dc0-harmonics MWEPEPs.¹⁰³ Hence, these IACF EEPTs provide some indirect empirical evidence to support that gravitational potentials have a quantized singularity and IACF measurement methods have a potential to be a simpler indirect way to measure the gravitational constant.

3 Why current gravitational constant measurements have wide deviations

It is a well-known fact that there are large deviations between gravitational constant measurements; this is because these experiments also measured distance and environment sensitive EIDIP effects couplings (e.g., G_{PGC} and G_{APC}), the culprits of the large deviations.

E.g., referring to FIG. 41, the G_{PGC} effect is distance sensitive. Although the conformal G_{PGC} is close to a constant, the NSTEE region (green dashed box, FIG. 41) G_{PGC} fluctuates and even becomes repulsive; of which the effects affect the Newtonian gravitational constant measurements and can push the measured gravitational constant below $[2R_0]_{m^3/s^2}$ in some setups.

The Newtonian gravitational constant measurements are sensitive to environments because of environmental EIDIP effects. E.g., the environmental EIDIP effects are different between the deep underground and high-altitude orbital space-crafts measurements setups. The deep underground measurements would include additional Earth mass induced NSTEEs;¹⁰⁴ whereas the orbital measurements would include additional zero-order xE-domain EIDIP effects induced frame dragging effects.

C. EIDIP-gradient induced neutron-neutron potential

Neutron-neutron potential (NNP) is ideal for studying the nuclear force (aka residual-strong force) that binds nucleons into atomic nuclei. In the EIDIP framework, instead of composing of the Yukawa and EM potentials, the NNP is an internucleon EIDIP-gradient induced potential.

With $T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$, an integer distance scaler $k_x = [1]_{Dc2.5}$, and a magnitude formula

$$G_{PGP}^{NNP} = [P_d \times (H_{Mc}^0 c^2)_{MeV} \times R_0^2]_{MeV}, \quad (57)$$

¹⁰³ With $[8R_0]_{m^3/s^2}$ and $[4R_0]_{m^3/s^2}$ coupling constants respectively, but both have the same $[2R_0]_{m^3/s^2}$ effective coupling after accounting for their distance scalers' effects.

¹⁰⁴ The Earth surface can be viewed as a many-body E-fermion boundary; hence, the deep underground is in an environmental NSTEE region.

with R_0^2 as the isotropic E-space membrane energy (IEME) density, the P_d based NNP curve (blue line, FIG. 42) depicts NNP's strange behaviors: repulsive at short distances (red dotted region, FIG. 42) and highly attractive between 0.5-2 femtometer (green dotted region, FIG. 42). And, with some distance offset, it (purple dashed line, FIG. 43) is comparable to the NNP curves of [13].⁹⁹

Note that the maximum neutron-neutron attraction potential radius $R_{NNP}^{max} = [0.673836]_{fm}$ ¹⁰⁵ is a prominent parameter in the Deuteron and Helium-4 EPNCR-SEFs (TABLE IV). Furthermore, the $k_x = [1]_{Dc2.5}$ distance scaler and $T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$ are common among the subatomic EEPTs (TABLE V). The P_d based NNP curve (FIG. 42) also has a saturation region approximately at the 0.3 ferrometer range that differs from conventional NNP models; this saturation region provides a definitive falsifiability to the P_d based NNP model.

FIG. 42. (Color online) EIDIP-gradient ($T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$) based NNP curve figure; (red dotted box: repulsive region, green dotted box: highly attractive region).

¹⁰⁵ $R_{NNP}^{max} = [0.673836]_{fm}$ is based on the EIDIP function generated by a MATLAB simulation with an error tolerance setting: 1E-14; minimum value location, shown as red dashed line in FIG. 42, was deduced from a spline fitted curve with 10^5 subsampling.

FIG. 43. (Color online) EIDIP NNP curve (purple dashed line, shifted in X-axis green vertical dashed depicts the original Y-axis) and NNP of [13].¹⁰⁶

Assuming the effective mass involved in these NNP measurements is $M_{kg}^{NNP} = [R_0^3/(32\pi)^2/2]_{kg} = [1.014]_{\text{eV}/c^2} \cong [1]_{\text{eV}/c^2}$, equation (57) can be rewritten in the SI base units as

$$G_{PGP}^{NNP} = [P_d \times (M_{kg}^{NNP} c^2) \times 2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3]_{N_m}^{PGP} \quad (58)$$

with $(M_{kg}^{NNP} c^2) \cong [1]_{\text{eV}}$ as the NNP energy unit. Note that the $2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3$ also appears in the magnitude formulas of other gradient-EEPTs: IACF (equation (54)) and the NGCD (equation (56)). The shared magnitude scaler term indicates that these EEPTs are likely not coincidental.

1 Composite EIDIP effect induced neutron-neutron potential

Employing *two-body* interaction EIDIP effects to describe few-body interactions would require additional adjustments. Because a nucleon comprises three quarks, in short-distance, the NNP may be closer to a bi-group than a two-body interaction potential. With additional adjustments: 0.72 for distance and 1.44 for magnitude, the scaled P_d -NNP curve traces the AV18 curve (FIG. 44); whereas with additional adjustments: 1/1.15 for distance and 1.15 for magnitude, the scaled P_d -NNP curve also traces the Reid93 curve (FIG. 45).

¹⁰⁶ Three examples of the high-precision NNP in the 1S_0 channel. AV18 stands for the Argonne V_{18} potential, Reid93 stands for one of the Nijmegen potentials and Bonn stands for the Bonn potential (from figure 1 of [13]).

FIG. 44. (Color online) Horizontal shifted EIDIP NNP-AV18 curve (purple dashed line, green vertical dashed depicts the original Y-axis) aligns with AV18-NNP of [13].⁹⁹

FIG. 45. (Color online) Horizontal shifted EIDIP NNP-Reid93 curve (purple dashed line, green vertical dashed depicts the original Y-axis) aligns with Reid93-NNP of [13].⁹⁹

VII. ANGULAR EIDIP EFFECT PHENOMENOLOGICAL TESTS

Angular EIDIP effects induced accelerations G_{APA} can trace the strong force's asymptotic and confinement behaviors, and the anomalous forces underlying the Pioneer 10/11 spacecraft's sunward acceleration anomaly (PSAA) and Milky Way rotation curve (MWRC) anomaly.¹⁰⁷ This section contains these angular EIDIP

¹⁰⁷ The normalized EIDIP function underlying the angular EIDIP phenomenological tests was numerically generated by the MATLAB based on the EIDIP function equation (23) in dual columns (position and magnitude) look-up table (LUT). It was numerically translated into the angular EIDIP function LUT based on equation (31) and then case-

phenomenological tests (angular-EEPTs): inter-quark strong force (SF), interatomic Bohr radius, and interplanetary PSAA. The internucleon strong coupling phenomenological test are presented in the following composite EIDIP effects phenomenological tests section.

A. Angular EIDIP induced strong force

It is a well-known fact that strong force is asymptotic (getting weaker as distance decreases) at short distances and conformal (settle-to-constant) at long distances. In the EIDIP framework, because quarks possess intrinsic spins, interactions between quarks produces angular EIDIPs. The G_{APA} from them produce the strong force that possesses these strange asymptotic freedom and color confinement behaviors (FIG. 46).

With $T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$, an integer distance scaler $k_x = [1]_{Dc2.5}$, and a magnitude formula

$$G_{APA}^{SF} = [P_r^\infty \times 2H_{kg}^0 \times 2_{Dx2.5}^2]_{N}^{APA},^{108} \quad (59)$$

the P_r based strong force strength in the conformal region is 10359 newtons (FIG. 46) compared to the estimated strong force strength of 9800 newtons approximately from “the Behavior of the strong force” [14]. Note that the maximum strong interaction distance $R_{SF}^{max} = [0.707056]_{fm}^{109}$ (the acme radius, FIG. 46) is a prominent component of the EPNCR-SEFs especially for those light nuclei (TABLE IV).

FIG. 46. (Color online) Angular EIDIP ($T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$) based strong force curve figure.

Furthermore, the angular EIDIP effect coupling can also describe the subatomic effective strong coupling (FIG. 55) and meter-range effective magnetic couplings (section VIII.E). Note that the integer distance scaler $k_x = [1]_{Dc2.5}$ and $T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$ are common among the subatomic EEPTs (TABLE V); and that the $Dx2.5$ -domain of the $2_{Dx2.5}^2$ term in the magnitude formula is complementary to

dependently scaled in distance and magnitude to fit the physical phenomena.

¹⁰⁸ Alternative formula: $G_{APA}^{SF} = [P_r \times 2H_{kg}^0 \times (32\pi)^5 c^2]_{N}^{APA}$.

the $Dc2.5$ -domain of the distance scaler $[1]_{Dc2.5}$.

1 Asymptotic and conformal regions strong force can be approximated by quadratic power and constant functions

The P_r based strong force curve comprises two linear segments in a log-log plane presentation (FIG. 47); the asymptotic segment has a 1.9977 linear slope (between two magenta dashed lines) which can be approximated by a quadratic power function in a linear-linear plane presentation; whereas the conformal segment has a close to zero linear slope 7.448×10^{-7} (between two green dashed lines) which can be approximated by a constant function in a linear-linear plane presentation. I.e., the asymptotic region strong force F_s can be approximated by a quadratic power function,

$$F_s^{asymptotic} \propto r^{-2}; \quad (60)$$

whereas, the conformal region strong force is approximately constant,

$$F_s^{confinement} \propto cnst. \quad (61)$$

FIG. 47. (Color online) Angular EIDIP ($T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$) based strong force curve on a log-log plane figure.

B. Angular EIDIP induced Bohr radius

Bohr radius approximately equals the most probable distance between the proton and electron in a hydrogen atom in its ground state. The distance is not exactly the Bohr radius due to the reduced mass effect; the difference is about 0.1% [15]. In the EIDIP framework, the centripetal force that binds the orbital electron to hydrogen nuclei is from the rotational G_{APA} effect because of the high orbiting speed of the electron.

With $T_c = 32\pi$ and an integer distance scaler $k_x =$

¹⁰⁹ $R_{SF}^{max} = [0.707056]_{fm}$ is based on EIDIP error tolerance setting 1E-14 mat file; maximum value location, shown as red dashed line in FIG. 55, was deducted from the spline curve fit with 10^5 subsampling.

[1]_{DC0} = [R₀]_m, the scaled G_{APA} curve peak at $[5.27747 \times 10^{-11}]_m$ (red vertical dashed line, FIG. 48)¹¹⁰ compared to the CODATA Bohr Radius $[5.2917721067(12) \times 10^{-11}]_m$ [16].¹¹¹

FIG. 48. (Color online) Angular EIDIP G_{APA} ($T_c = 32\pi$) based Bohr Radius curve figure.

The Bohr radius EEPT indicates that it is the G_{APA} origin centripetal force that holds the orbital electron to hydrogen nuclei. Note that angular EIDIP effect coupling G_{APC} is part of the measured neutron charge distributions and effective magnetic coupling (refer to sections VIII.A and VIII.E).

C. Interplanetary range angular EIDIP induced Pioneer 10/11 anomaly

The authors of “Support for the thermal origin of the Pioneer anomaly” [17] have concluded that, after accounting for all thermal recoil forces (TRF) including source uncertainty, no statistically significant acceleration anomaly exists. In this section, I shall show that the Pioneer 10/11 spacecraft sunward acceleration (PSAA¹¹²) have a G_{APA} origin and argue that the TRF-based model put forth by [17] is not a right model for the Pioneer 10/11 anomalies because it cannot explain the steep-ascending segment of the Pioneer 11 anomaly.

The sun rotates once approximately every 27 days; although slow, the Pioneer 10/11 spacecraft and rotating sun make up interaction systems that can produce rotational xE-domain EIDIPs; the xE- G_{APA} from them is asymptotic in the NSTEE region and conformal (settle-to-constant) at long distances similar to the asymptotic-confinement behaviors of the cE- G_{APA} induced strong force.

Because of G_{APA} 's asymptotic behavior, the meter-range sunward G_{APA} is much lower than gravity and neglectable.

¹¹⁰ From MATLAB simulation: $T_c = 32\pi$, error tolerance of 10^{-14} , simulation range [0.001:4] with 100 linear samplings, and then using MATLAB's spline line fit function with 10^5 subsampling to determine the maximum location.

¹¹¹ With an approximately $[1.43 \times 10^{-13}]_m$ deviation or 0.27% relative deviation.

However, with the massive sun mass, the sunward G_{APA} becomes noticeable at inter-planetary distances. Because Newtonian gravity model does not account for EIDIP effects, the G_{APA} induced sunward accelerations appear as anomalies.

With $T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$, an integer distance scaler $k_x = [1]_{Dx2} = [(32\pi)^2 c/2]_m$, and a magnitude formula

$$G_{APA}^{PSAA} = P_r M_\odot H_{kg}^0 Z_{Dc2}^2 1_{Dx2},^{113} \quad (62)$$

with $M_\odot = [1.98855 \pm 0.00025 \times 10^{30}]_{kg}$ as the sun mass in kilograms [18], the G_{APA}^{PSAA} curve (blue curve, FIG. 49) traces *both* Pioneer 10/11 spacecraft's sunward acceleration anomaly datasets of [19].

FIG. 49. (Color online) G_{APA} ($T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$) based PSAA curve (blue) traces *both* Pioneer 10/11 sunward acceleration empirical data figure of [19]: magenta dashed lines show the PSAA curve acme location and magnitude.

Furthermore, astronomical range G_{APA} and EIDIP effects can also described the anomalous Milky Way rotation curve (refer to the MWRC EEPTs in section VIII.G). With that and that the G_{APA}^{PSAA} based PSAA curve can trace *both* Pioneer 10/11 spacecraft's data, they suggest that the PSAAs are G_{APA} induced accelerations.

1 Thermal recoil forces vs. angular EIDIP source of anomalous Pioneer sunward acceleration

The data points listed below suggest that the TRF-based model put forth by [17] is not the right model for the Pioneer 10/11 spacecraft's anomalies:

- (1) Based on figure 4 of [17], the estimated Jaccard similarity coefficient between the TRF model data and Doppler residual empirical data is approximately 20% which indicates inequality between the TRF model and empirical data;¹¹⁴
- (2) The TRF model data is slowly descending with distance of which the behavior cannot explain the

¹¹² Aka Pioneer 10/11 spacecraft's sun-ward acceleration anomaly (SWAA).

¹¹³ Note that like other magnitude formulas, the radius term r in $P_r = (P_r)_\ell = r P_\ell$ is in DSU (denoted by the subscript ℓ).

¹¹⁴ Refer to page 69-70 of [53] for the details TRF- and G_{APA} -origin PSAA models' comparison.

steep-ascending segment of the newer Pioneer 11 spacecraft's data;

- (3) In comparison, the G_{APA} -PSAA curve fits both Pioneer 10/11 spacecraft's data including the steep-ascending segment.

2 G_{APA}^{PSAA} crossover gravity distances

The non-decaying long-range G_{APA}^{PSAA} and inverse distance square gravitational G_{MGA} can reach equilibrium at some interstellar distances despite the meter-range G_{APA}^{PSAA} being much weaker than gravity. The G_{APA}^{PSAA} become noticeable and even surpass gravity approximately at $[2858]_{AU} = [1.386 \times 10^{-5}]_{kpc}$ and become dominant forces (FIG. 50).

FIG. 50. G_{APA}^{PSAA} -OCF (blue line), gravity-OCF (green line), and combined OCF (red dotted line) underlying PSAA EEPT on a log-log plane figure.

VIII. COMPOSITE EIDIP EFFECTS PHENOMENOLOGICAL TESTS

The normalized EIDIP effects functions assume the underlying two MWEPs are perfectly spherical; hence, they could deviate from the real-world EIDIP effects produced by the real-world few-body (higher-than-two-body) interactions. However, for those few-body interaction systems that can be partitioned into two sub-groups (bi-group), both possess MWEF-like energy structures, it is possible that a composite EIDIP effect that comprises the simplified two-body interaction EIDIP effects can also describe a few-body interaction with some expected artifact (aka bi-group artifact).¹¹⁵ This section contains these composite EIDIP effects phenomenological tests (composite-EEPTs): proton and neutron charge distributions, Milky Way rotation curve anomaly

¹¹⁵ E.g., the composite MWEF of three quarks within a neutron (neutron-group) looks spherical at long distances and the neutron-group and test particle can be treated as a bi-group interaction system; however, at short distances, the composite MWEF is not spherical and the effect of which becomes obvious.

¹¹⁶ The normalized EIDIP function underlying the composite-EEPTs was numerically generated by the MATLAB based on the EIDIP function

(MWRC), and effective couplings: strong, residual-strong, electrostatic, and magnetic.¹¹⁶

A. Second-order-EIDIP-effect-coupling neutron charge distribution curve phenomenological test

In Coulombic electron-scattering neutron charge distribution (NCD) measurements, the measured subatomic distance-variant expulsive and attractive centripetal force distributions are produced by the positive and negative *charge* distributions in conventional models. Contrarily in the EIDIP framework, the measurements represent subatomic expulsive and attractive NSTEE *couplings* distributions. Both the electron and the neutron possess MWEFs, and the interaction between them produces various NSTEE distributions near the neutron cores depending on the scattering angles. I.e., the measured expulsive and attractive centripetal force distributions are the result of the expulsive and attractive NSTEE, not charge distributions.

A neutron comprises three quarks; along with the electron test-projectile in the NCD measurements, they constitute a bi-group interaction system: a three-quark neutron target group and the electron projectile, both possess MWEFs.

In electron scattering NCD measurements, most of the electron-projectiles swing-by the neutron-targets and change directions; because their encounters have both the rotational and the irrotational components, they produce rotational angular EIDIP and irrotational EIDIP-gradient effects. The interest of these NCD measurements is radial force magnitude distributions. Conventionally, the distance-variant charge distributions $q(r)$ are deduced based on Coulomb's law $F_C = k_e \times q(r) \times e^2/r^2$.

In the EIDIP framework, the force distributions can be described by the distance-variant NSTEEs induced force $F_C = k_{NCD}(r) \times e^2/r^2$ with distance-variant EIDIP effects couplings; e.g., $k_{SEPC}^{NCD}(r) \propto rP_r'$, named second-order EIDIP coupling (SEPC).

With $T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$, an integer distance scaler $k_x = [1]_{DC2.5} = [R_0/(32\pi)^{2.5}]_m$, and a magnitude formula¹¹⁷

$$k_{SEPC}^{NCD}(r) \cong \left[(rP_r')_\ell (H_{Mc}^0)^2 \frac{5.3}{10^{13}} \right]_{fm^{-1}}, \quad (63)$$

the SEPC-NCD curve (light blue line) resembles the aggregated NCD mean curve of [20] (black line, FIG. 51). Note that the $rP_r' = P_d r^2 + P_r$ coupling has a rotational P_r and an irrotational $P_d r^2$ components.

equation (23) in dual columns (position and magnitude) look-up table (LUT) format. It was then numerically translated into the needed EIDIP composite function and case-dependently scaled in distance and magnitude to fit the targeted physical phenomena.

¹¹⁷ The radius term r in $(rP_r')_\ell$ is in DSU denoted by the subscript ℓ .

FIG. 51. (Color online) rP_r' ($T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$) based neutron charge distribution (rP_r' -NCD) curve (light blue line) overlaid on aggregated NCD mean curve (black line) of [20] figure.¹¹⁸

It is obvious that the SEPC-NCD curve has noticeable deviations from the empirical NCD curve, bi-group artifacts. Nonetheless, it does trace the minimum and maximum magnitude ratio of the empirical NCD curve.

B. Quadratic-EIDIP-effect-coupling neutron charge distribution curve phenomenological test

Because of neutron's bi-group composition, quadratic EIDIP effects couplings can better describe the aggregated NCD mean curve of [20] than the two-body system SEPC-NCD curve described in the last section. E.g., a quadratic EIDIP-gradient coupling (QEGC): $k_{QEGC}^{NCD}(r) \propto d/dr (P_E^2) \propto P_E \times P_d$ with $T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$, a non-integer distance scaler $k_x = [1.87]_{Dc2.5}$ with a $[-0.125]_{fm}$ distance offset, and a magnitude formula

$$k_{QEGC}^{NCD}(r) \cong \left[(P_E P_d)_\ell (H_{Mc}^0)^2 \frac{4}{10^{14}} \right]_{fm^{-1}}, \quad (64)$$

the QEGC-NCD curve (light blue curve, FIG. 52) traces the empirical NCD curve (black line, FIG. 52) at a distance longer than $[0.26]_{fm}$. Note that with the same integer distance scaler $k_x = [1]_{Dc2.5}$ as the SEPC-NCD case, the non-shifted QEGC-NCD curve (light-blue dotted line, FIG. 52) traces the empirical NCD curve's ascending segment without the distance offset.

FIG. 52. (Color online) $P_E P_d$ ($T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$) based neutron charge distribution ($P_E P_d$ -NCD) curve (light blue curve, $k_x = [1.87]_{Dc2.5}$, shifted by -0.125 femtometer, red dashed line depicts the original Y-axis and the non-shifted and $k_x = [1]_{Dc2.5}$ $P_E P_d$ -NCD curve (light blue dotted line) overlaid on aggregated NCD mean curve (black line) of [20].¹¹⁸

C. EIDIP-effects-coupling proton charge distribution curve phenomenological test

The three quarks of a proton, along with the electron test-projectile in proton charge distribution (PCD) measurements, constitute a bi-group interaction system. However, the simplified two-body interaction EIDIP can still partially describe the aggregated PCD mean curve of [20].

With $T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$, an integer distance scaler $k_x = [1]_{Dc2.5}$, and a magnitude formula

$$k_{PE}^{PCD}(r) \cong \left[(P_E)_\ell (H_{Mc}^0)^2 \frac{4}{10^{12}} \right]_{fm^{-1}}, \quad (65)$$

the P_E -PCD curve (light blue dotted curve, FIG. 53) traces the ascending segment of the aggregated PCD mean curve of [20] (black curve, FIG. 53) with an approximately $[0.08]_{fm}$ offset (red vertical dotted line, FIG. 53). However, the P_E -PCD has a more moderate post-acme slope, an artifact of using a two-body interaction EIDIP effect to model the bi-group interaction EIDIP effect. Note that, because of $k_{PCD}^+ \cong (k_{PE}^{PCD})^+ \propto P_E^+ \propto r$, the ascending segment of the aggregated PCD curve is approximately a linear distance function.

¹¹⁸ Which depicts the combined result of experiments around the globe that use polarization techniques in electron scattering (mean value shown as a black curve with uncertainty shown in red).

FIG. 53. (Color online) P_E ($T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$) based proton charge distribution (P_E -PCD) (light blue dotted curve) and P_E^2/r -PCD (light blue curve) overlaid on an aggregated PCD mean curve (black line) of [20] (red vertical dotted line: the original Y-axis of P_E -PCD line).¹¹⁸

D. Quadratic-EIDIP-effect-coupling proton charge distribution curve phenomenological test

Because the proton's quarks and electron projectile constitute a bi-group interaction system, quadratic EIDIP effects couplings are better in describing the PCD curve of [20]; e.g., a quadratic EIDIP radial unit (QERU) coupling P_E^2/r .

With $T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$, a non-integer distance scaler $k_x = [1.765]_{Dc2.5}$, and a QERU comprised magnitude formula¹¹⁹

$$k_{QERU}^{PCD}(r) \cong \left[\left(\frac{P_E^2}{r} \right)_\ell (H_{Mc}^0)^2 \frac{2.04}{10^{13}} \right]_{fm^{-1}},^{120} \quad (66)$$

the QERU-PCD curve (blue curve, FIG. 53) traces the aggregated PCD mean curve. Note that, because of $P_E^+ \propto r$ and $P_E^\infty \propto r^{-1}$, this P_E^2/r -PCD EEPT indicates the ascending segment k_{PCD}^+ is approximately a linear distance function: $(k_{QERU}^{PCD})^+ \propto (P_E^+)^2/r \propto r$; and the descending segment k_{PCD}^∞ is approximately an inverse cubic distance function: $(k_{QERU}^{PCD})^\infty \propto (P_E^\infty)^2/r \propto r^{-3}$.

E. EIDIP effects based effective strong, residual-strong, electrostatic, and magnetic couplings

The SF and NNP EEPTs have revealed that strong force and residual-strong force are induced by subatomic rotational G_{APA} and irrotational G_{PGA} . Besides the NSTEE region SEPC can approximately describe the turbulent couplings near the neutron core as shown in the rP_r' -NCD-

¹¹⁹ Note that the quadratic EIDIP based NCD and PCD curves have similar distance scaling factors $1.87_{Dc2.5}$ and $1.765_{Dc2.5}$, $P_d = d(P_E)/dr$ and P_E/r also have the same unit.

¹²⁰ The radius term r in $(P_E^2/r)_\ell$ is in DSU denoted by the subscript ℓ .

¹²¹ The X-axis is scaled with $1_{Dc2.5}$, the same as FIG. 51; whereas the Y-axis is in a normalized DSU unit.

EDPF, its components: G_{APC} and G_{PGC} can also describe the subatomic effective strong coupling (ESC) and effective residual-strong coupling (ERC). Furthermore, the long-range conformal G_{APC} and G_{PGC} can approximately describe the effective electrostatic coupling (EEC) and effective magnetic coupling (EMC) defined in the following sub-sections. I.e., the SEPC reveals the intimate relationships between these effective couplings.

The SEPC $rP_r' = P_d r^2 + P_r$ comprises an irrotational coupling $G_{PGC} \propto P_d r^2$ (green curve, FIG. 54) and a rotational coupling $G_{APC} \propto P_r$ (red curve, FIG. 54). In disparate conventional models, the NSTEE region G_{PGC} becomes the ERC and the conformal region G_{PGC}^∞ becomes the EEC; whereas the NSTEE region G_{APC} becomes the ESC and the conformal region G_{APC}^∞ becomes the EMC.

FIG. 54. (Color online) Subatomic SEPC rP_r' and components ($T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$): $P_d r^2$ and P_r figure: blue curve (NCD: ERC+ESC or EEC+EMC), red curve (ESC:EMC), and green curve (ERC:EEC).¹²¹

1 Effective strong coupling phenomenological test

With $T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$, an integer distance scaler $k_x = [1]_{Dc2.5}$, and G_{APC} magnitude normalized to [1:0], the NSTEE region G_{APC} based ESC (k_{ESC}^{APC}) curve (blue line, FIG. 55) traces those quantum chromodynamics (QCD) based effective strong couplings (ESC) of [21, p. 35] reproduced in FIG. 55.

Note that the maximum ESC distance $R_{SF}^{max} = [0.707056]_{fm}$ ¹²² (red vertical dashed line, FIG. 55) is a prominent component of the EPNCR-SEFs especially for those light nuclei (TABLE IV).

¹²² $R_{SF}^{max} = [0.707056]_{fm}$ is based on an EIDIP function generated by a MATLAB simulation with error tolerance setting 1E-14; the maximum value location, shown as red dashed line in FIG. 55, was deduced from a MATLAB spline fitted curve with 10^5 subsampling.

FIG. 55. (Color online) NSTEE region G_{APC} ($T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$) based effective strong coupling (ESC) curve (blue line) compared to the QCD ESCs of [21, p. 35].

2 Effective electrostatic coupling phenomenological test

The long-range $G_{PGC}^\infty = P_d^\infty r^2$ is approximately constant which concurs with the effective electrostatic coupling constant

$$k_{EEC} \equiv [k_e e^2]_{Nm^2}, \quad (67)$$

with k_e as Coulomb's constant, $e = [1.6022 \times 10^{-19}]_C$ as the elementary charge. With $T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$, the normalized $P_d^\infty r^2 = 24.9353$,¹²³ and a G_{PGC}^∞ comprised EEC formula

$$k_{EEC}^{PGC} = [P_d^\infty \times (2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3) \times 2_{Dc2.5}]_N^{PGA} \times [(r^2)_{\ell^2} (1_{Dc0}^2)_{(m/\ell)^2}]_{m^2}^2, \quad (68)$$

with $(1_{Dc0}^2)_{(m/\ell)^2}$ as the normalized unit area $[1^2]_{\ell^2}$ to $[1^2]_{m^2}$ conversion factor ($G_{PGC} = G_{PGA} \times r^2$), the k_{EEC}^{PGC} is approximately 4.43% lower than the k_{EEC} . Note that the $2_{Dc2.5}$ term shows the EEC's Dc2.5-domain ERC origin; and the $2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3$ term also appears in other gradient-EEPTs magnitude formulas: IACF, NGCD, and NNP.¹²⁴

Equation (68) can be simplified to

$$k_{EEC}^{PGC} = [P_d^\infty r^2 \times H_{kg}^0 \times 4/(32\pi)^{2.5}]_{Nm^2}^{PGC}. \quad (69)$$

with $(32\pi)^{2.5}$ as the IDTC (T_c) between Dc0 and Dc2.5-domains.¹²⁵ Note that the uncannily simple H_{kg}^0 and T_c components of equation (69) affirm the relationship between G_{PGC}^∞ and $k_e e^2$ is likely not coincidental.

¹²³ Based on the MATLAB simulation: $T_c = (32\pi)^{2.5}$, end point 10^{12} , and error tolerance 10^{-22} . The long-range P_r^∞ and $P_d^\infty r^2$ have the same normalized values approximately.

3 Effective magnetic coupling phenomenological test

The long-range $G_{APC}^\infty = P_r^\infty$ is approximately constant which concurs with the effective magnetic coupling constant

$$k_{EMC} \equiv \mu_0 e^2 c^2 / 4\pi = [\alpha \hbar c]_{Nm^2},^{126} \quad (70)$$

with μ_0 as the vacuum permeability, α as the fine structure constant and \hbar as the reduced Planck constant. With $T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$, a normalized $P_r^\infty = 24.9353$,¹²³ and a $G_{APA} = P_r^\infty / r^2$ comprised EMC formula

$$k_{EMC}^{APC} = [(P_r^\infty / r^2) \times (2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3) \times 2_{Dc2.5}]_N^{APA} \times [(r^2)_{\ell^2} (1_{Dc0}^2)_{(m/\ell)^2}]_{m^2}^2, \quad (71)$$

with $(1_{Dc0}^2)_{(m/\ell)^2}$ as the normalized unit area $[1^2]_{\ell^2}$ to $[1^2]_{m^2}$ conversion factor ($G_{APC} = G_{APA} \times r^2$), the k_{EMC}^{APC} is approximately 4.43% lower than the k_{EMC} . Note that the $2_{Dc2.5}$ term shows the EMC's Dc2.5-domain ESC origin; and the $2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3$ term also appears in other gradient-EEPTs magnitude formulas as the EEC EEPT.

Equations (71) can be simplified to

$$k_{EMC}^{APC} = [P_r^\infty \times H_{kg}^0 \times 4/(32\pi)^{2.5}]_{Nm^2}^{APC}, \quad (72)$$

with $(32\pi)^{2.5}$ as the IDTC (T_c) between Dc0 and Dc2.5-domains. Note that the uncannily simple H_{kg}^0 and T_c components of the k_{EMC}^{APC} formula affirm the relationship between the G_{APC}^∞ and $\alpha \hbar c$ is likely not coincidental.

The EEC, EMC, NCD, and PCD EEPTs also show that, in addition to the positive and negative charges, the ESC, ERC, EEC, and EMC can be described by the EIDIP effects couplings from the interaction of MWEPTs (gravitational potential). These EEPTs affirm that the EIDIP framework can unify the gravitational interaction with the strong and EM interactions.

4 k_{EEC}^{PGC} and k_{EMC}^{APC} deviation source

The source of the k_{EEC}^{PGC} and k_{EMC}^{APC} 's 4.43% deviation from the k_{EEC} and k_{EMC} deserves further investigations. Ignoring these defined constants: μ_0 , c , and k_e , the possible deviation sources are P_r^∞ , P_d^∞ , H_{kg}^0 , e , α , \hbar , and unaccounted EIDIP effects.

The P_r^∞ , P_d^∞ , and H_{kg}^0 are unlikely to be the major deviation sources. The relative uncertainty of the measured Higgs boson mass is about 0.63% for the ATLAS and 0.72% for the CMS. Because the Higgs-boson-like mass H_{kg}^0 derived from the NBE EEPT deviates approximately 0.3% from the mean value of ATLAS and CMS measurements, the deviation is well below the uncertainty

¹²⁴ IACF: equation (54), NGCD: equation (56), and NNP: equation (58).

¹²⁵ $T_c = [1]_{Dc0} / [1]_{Dc2.5} = (32\pi)^{2.5}$.

¹²⁶ $\mu_0 = 2\alpha h / (e^2 c)$, $\hbar = h / (2\pi)$, and $[1]_{Dc2.5} = (32\pi)^{2.5} c$.

of both the ATLAS and the CMS. Hence, the H_{kg}^0 is unlikely to be the major source of the 4.43% deviation. Both the P_r^∞ and the P_d^∞ values are calculated at a normalized distance $[10^{12}]_e$ with error tolerance 10^{-22} such that their errors should be way below the 4.43% range; hence, they are also unlikely to be the major deviation sources.

Although these measured constants: e , α , and \hbar have very low uncertainty, they are codependent constants: $e^2 \propto \alpha\hbar$. Note that e is defined as the electric charge carried by a single proton. The NCD and PCD EEPs have shown that these Coulombic *charge* distributions are the NSTEE couplings distributions. Hence, the elementary charge e derived from proton charge measurements, which require charge density form factors derived from experiments, would include some omitting EIDIP effects induced artifacts (OEIAs) and need some adjustments.

Other unaccounted EIDIP effects could also be the deviation contributors and affect the derived e value. E.g., the rP'_r -NCD curve has a noticeable deviation from the closer fit $P_E P_d$ -NCD curve; The deviation between the $P_E P_d$ and rP'_r could contribute to the 4.43% deviation and muddle the derived elementary charge constant. The 4.43% deviation sources are fertile grounds for future discoveries.¹²⁷

5 Long-range composite EIDIP effects' neutralizing effects

FIG. 54 shows that the EIDIP effects are turbulent in the hadron radius range and that both the long-range ESC and the ERC have similar strengths but with opposite signs (both the P_r^∞ and the P_d^∞ have approximately the same 24.935 normalized value). Their sum is close to zero and is an inverse distance function ($rP'_r \propto r^{-1}$) based on the MATLAB simulation shown in FIG. 56.¹²⁸ I.e., the long-range ESC and ERC neutralize each other, an example of the long-range composite EIDIP effects' neutralizing (LCEN) effect. The LCEN effect can explain the short interaction range of the strong interaction.

FIG. 56. (Color online) Long-range $rP'_r \propto r^{-1}$ because it has a -1 slope approximately in log-log presentation figure.

F. EIDIP effects Milky Way rotation curve phenomenological tests

From measurements of stars and hydrogen clouds in a galactic disk, astronomers construct a rotation velocity (RV) curve, aka rotation curve (RC), for the galaxy. The "rotation" part of the term refers to the motion of the disk as a whole. The rotation curve is used to calculate the amount of mass inside a given distance from the center [22].

Astronomical range EIDIP effects can range from noticeable to dominant compared with gravity. Because Newtonian Kepler's laws do not account for EIDIP effects, galaxy rotation curves can deviate from Keplerian predictions and require additional dark matter distribution form factors to explain the deviations.

Galaxy rotation curves have a steep-ascending segment and moderate-then-slow descending segment. Some of them have shapes similar to P_r functions; e.g., the Milky Way rotation curve (MWRC) based on the observed circular velocities of [23] (CMWRC) has such a shape (FIG. 57).

1 CMWRC phenomenological tests

Presuming the MW galactic disk has constant density, the center of mass of such a body is the integral of the galactic radius r over the mass within. With a simplified radial-quadratic (RQ) galactic disk mass model $M_{kg}^{RQ} = M_{kg}^{ISO} (r^2 / 8_{kpc}^2)$ and a quadratic EIDIP radial unit (QERU) P_E^2 / r effect induced centripetal force, a hybrid QERU- and gravity- origin centripetal forces (OCFs) produced MWRC

¹²⁷ One way to compensate for the deviation between the $P_E P_d$ and rP'_r is to define an effective elementary charge to $e_e = \sqrt[3]{1.0463} \times e = 1.0152 \times e$ (two orders for e^2 term in the k_{EEC} and k_{EMC} , and one order e underlying the H_{kg}^0 from which the H_{kg}^0 is derived). Another way is to use the alternative Higgs-boson-like mass $H_{ykg}^0 = 1.03 \times H_{kg}^0$ (equation

(49)) in the EEC and EMC formulas; if we do that, both the k_{EEC}/k_{EEC}^{EEC} and the k_{EMC}/k_{EMC}^{APC} ratios will be reduced to 1.016.

¹²⁸ With a ≈ -1.0038 linear slope in the log-log plane which represents an inverse distance function. Note that, because MATLAB gradient function approximates a derivation operation, the linear slope is an approximation.

(QG-MWRC) can fit the CMWRC:

$$v_c^{QG} = \sqrt{r k_M M_{kg}^{RQ} (k_E k_A G_{QERU}^{MWRC} + \frac{g_m}{r^2})}, \quad (73)$$

and

$$G_{QERU}^{MWRC} = \left(P_E \times \frac{P_E}{r} \right) (H_{kg}^0)^2; \quad (74)$$

with g_m as the gravitational constant, k_E as the QERU to gravity-OCFs ratio, $M_{kg}^{ISO} \cong 1.11 M_{kg}^{sta}$, $M_{kg}^{sta} = 6.43 \times 10^{10} M_\odot$ as the upper bound of estimated MW stellar mass, $k_M \cong 1/(1+k_E)$ as the MW required mass scaler. ¹³¹ I.e., the QERU to gravity OCFs ratios affect galaxies' mass estimates.

With $T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$, an integer distance scaler $k_x = [4]_{Dx5}$, ¹³² $k_A \cong 2.35$, ¹³³ and $k_E = 16$ as an example, the QERU-OCF dominant QG-MWRCs (blue line, green line with $[4]_{2Dx5}$ offset, FIG. 57) trace the ascending and slow-descending segments of the observed RV of [23].

FIG. 57. (Color online) QERU ($T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$) dominant $k_E = 16$ QG-MWRC (blue line), overlaid on observed MW RVs (open circles and squares) figures (reproduced from figure 4 of [23]).¹³⁴

2 Majority of centripetal force underlying MWRC is from QERU, not gravity

It is worth noting that the higher the gravity's contribution, the worse the QG-MWRC's fit, and the higher the required MW mass. E.g., compared with the QERU-OCF dominant ($k_E = 16$) QG-MWRC (blue line in FIG. 58), a gravity-dominant ($k_E = 1/16$) QG-MWRC (red line in FIG. 58) requires 16 times ISO mass ($k_M = 16/17$ instead of $k_M = 1/17$) and has a steep slope and almost no overshoot around $[1]_{kpc}$. I.e., the higher the QERU to gravity OCFs ratio, the better the QG-MWRC

¹²⁹ The $M_{kg}^{ISO} \cong 1.11 M_{kg}^{sta}$ is set to this value so that both the EIDIP effect and the gravity OCF only v_c^{MW} magnitude is approximately $[200]_{km/s}$ at sun's galactic radius $[8]_{kpc}$.

¹³⁰ $M_{kg}^{sta} = 6.43 \times 10^{10} M_\odot$ as the upper bound of estimated MW stellar mass [49]; the estimated MW stellar mass which ranges between $4.6 \times 10^{10} M_\odot$ to $6.43 \times 10^{10} M_\odot$.

¹³¹ The QERU-OCF contribution reduces the required MW-ISO mass; this is because gravitational coupling is constant; hence, the only way to fit the reduced gravity's contribution is to reduce the mass.

¹³² The DSU of the 4^*Dx5 -harmonic.

fits. In addition to lowering the required stellar mass to fit the CMWRC, the better fit $k_E = 16$ QG-MWRC indicates that the majority of the centripetal force underlying the CMWRC is from the EIDIP effect, not gravity.¹³⁵

Galaxies rotation curves comprise a fast ascending segment, reaching the maximum rotational velocity v_{max} at a radius r_{max} (aka the turnover radius), and a moderate-ascending to slow-descending second segment (aka the turnover segment). Because the turnover segment's gradients of the QG-MWRCs are related to their systematic EIDIP effect to gravity OCFs ratios k_E , the QG-MWRCs with various k_E values are capable to describe many galaxies' rotation curves.

Because galaxies' angular velocities affect their systematic EIDIP effect to gravity OCFs ratios, the fitted QG-MWRCs' shapes can provide additional clues for the dynamics and structures of these galaxies. E.g., the lower the gradients of galaxies' turnover RC segments, the higher their systematic EIDIP effect to gravity OCFs ratio k_E , the faster their rotation speeds, and the lower their required mass scaler $k_M \cong 1/(1+k_E)$. Their RCs' overshoot radii also indicate their EIDIP effects xE-domains and speed. Furthermore, the QG-MWRC in the NSTEE region can also explain galactic rings (refer to FIG. 66 in section VIII.G.4).¹³⁶

FIG. 58. Gradients of RCs' turnover segment are related to their systematic EIDIP effect to gravity OCFs ratios k_E examples figure: $k_E = 16$ (blue line), $k_E = 1$ (green line) and $k_E = 1/16$ (red line) of QG-MWRCs.

¹³³ The EIDIP effect scaler k_A is set to this value so that the QERU-OCF only ($k_E = 1$ and no g_m/r^2 term) QG-MWRC can trace the MWRC.

¹³⁴ The observed RV are shown by open circles and the most recent accurate results from VERA (Honma et al. 2007; Oh et al. 2010) are shown by squares; only those observed RV (open circles and squares) are relevant to this EEP. The green dotted line of the QERU dominant NQ-MWR mostly traces the blue line of the QERU only QG-MWRC.

¹³⁵ This finding concurs with the high dark matter ratio required in the conventional MWRC models.

¹³⁶ These implications can be used as the EIDIP framework's predictions.

3 Reference-centric NSTEE overshoots can boost and smear the overshoot of observed CMWRC

The $G_{QERU}^{MWRC}(r)$ effects are segmented with very different behaviors: ascending $(P_E^2/r)^+ \propto r$ and descending $(P_E^2/r)^\infty \propto r^{-3}$.¹³⁷ Combining that with the radial-quadratic mass model $M_{kg}^{RQ}(r) \propto r^2$, the simplified $G_{QERU}^{MWRC}(r)M_{kg}^{RQ}(r)$ model would produce a narrow ascending and overshoot region MWRC compared with the observed MWRC that includes the results of the target-centric incremental mass (purple or blue dot-dashed circles, FIG. 59) interacting with the mixed-segments of the reference-centric $[0:8_{DSU}]$ region $G_{QERU}^{MWRC}(r)$ (disk region within the red or blue dotted circle, FIG. 59) that would produce a gentler ascending segment and wider overshoot, i.e., a smeared-overshoot region.

To fully describe the smeared-overshoot artifact requires complicated MATLAB programs. However, it can be explained figuratively. FIG. 59 depicts three P_r shaped QG-MWRCs overshoots on the galactic plane (sloped-line shaded circular bands): a GC-centric and two star-centric at galactic locations: $X_1 = [4]_{DSU}$ and $X_2 = [8]_{DSU}$, and the figure-insert depicts their radial P_r shaped magnitude. For this discussion, the $R = [4]_{DSU}$ is the overshoot's outer boundary where the normalized P_r magnitude reduced to 91% of its peak value, the $R = [1.55]_{DSU}$ is the overshoot's inner boundary where the P_r has the same magnitude, and the $R = [8]_{DSU}$ is where the GC- and reference-centric overshoots (RCOS) regions (cross-line shaded disks, FIG. 59) start to separate.¹³⁸

For stars at X_1 , even though they are out of the GC-centric overshoot region, their reference- and GC-centric overshoot regions' overlap is sizeable (dark yellow shaded area with cross lines, FIG. 59); which can boost and extend the observed CMWRC overshoot from the simplified QG-MWRC. For stars at X_2 and beyond, although their overshoot regions do not overlap with the GC-centric overshoot region, their overshoot regions within the target-centric $R = [8]_{DSU}$ circle (dark yellow shaded area with sloped lines, FIG. 59) are still sizeable enough to boost and extend the observed overshoot of the CMWRC.

However, as the radius increases, the sizes of the boosting RCOS regions settle to constant (half ring maximum, i.e., do not change much) whereas the conformal interaction contribution from the remaining disk region increases with radius. With a simplified radial-quadratic (RQ) galactic disk mass model, the effective (inner-disk) mass is proportional to the radius squared, and the RCOS contribution is inversely proportional to the distances squared approximately.¹³⁹ I.e., the longer the radius, the lower their RCOS contributing ratio which would add a slow-descending boosting right after the acme on top of the P_r shaped QG-MWRC. Hence, although the RCOS boosting effects are noticeable right after the acme

of the observed CMWRC, they are not noticeable in the long range such that the P_r shaped QG-MWRC can still trace the observed CMWRC.

FIG. 59. (Color online) Target-centric incremental mass interacts with reference-centric mixed-segments QERU effects figure; (insert subfigure) normalized P_r curve.¹³⁸

Taking the smeared-overshoot artifact into account, the CMWRC can be better fitted, in some aspects, with a smaller distance scaler $k_x = [2]_{Dx5} = [1]_{2 \times Dx5}$ produced QG-MWRC. E.g., FIG. 60 depicts two updated QG-MWRCs: a non-shifted QG-MWRC (blue line) and a $[4]_{2 \times Dx5} \cong [0.43]_{k_{DC}}$ shifted QG-MWRC (green line) to emulate the smeared-overshoot effect, both produced by an updated distance scaler $k_x = [2]_{Dx5}$, and an updated $k_A \cong 2.35 \times 8 = 18.8$. Note that the updated QG-MWRC trace the CMWRC's ascending segment and overshoot's rising slope better than the original QG-MWRC shown in FIG. 57, the shifted QG-MWRC trace the falling slope of the CMWRC overshoot, and all three QG-MWRCs trace the settle-to-constant segment (conformal region) of the CMWRC.

¹³⁷ Because of the ascending $P_E^2 \propto r$ and descending $P_E^2 \propto r^{-1}$.

¹³⁸ To simplify the discussion, assuming the target- and reference-centric P_r curves have the same overshoot width and location.

¹³⁹ $R_{RCOS/cfml} = F_{RCOS}A_{ROCS}/(F_{RCOS}A_{ROCS} + F_{cfml}(\pi r^2 - A_{ROCS}))$ with F_{RCOS} as the RCOS region OCF contribution per unit area, F_{cfml} as

the conformal region OCF contribution per unit area, and A_{ROCS} as the RCOS area. Because of $A_{ROCS} \rightarrow cst$ at a distance, $R_{RCOS/cfml} \propto r^{-2}$.

FIG. 60. (Color online) QERU ($T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$) dominant $k_E = 16$ QG-MWRCs (blue line, green line with $[4]_{2 \times D_{x5}}$ offset) with updated distance scaler $k_x = [2]_{D_{x5}}$ and $k_A = 18.8$, overlaid on observed RVs (upper subfigure, reproduced from figure 4 of [23]).

4 MWRC overshoot radius can reveal underlying Gravity and EIDIP effects speed

Because EIDIP effects have rigid shapes when their shaping T_c values are set, their acme locations, even with the smeared-overshoot artifacts, can reveal which xE-domains the underlying EIDIP effects and high order gravity OCFs operate in. E.g., a normalized $T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4} P_r$ curve peaks at $[2.16]_{D_{SU}}$, the acme location of the QERU effects dominant P_r shaped QG-MWRC peaks at $[0.43]_{kpc} \cong [2.16]_{4 \times D_{x5}}$; which indicates that the underlying high order gravity and EIDIP effects operate in the D_{x5} -domian harmonic $4 \times D_{x5}$ -domain.

Because E-domains, including their harmonic E-domains, have the speed limits of $[2]_{D_{SU}/s}$, the acme location indicates that the OCFs underlying the observed MWRC operate with a speed limit of $[2]_{D_{x5}/s} \approx [10^{10}c]_{m/s}$. The asserted gravity and EIDIP effects speed is in the same order of magnitude, but approximately half of, the observed gravity speed $> [2 \times 10^{10}c]_{m/s}$ based purely on observed gravity-OCF from the solar system and binary stars [6].²³ Note that the gravity speed calculations of [6] did not account for the EIDIP effects which could have induced the higher gravity speed calculation, a type of omitting EIDIP effect artifact (OEIA).

G. RAVE-DR2 Milky Way rotation curve phenomenological tests

Granted that our universe started with zero-sum kinetic energy, the stars should start with an omnidirectional velocity distribution; i.e., the average radial and ortho-radial velocities of all the stars existed then should be zero initially. Over time, stars gained various (positive or negative) radial galactic velocities because of the

interaction with other stars; the effect of which would affect the current rotational velocity (RV) to galactic radius relationship and muddle the observed rotation curve (RC).

However, because stars “remember” the dynamics of their orbits at the time of formation (dynamics of stellar systems is dissipation-less) [24], the radial velocity’s muddling on the current RV should be averaged out with a large enough number of stars.¹⁴⁰ Because centripetal forces induced RVs are transversal (bi-directional), MW stars’ absolute RVs’ mean curves should better trace the systemic MWRC. I.e., the radial bin-averaged absolute (RBAA) MW stars’ RC should resemble the systemic MWRC.

Because galaxies’ rotation planes may not align with the MW systematic rotation plane, the galactic-center (GC) centric centripetal forces induced transverse accelerations are *spherically* ortho-radial; i.e., they are not limited to the *cylindrical* ortho-radial accelerations on the galactic-plane (GP). Hence, the following sections present two types of MWRC EEPTs based on two types of ortho-radial velocities (ORV) of those 16157 Milky Way stars listed in the CDS RAVE-DR2 catalog [25]:¹⁴¹ *cylindrical* ORV (CORV, CgV_o, V_ϕ : green cross-dot toward paper, FIG. 61) curve (LMWRC) and *spherical* ORV (SORV, SgV_o) curve (SMWRC).¹⁴² The SMWRC is better in revealing the stars’ GC-centric centripetal forces; whereas the LMWRC is better in revealing their ortho-GP positional velocities influencers, e.g., the AEAAN effects.

The MWRC EEPTs presented in the following sections employ the same $T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$ EIDIP effects with an integer distance scaler $k_x = [4]_{D_{x5}}$ as the original CMWRC EEPT. Note that, because very few of the RAVE-DR2 stars resides outside the conformal region, their rotation curves are not sensitive to the distance scalers; hence, with different k_A values, they can also be fitted with other distance scalers; e.g., $[1]_{D_{x5}}$ and $[2]_{D_{x5}}$.

¹⁴⁰ With a large enough sample size, an averaging operation can average out random noises.

¹⁴¹ Note that, in the RAVE-DR2 catalog, the ortho-radial V_ϕ (V_{ϕ}), radial velocity V_ρ (V_{ρ}), and V_z velocities are in cylindrical coordinates.

¹⁴² $CgV_o = \vec{V}_\phi$ (green cross-dot toward paper, FIG. 61); $SgV_o = \vec{V}_\theta + \vec{V}_\rho$. $V_\theta = -V_\rho \sin \theta + V_z \cos \theta$ (blue dotted arrow, FIG. 61) with θ as stars’ galactic inclination angle to the galactic disk, and V_ρ and V_z as stars’ *cylindrical* radial and Z velocities.

FIG. 61. RAVE-DR2 cylindrical radial ρ , ortho-radial angle φ , and Z velocities (V_ρ , V_φ , and V_z green dotted arrows and toward paper cross-dot), and *spherical* radial velocity V_r and ortho-radial angle θ velocity V_θ (blue dotted arrows) figure.

1 SMWRC phenomenological tests

The QG-MWRC can also describe the spherical SORV curve of the RAVE-DR2 MW stars (SMWRC). With the same $k_A = 18.8$, $[2]_{D_{x5}}$ distance scaler, and radial-quadratic galactic disk mass model as the updated CMWRC EEPT, FIG. 62 depicts the RAVE-DR2 MW stars SORV distribution, a $[0.2]_{kpc}$ binned RBAA-SgV_o (aka SMWRC), and a primary $k_E = 1$ and comparative $k_E = 16$ QG-MWRCs along the *spherical* galactic radius. Which shows that the SMWRC is approximately linear in the high star count region but fits better by the steeper $k_E = 1$ QG-MWRC. Note that the SMWRC's steeper gradient is mainly caused by the AEAAN effects that dilute the QERU effects on those stars away from the galactic midplane (refer to FIG. 64 and FIG. 65 in section VIII.G.3).

There are alternative SMWRC EEPTs; e.g., with an alternative point mass model, the SMWRC can be described by an angular EIDIP P_r effect; refer to Appendix V.1 for details.

FIG. 62. (Color online) RAVE-DR2 MW stars' spherical ortho-radial RV (color dots), RBAA-SgV_o (SMWRC, magenta line), and QG-MWRCs ($k_E = 1$: blue line, $k_E = 16$: blue dotted line) along *spherical* galactic radius figure.^{143,144}

2 LMWRC phenomenological tests

The RAVE-DR2 MW stars' RBAA-cylindrical-ORV

¹⁴³ RAVE-DR2 star SORV is shown with color dots, the color of which indicates whether the QG-SMWRC (blue line) intersects with (cyan) or out of (orange) the star's uncertainty range; the comparative fitting curve is shown as a dotted blue line; black dashed line shows binned star count and magenta dashed line shows sun's galactic radius $[8]_{kpc}$.

¹⁴⁴ Title section legend shows the stars' velocities to the primary EIDIP effect fitting curve (blue line) deviation statistics for comparison reasons: RMS: root mean square, MAD: mean absolute deviation, STD: standard

curve (LMWRC, magenta line, FIG. 63) resembles a squared root function rather than the linear functions of the SMWRC (magenta line, FIG. 62) in the high star count region. However, the RBAA-cylindrical-ORV curve can be traced by an angular EIDIP-gradient (AEG) P_r' and gravity OCFs induced acceleration with the same radial-quadratic (RQ) galactic disk mass model as the CMWRC and SMWRC EEPTs. I.e., The EIDIP effect portion of equation (73) can be rewritten for LMWRC as

$$v_c^{AG} = \sqrt{rk_M M_{kg}^{RQ} (k_E k_A G_{AEG}^{MWRC} + \frac{g_m}{r^2})}, \quad (75)$$

and

$$G_{AEG}^{MWRC} \cong -P_r' (H_{kg}^0)^2. \quad (76)$$

With $k_A = 5.25$,¹⁴⁵ the hybrid AEG and gravity OCFs produced MWRC (AG-MWRC) trace the LMWRC for both the $k_E = 1$ and the $k_E = 16$ cases (FIG. 63). The AEG to gravity OCFs ratio k_E has no big effect on the shape of AG-MWRCs because both the gravity and P_r' OCFs are proportional to the inverse distance square.¹⁴⁶

There are alternative LMWRC EEPTs; e.g., with an alternative radial-linear mass model, the LMWRC can be fitted with a second-order EIDIP coupling (SEPC, rP_r') effect as the rP_r' -NCD EEPT; refer to Appendix V.2 for details.

FIG. 63. RAVE-DR2 MW stars' cylindrical ortho-radial RV (color dots), RBAA-CgV_o (LMWRC, magenta line), and AG-MWRCs ($k_E = 16$: blue line, $k_E = 1$: blue dotted line) along cylindrical galactic radius figure.^{143,144}

3 Different shapes of SMWRC, LMWRC, and CMWRC

The different shapes of the circular, spherical, and cylindrical MWRCs are mainly caused by the AEAAN

deviation, and WUR: within uncertainty range; Note that the EIDIP effect fitting magnitude scaler, k_A [parameter value], affects the deviation statistics.

¹⁴⁵ k_A is set to this value such that the MWRC curve (blue line) magnitude is approximately $[200]_{km/s}$ at sun's galactic radius $[8]_{kpc}$. The k_A could be set to a lower value to better fit the RBAA curve.

¹⁴⁶ $P_r' \propto r^{-2}$ because of $rP_r' \propto r^{-1}$ (FIG. 56).

effects acting on those stars away from the galactic midplane (GMP). The RAVE-DR2 stars are a collection of local stars on the cylindrical galactic plane (GP) including those stars away from the galactic midplane. Although gravity is omnidirectional, AEAAN effects are not. Because these stars reside in the EIDIP effects dominant region where the AEAAN effects on their velocities vary with their inclination angles, the AEAAN effects can induce different shapes of GMP-centric CMWRC,¹⁴⁷ GP-centric LMWRC, and GC-centric SMWRC.

The QERU and mass (QEM) effect portion of equation (73) can be rewritten as $V_c(r) = (P_{QEM})^{0.5}$ with $P_{QEM} = r M_{kg}^{RQ} G_{QERU}^{MWRC} \propto P_E^2 \times r^2$. The P_{QEM} acting on a star with an inclination angle δ is

$$P_{QEM}(r, \delta) \propto P_E(r_\delta)^2 \times r^2 \quad (77)$$

with $r = r_\delta \cos \delta$ as the projected on-rotation-plane inter-object distance.¹⁴⁸ Because the $P_{QEM}(r, \delta)$ effect projected on and orthogonal to the rotation plane are $P_{QEM}(r, \delta) \cos \delta$ and $P_{QEM}(r, \delta) \sin \delta$ respectively, one can derive the on-rotation-plane $P_{QEM}^p(r) \propto P_r(r_\delta)^2 \cos \delta^3$ and the ortho-rotation-plane $P_{QEM}^o(r) \propto P_r(r_\delta)^2 \cos \delta^2 \sin \delta$.¹⁴⁹ Furthermore, because most of the stars reside in the conformal region where $P_r^\infty(r_\delta) \cong P_r^\infty(r) \cong cnst$, one can derive

$$\begin{aligned} P_{QEM}^p(r, \delta) &\propto P_r^\infty(r)^2 \cos \delta^3, \\ P_{QEM}^o(r, \delta) &\propto P_r^\infty(r)^2 \cos \delta^2 \sin \delta. \end{aligned} \quad (78)$$

Because the ortho-GP gV_z , *cylindrical* ortho-radial CgV_o , and *cylindrical* radial CgV_r include the transversal velocities components induced by the *spherical* radial G_{QEM} ,¹⁵⁰ the AEAAN effects on these velocities are proportional to the square root of the P_{QEM} . Furthermore, the centripetal P_{QEM}^p acting on the CgV_o also acts on the radial CgV_r in addition to the stars' centrifugal inertia. To reveal the rotation curve of those stars on the rotation plane, we need to remove the AEAAN effects on the stars' velocities:

$$\begin{aligned} gV_z' &= gV_z(|\cos \delta^2 \sin \delta|^{-0.5} - k_i), \\ CgV_r' &= CgV_r(|\cos \delta|^{-1.5} - k_i), \\ CgV_o' &= CgV_o|\cos \delta|^{-1.5}. \end{aligned} \quad (79)$$

with k_i as the inertia factor.¹⁵¹ For the effects of the AEAAN effects adjustments on the gV_z and CgV_r , refer to Appendix V.4. for details. Note that the centripetal

AEAAN effects on the gV_z and CgV_r are directional whereas their effects on the CgV_o are transversal (bidirectional). I.e., the absolute $|CgV_o|$ is more accurate in revealing the transversal AEAAN effects.

With the same radial-quadratic galactic disk mass model and k_A as the CMWRC and SMWRC EEPTs, the AEAAN effects adjusted RBAA- CgV_o' now has an approximately flat in the high star count region and can be traced by the $k_E = 16$ QG-MWRC (FIG. 64) as the CMWRC EEPT.¹⁵² I.e., the AEAAN effects adjusted LMWRC now behaves like the GMP-centric CMWRC in the high star count region.

FIG. 64. (Color online) RAVE-DR2 MW stars' AEAAN effects adjusted CgV_o' (color dots), RBAA- CgV_o' (magenta line), and QG-MWRCs ($k_E = 16$: blue line, $k_E = 1$: blue dotted line) along cylindrical galactic radius figure.^{143,144}

Note that if we used the spherical-centric $P_E(r_\delta)^2$ instead of the cylindrical-centric $P_E(r_\delta)^2 \cos \delta$ to derive the AEAAN effects adjusted term for the CgV_o , i.e., $CgV_o'' = CgV_o/|\cos \delta|$, the adjusted RBAA- CgV_o'' now can be traced by the $k_E = 1$ QG-MWRC (FIG. 65) as the spherical-centric RBAA- SgV_o (FIG. 62).

¹⁴⁷ The GMP-centric description of the CMWRC is affirmed by the AEAAN effects adjusted LMWRC behaving like the CMWRC in the high star count region.

¹⁴⁸ $M_{kg}^{RQ}(r, \delta) \propto r^2$ and $G_{QERU}^{MWRC}(r, \delta) = P_E(r_\delta)^2/r$; the inter-object EIDIP effect references the inter-object distance r_δ whereas the transverse distances reference the projected distance r .

¹⁴⁹ $P_E(r_\delta) r = P_E(r_\delta) r_\delta \cos \delta = P_r(r_\delta) \cos \delta$. Note that, compared with the AEAAN effect induced force example discussed in the section IV.C.3 (equation (41)), the AEAAN effect induced potential of this case requires an additional $\cos \delta$ adjustment term.

¹⁵⁰ Note that the CgV_r and CgV_o of the RAVE-DR2 are the stars' *cylindrical* radial and ortho-radial velocities in cylindrical coordinates.

¹⁵¹ These AEAAN effects adjustments only account for the magnitude of the AEAAN effects.

¹⁵² Note that, because the stars' galactic Z position uncertainties increase with heliocentric galactic radius distances (FIG. 79) and the stars' velocities uncertainties increase with their heliocentric distances (FIG. 80), the adjusted RBAA- CgV_o' curve is expected to have higher swings in the low star count extremities than the unadjusted cases (FIG. 78).

FIG. 65. (Color online) RAVE-DR2 MW stars' AEAAN effects adjusted CgV_o'' (color dots), RBAA- CgV_o'' (magenta line), and QG-MWRCs ($k_E = 1$: blue line, $k_E = 16$: blue dotted line) along *spherical* galactic radius figure.^{143,144}

In addition to the AEAAN effects adjusted gV_z' and CgV_r' have approximately the same gradients between the first-order ISO and OSO region fitted lines (refer to FIG. 81 in Appendix V.4), the AEAAN effects adjusted LMWRC now has a similar gradient as the SMWRC and CMWRC. Furthermore, these adjustments also affirm the stars' velocities are influenced mostly by the G_{QEM} -OCF because gravity-OCF would have added an additional $\cos \delta^{-0.5}$ adjustment term.¹⁵³ These facts valid the existence AEAAN effects and in turn the EIDIP effects.

4 Galactic gravitational force ripple and negative gravitational force regions

Because of xE-domain NSTEEs, the combination of the astronomical range Gravity and EIDIP effects can produce astronomical gravitational force ripples (GFR) that may include negative (reversed direction) gravitational force (NGF) regions. E.g., the hybrid QERU and gravity OCFs of the $k_E = 16$ QG-MWRC underlying the MWRC EEPs produces such a GFR region (blue dashed box, FIG. 66).¹⁵⁴ Whereas the hybrid AEG and gravity OCFs of the $k_E = 1$ AG-MWRC underlying the LMWRC EEP produces a GFR region that includes an NGF region (red dashed box, FIG. 67).¹⁵⁵

¹⁵³ The gravity-OCF portion of equation (73) can be rewritten as $v_c^G = \sqrt{r k_M M_{kg}^{ISO} / 8_{kpc}^2 g_m} \propto \sqrt{r}$ and $gV_z^{(G)} \approx v_c^G \sin \delta \propto \sin \delta_\phi \sqrt{r}$; hence, the gravity-OCF induced $v_c^G \propto \sqrt{r} \propto (r \cos \delta)^{-0.5}$ vs. $v_c^{QERU} \propto cnst$.

¹⁵⁴ Equation (73) with $k_x = [4]_{Dx5}$, $k_A = 2.35$, $k_E = 16$, and $k_M \cong 1/(1+k_E)$.

FIG. 66. QERU (blue line), gravity (green line) and combined (red dotted line) OCFs, and GRF region (blue dashed box) underlying $k_E = 16$ QG-MWRC figure.

FIG. 67. AEG-OCF (blue line), gravity-OCF (green line), combined OCF (red dotted line) induced negative gravitational force (NGF) region (red dashed box) and gravitational force ripple (GFR) region (blue dashed box) underlying $k_E = 1$ AG-MWRC figure.

Note that the GFR and NGF regions can affect the stars distributions and induce galactic rings. E.g., because of the high (approximate 280) peak-to-ground ratio of the QG-MWRC, the GFR can nudge MW stars to stay in this region and induce a galactic "band" structure between $[0.024]_{kpc}$ and $[133]_{kpc}$.¹⁵⁶ Furthermore, the steeper the GFR's gradient, the denser the stars congregated near the maximum rotational velocity radius, aka the turnover radius; i.e., the steeper ascending segment of GFRs are also likely to induce turnover rings.

¹⁵⁵ AG-MWRC centripetal force: $k_M M_{kg}^{RQ} (k_E k_A G_{AEG}^{LMWRC} + g_m / r^2)$, $k_x = [4]_{Dx5}$, $k_A = 5.25$; $k_E = 1$ is chosen to show the AEG and gravity OCFs effects more clearly.

¹⁵⁶ Although the MW radial-quadric mass model can be fair representations for EIDIP effects OCFs calculations in the *conformal* region (the stable region in the second MWRC segment), the mass models are only approximations for the OCFs calculations in the NSTEE region (the MWRC's ascending and overshoot region) because of the turbulent and nonlinear EIDIP effects.

Furthermore, although the AG-MWRC's GFR range $\sim 5 \times 10^{-10}$ shown in FIG. 67 is lower than the QG-MWRC's GFR range $\sim 5 \times 10^{-9}$ shown in FIG. 66, because of the narrower the GFR region, the higher the ripples' gradient such that the AG-MWRC's GFR can still induce the star distribution ripple around $[2.16]_{4 \times D_{x5}} = [0.43]_{k_{pc}}$ near the MWRC's turnover radius and produce a turnover ring.

Note that these star distribution ripples implications near the turnover radii concur with the observed very bright inner ring lies virtually exactly at the turnover radius of rotation curves [26]. Furthermore, the GFR locations reveal the underlying EIDIP effects' E-domains; hence, they can be used to distill their speed.

IX. EEPT SUMMARY AND IMPLICATIONS

This section contains the distance and magnitude formula summary table (TABLE V), the EEPTs' distribution in paired cE- and xE- domains overview figure (FIG. 68), and the commonalities among and implications of the 10+ EEPTs. Because the normalized EIDIP effects functions used in the EEPTs are single shaping-parameter nonlinear functions of distance, they have semi-rigid shapes.¹⁵⁷ Hence, they enable us to distill the underlying meanings of distance and magnitude scaling factors, especially those terms shared among the EEPTs. Furthermore, because the EIDIP framework is nonperturbative, these EEPTs provide insights into areas perturbative methods cannot reveal.

FIG. 68. Symmetrical cE- and xE- domains EIDIP effects (SCXEE) and EEPTs distribution overview figure. Shaded color: NSTEE, solid color: conformal region, partition not to scale. Dark and light blue shades: *rotational* P_r effect induced force and coupling, dark and light green shades: *irrotational* P_d effect induced force and coupling, dark purple shade: P_E effect induced phenomena, orange shade: composite EIDIP effects induced phenomena. Gray dashed line and shade: yet-to-be-identified physical phenomena implicated by the multiple E-domain pair (MEP) hypothesis (section X.C.4). Italic texts indicate yet to be verified EEPTs: gravitoelectromagnetism (sections X.C.2 and X.D.19) which includes galactic effective couplings: GSC, GRC, GMC, and GEC (section X.D.19), GW: gravity wave, A. jet: astrophysical jet, NEFA: near-Earth-fly-by anomalies (section X.D.22). (* gravitoelectromagnetism is likely describing the stable behaviors of conformal EIDIP effects, e.g., GMC and GEC.)

TABLE V. EEPTs' distance scaler and magnitude formula table (# superscript denotes a NHTN status).

EIDIP applications	Distance scaler	Magnitude formula	IDTC (T_c)
PSAA #158	$[1]_{D_{x2}}$ #159	$[P_r \times H_{kg}^0 \times M_\odot \times (2_{D_{c2}}^2) \times 1_{D_{x2}}]_N^{APA}$ #160	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$ #161
PG-MWRC: P_r	$[4]_{D_{x5}}$	$[P_r \times H_{kg}^0 \times M_{kg}^{EP} \times (2_{D_{c2}}^2) \times 4 \times k'_M]_N^{162, \#160}$ $[P_r \times H_{kg}^0 \times M_{kg}^{EP'} \times (2_{D_{c5}}^2) \times 1_{D_{x5}} \times k'_M]_N^{162}$	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$
Bohr Radius #158	$[1]_{D_{c0}}$ #159	$[P_r]_{D_{c0}}$	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$ #161
SF #158	$[1]_{D_{c2.5}}$ #159	$[P_r^\infty \times 2H_{kg}^0 \times (2_{D_{x2.5}}^2)]_N^{APA}$ #160	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$ #161
ESC #158	$[1]_{D_{c2.5}}$ #159	$[P_r]_{D_{c2.5}}$	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$ #161
EMC (αhc) #158	$[1]_{D_{c2.5}}$	$[P_r^\infty \times 2H_{kg}^0 \times 2/(32\pi)^{2.5}]_{Nm^2}^{APC}$ #160	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$ #161

¹⁵⁷ The T_c is the only control parameter affecting the shape of the EIDIP effects functions used in the 10+ EEPTs.

¹⁵⁸ It is a primary NHTD because the single shaping-parameter EIDIP effect function plus distance and magnitude scalars can be phenomenologically fitted to the empirical figure or data.

¹⁵⁹ It is a primary NHTD because this distance scaler has integer DSU and the involved turbulent EIDIP effect curve requires a precise distance scaler fitting.

¹⁶⁰ It is a secondary NHTD because the magnitude formula has a shared term or EIDIP effect with other EEPTs.

¹⁶¹ It is a primary NHTD because the T_c value is either $(32\pi)^{1/4}$ or 32π .

¹⁶² $k'_M \approx 1$ for $k_E \gg 1$.

		$[P_r^\infty / r^2 \times (2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3) \times 2_{Dc2.5}]_N^{APA} [r^2 \times 1_{Dc0}^2]_{m^2}^{r^2}$ #160	
IACF (tip1) #158	$[4]_{Dc0}$ #159	$[P_d \times (2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3) \times M_{kg}^{IACF} / 24]_N^{PGA}$ #160	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$ #161
IACF (tip2)	$[2]_{Dc0}$ #159	$[P_d \times (2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3) \times M_{kg}^{IACF} / 4]_N^{PGA}$	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$
NGCD #158	$[1]_{Dc0}$	$[P_d^\infty \times (2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3) \times M_{kg}^{NGCD}]_N^{PGA}$ #160	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$ #161
EEC ($k_e e^2$) #158	$[1]_{Dc2.5}$	$[P_d^\infty \times (2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3) \times 2_{Dc2.5}]_N^{PGA} [r^2 \times 1_{Dc0}^2]_{m^2}^{r^2}$ #160	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$ #161
NNP (EIDIP) #158	$[1]_{Dc2.5}$ #159	$[P_d^\infty r^2 \times 2H_{kg}^0 \times 2 / (32\pi)^{2.5}]_{Nm^2}^{PGC}$	
		$[P_d \times (2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3) \times (M_{ykg}^{NNP} c^2)]_{Nm}^{PGP}$ #160	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$ #161
NNP (Reid93)	$[0.97]_{Dc2.5}$	$[P_d \times (H_{Mc}^0 c^2) \times R_0^2 \times 1.15]_{MeV}^{PGA}$ r	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$
NNP (AV18)	$[0.72]_{Dc2.5}$	$[P_d \times (H_{Mc}^0 c^2) \times R_0^2 \times 1.44]_{MeV}^{PGA}$ r	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$
NBE (BE_{ref}) #158	$[1_{Dc2} \times c^2]_A$ #159	$[P_E \times (H_{Mc}^0 c^2) \times R_0^2 \times 2 / (32\pi)]_{MeV}^{BEref}$ #160	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$ #161
		$[P_E \times H_{ykg}^0 \times R_0^2 \times 1_{Dc2}]_{Nm}^{BEref}$ #160	
NCD: rP_r' #158	$[1]_{Dc2.5}$ #159	$[rP_r' \times (H_{Mc}^0)^2 \times 5.3 \times 10^{-13}]_{fm^{-1}}$ #160	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$ #161
SG-MWRC: rP_r'	$[4]_{Dx5}$	$[rP_r' \times (H_{kg}^0)^2 \times M_{kg}^{RL} \times 5.25 \times k'_M]_N$ #162, #160	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$
AG-MWRC: P_r' #158	$[4]_{Dx5}$	$[P_r' \times (H_{kg}^0)^2 \times M_{kg}^{RQ} \times 5.25 \times k'_M]_N$ #162	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$ #161
NCD: $P_E P_d$ #158	$[1.87]_{Dc2.5}$	$[P_E P_d \times (H_{Mc}^0)^2 \times 2 \times 10^{-14}]_{fm^{-1}}$ #160	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$ #161
PCD: P_E^2 / r #158	$[1.87]_{Dc2.5}$	$[P_E^2 / r \times (H_{Mc}^0)^2 \times 2 \times 10^{-13}]_{fm^{-1}}$ #160	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$ #161
QG-MWRC: P_E^2 / r #158	$[4]_{Dx5}$ #159	$[P_E^2 / r \times (H_{kg}^0)^2 \times M_{kg}^{RQ} \times 2.35 \times k'_M]_N$ #162, #160	$(32\pi)^{1/4}$ #161

A. Commonalities among EEPTs

There are shared terms in the magnitude and distance formulas of EEPTs that cover from cE- to xE-domain phenomena (TABLE V). These isomorphic formulas can not only reveal underlying realities and connections but also provide more evidence that EIDIP effects exist in various E-domains.

1 Shared EIDIP effects, E-domains, and IDTCs

The 10+ EEPTs employ only two IDTCs: $(32\pi)^{1/4}$ and 32π . Despite operating in the different cE- and xE-domains, some EEPTs have shared the same underlying EIDIP effect as shown in grouped rows in TABLE V; e.g., despite operating in different cE-domains, the NGCD, IACF, EEC, and NNP EEPTs have shared the same EIDIP-gradient effect P_d . Although operating in different cE- and xE-domains, the atomic Bohr radius, subatomic SF, interplanetary PSAA, and galactic PG-MWRC EEPTs have shared the same angular EIDIP effect P_r' . The astronomic QG-MWRC and subatomic PCD EEPTs have also shared the same EIDIP effect P_E^2 / r whereas the

astronomic SG-MWRC and subatomic NCD EEPTs have shared the same EIDIP effect rP_r' .

These shared EIDIP effects affirm that MWEP (gravitational potential) interactions occur in a wide range of cE- and xE-domains. Because the same EIDIP effect implies the same underlying IMO structure, these shared EIDIP effects can provide more clues for the underlying IMO structures of these physical phenomena.¹⁶³

2 Shared magnitude and distance scaler terms

Most of the EEPTs have shared integer DSU distance scalars. Despite operating in different cE-domains, the NGCD, IACF, EEC, EMC, and NNP EEPTs have shared the magnitude scaler term $2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3$. The EMC and EEC EEPTs have shared the same $4H_{kg}^0 / (32\pi)^{2.5}$ magnitude scaler term. The NNP and NBE EEPTs have shared the same $(H_{Mc}^0 c^2) R_0^2$ magnitude scaler term in the SI base unit. These shared terms further affirm the EIDIP connection between these physical phenomena.

The EIDIP effects underlying the interplanetary PSAA- and subatomic SF EEPTs operate in the Dx2- and Dc2.5-domains whereas their magnitude formulas have complementary E-domains terms 2_{Dc2}^2 and $2_{Dx2.5}^2$.

¹⁶³ E.g., the Pioneer-sun spin structure gives additional clues for the projectile-quark spin structure underlying the SF; the average MW star-galactic plane spin structures give additional clues for the electron-neutron spin structure underlying the NCD and vice versa.

respectively. These complementary E-domain terms affirm the E-space contractive-expansive transform and E-domain pair hypothesis described in sections II.C.1 and II.D.

3 Target-centric EIDIP effects underlay EEPTs

In contrast to the symmetries of the SM, although the conformal EIDIP effects are object-symmetric, the NSTEE region EIDIP effects are object-asymmetric. Note that all EIDIP effects underlying the NSTEE region EEPTs (e.g., SF, NNP, NCD, PCD, PSAA, and MWRC) are *target-centric*. I conjecture that the target objects are relatively immobile or much heavier than the reference or test objects in these physical phenomena such that they produce the target-centric measurements.¹⁶⁴

B. Omitting EIDIP effects induced artifacts (OEIAs)

Because the EIDIP effects are beyond conventional physical models' limits, it is safe to assume that some current physical models and the data constructed from them could contain inaccuracies because they do not account for the EIDIP effects, hereafter referred to as the omitting EIDIP effects induced artifact (OEIA). E.g., astronomical gravitational anomalies: PSAA and galaxies rotation curves are OEIAs.

The PSAA and MWRC EEPTs have revealed that the xE-domain EIDIP effects can explain galaxies structures and behaviors beyond the Newtonian limit because, compared with gravity, the xE-domain EIDIP effects are already noticeable in the interplanetary range and can become dominant in the galactic range. Therefore, the xE-domain EIDIP effects can explain galaxies structures and behaviors beyond the capacities of conventional models; which in turn reveal the inaccuracy of Newtonian gravity model even in the interplanetary range and the inadequacy of Kepler's laws in the galactic range and beyond.

The OEIA can appear as form factors or disparate models to describe the observed phenomena. E.g., the NCD and PCD EEPTs have revealed that these Coulombic charge distributions are the EIDIP effects couplings distributions. The effective couplings EEPTs further revealed that Coulomb electrostatic and magnetic couplings are the conformal (settle-to-constant) portion of the long-range residual-strong and strong couplings induced by the subatomic irrotational ($P_d r^2$) and rotational (P_r) EIDIP effects.

Although the conventional electromagnetic models can describe the long-range electrostatic and magnetic behaviors with constant couplings, they rely on form factors and disparate models: effective strong and residual-strong force couplings to describe the subatomic range NSTEEs. These form factors and disparate models are OEIAs.

¹⁶⁴ In the particle scattering experiments, the targets are stationary and heavier than the projectiles; therefore, the targets are relatively "immobile" upon impact; furthermore, in the PSAA EEPT, the sun (target object) is relatively immobile compared with the Pioneer 10/11 spacecraft (reference object).

C. EIDIP effects can describe and unify a wide range of physical phenomena without form factors

EIDIP effects are orderly and object-symmetric at long distances but turbulent and object-asymmetric at short distances (aka the NSTEE) because of the MWEP's quantized singularity at 2_{DSU} . The NSTEEs can not only be object-asymmetric but also change signs; whereas the conformal EIDIP effects are not affected by the singularities, they are object-symmetric and orderly such that they can be approximated by radius power functions.¹⁶⁵ Therefore, the conformal EIDIP effects are likely to be described by classical models whereas the NSTEEs are likely to be described by separate or composite models with the aid of form factors. E.g., the NSTEE region ERC and ESC become the conformal region EMC and EEC couplings; the NSTEE region SF, NNP, and IACF are described by separate or composite conventional models.

The 10+ EEPTs have shown that EIDIP effects can unify a wide range of physical phenomena and describe them without resorting to non-relativistic or relativistic form factors. E.g.,

- (1) Asymptotic and conformal behaviors of strong interaction without particle form factors;
- (2) Subatomic neutron and proton charge distributions, which are EIDIP effects couplings distributions, without charge density form factors;
- (3) The upper bound of the internucleon nuclear binding energy for almost all known nuclei without particle form factors;
- (4) Distance-dependent repulsive-attractive behaviors of the subatomic nuclear force and interatomic covalent force without particle form factors;
- (5) The relationship between these effective couplings: residual-strong, strong, electrostatic, and magnetic without particle and charge density form factors;
- (6) Interatomic Bohr radius;
- (7) The large deviation between the gravitational constant measurements;
- (8) Both the steep ascending and the slow descending data of the Pioneer 10/11 spacecraft anomalies;
- (9) Astronomical MW rotation curve anomalies without dark matter form factors.

D. All energy entities possess MWEP regardless of their size

The 10+ EEPTs have shown that EIDIP effects can describe the interactions of these elementary and composite particles: quark, electron, nucleon, and atom without involving these massless force-carrying bosons: photon, gluon, and hypothetical graviton and astronomic

¹⁶⁵ E.g., the long-range EIDIP effect is an inverse distance function ($P_E^\infty \propto r^{-1}$), the long-range angular EIDIP effect is a constant function ($P_r^\infty = r P_E^\infty \propto r^0$), and the long-range EIDIP-gradient effect magnitude is proportional to the inverse distance square ($P_d^\infty = d(P_E^\infty)/dr \propto r^{-2}$) of which the coupling is a constant function ($r^2 P_d^\infty \propto r^0$).

bosons. E.g., these EEPTs have shown that

- (1) The inter-quark angular EIDIP P_r can describe the strong interaction without *gluon*;
- (2) The inter-nucleon EIDIP-gradient P_d can describe the residual-strong force without *gluon*;
- (3) The subatomic turbulent EIDIP effects couplings can describe the ERC and ESC whereas the conformal EIDIP effects couplings can describe the EMC and EEC; i.e., the EIDIP effects can describe these interactions without *gluon* or *photon*;
- (4) The Dc0-domain MWEP coupling $2R_0$ plus the conformal range IACF coupling G_{SPC}^∞ can fit the value of the Newtonian gravitational constant closely; the residual IACF coupling contribution can explain the wide deviation between the Newtonian gravitational constant measurements; i.e., the EIDIP framework can describe gravitational interaction without the hypothetical *Graviton*;
- (5) The astronomical EIDIP effects can describe the gravitational anomalies and galaxy structures without the aid of the dark matter form factors and hypothetical astronomical range bosons.

In short, these 10+ EEPTs have revealed that these objects: photon, quark, nucleon, electron, atoms, molecules, regular matter, and even astronomical objects possess the MWEP. Photons' particle-wave duality and antibunching behaviors also affirm that photons possess the MWEP.¹⁶⁶ I.e., all energy entities (matter, particles, photons, etc.) possess the MWEP regardless of their size (AEMWEP hypothesis).

E. Symmetrical cE- and xE- domains EIDIP effects and isomorphic magnitude formula between the same type of EIDIP effects in various E-domains

On top of the AEMWEP hypothesis, the EIDIP framework further hypothesizes that, because the cE- and xE- MWEPs are the same in terms of the DSU and IDTC effects, the interaction effects of which should be the same. I.e., although the EIDIP effects are object-asymmetrical, those cE- and xE- domains EIDIP effects should have their xE- and cE- domains counterparts, hereafter referred to as the symmetrical cE- and xE- domains EIDIP effects (SCXEE) hypothesis. The 10+ EEPTs have provided some affirmations to the SCXEE hypothesis (TABLE V, TABLE VIII); e.g., the cE-domain NSTEE region P_r^\pm effect underlying the strong force (SF) also exists in xE-domain such that it produces the PSAA anomaly.

Furthermore, because the MWEPs' interactions are objective, the results of which, the EIDIP effects, should have the same DSU based magnitude for the same type of EIDIP effect regardless their E-domains (different orders

or contrastive-expansive). I.e., the magnitude formulas of the same type of EIDIP effect should be isomorphic regardless of their E-domains such that EIDIP effects should have their generic DSU based magnitude formulas, hereafter referred to as the isomorphic EIDIP effects magnitude formula (ISOMF) hypothesis. However, because the measuring these interaction effects also involved the apparatuses which can only measure the zero-order effects of the high-order interactions such that the apparatus factor could muddy the observations of the ISOMF.

E.g., the magnitude formula of these gradient-EEPTs: IACF, NGCD, and NNP are isomorphic with case-specific effective masses M_{kg}^{eff} (M_{kg}^{NGCD} , M_{kg}^{IACF} , M_{kg}^{NNP}),¹⁷⁸

$$[(P_d)_\ell \times M_{kg}^{eff} \times (2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3)]_N^{PGA}. \quad (80)$$

Note that verifying these case-specific effective masses can affirm the ISOMF hypothesis and solidify the EIDIP-gradient effect's generic magnitude formula.

The 10+ EEPTs have provided some, but not enough, information to construct the generic magnitude formulas for other EIDIP effects. E.g., the angular-EEPTs: PSAA and SF have partial isomorphic magnitude formulas. Assuming the PSAA data are more accurate than the SF data,¹⁶⁷ there could be a "missing" DSU term $1_{Dc2.5}$ in the SF magnitude formula ($2_{Dc2.5}^2$) compared with the PSAA formula ($2_{Dc2}^2 \times 1_{Dc2}$) (TABLE V). I.e., the PSAA and SF EEPTs could have an isomorphic magnitude formula,

$$[P_r \times M_{kg}^{eff} H_{kg}^0 \times 2_{DSU}^2 \times 1_{DSU}]_N^{APA}, \quad (81)$$

with case-specific effective masses M_{kg}^{eff} : $M_{kg}^{PSAA} = M_\odot$ and $M_{kg}^{SF} \cong [2/1_{Dc2.5}]_{kg}$, and \overline{DSU} as the complementary DSU . However, the $M_{kg}^{SF} \cong [6.1 \times 10^{15}]_{kg}$ is way too heavy as elementary particle mass.

Another possible outcome is that the $1_{Dc2.5}$ is missing because of the OEIA in the measuring apparatus and data construction; e.g., the data constructed from Coulomb scattering's IDS-OCF could differ from those based on the G_{APA}^∞ constant-OCF, a type of OEIA (section X.D.10).

X. EIDIP FRAMEWORK'S SCIENTIFIC METHOD, STATISTICAL CONFIDENCE, AND FUTURE DEVELOPMENT PROPOSALS

A. EIDIP framework possesses major scientific method precepts

Theoretical frameworks can be judged through these major scientific method precepts: *verifiability*, *predictability*, *falsifiability*, and *fairness* [55];¹⁶⁸ it can also

Doppler residuals should be more accurate than the SF data constructed with more variables and higher relative uncertainty.

¹⁶⁸ *Verifiability* means that an experiment must be replicable by another researcher. *Predictability* in a scientific theory implies that the

¹⁶⁶ The expulsive NSTEE can keep photons from bunching.

¹⁶⁷ The PSAA data were constructed from the Doppler residuals, and the conformal SF strength was constructed from complicated subatomic scattering experiments; hence, the PSAA data constructed from the

be judged by their feasibilities: *accuracy*, *consistency*, *scope*, *simplicity*, *progressiveness*, *utility*, and *expediency* [27].¹⁶⁹ The EIDIP framework possesses these precepts and is also simpler and more elegant than conventional disparate models:

- (1) The 10+ EEPTs have shown that the EIDIP framework can describe a wide range of physical phenomena currently described by disparate models beyond the Newtonian limit (*fairness*, *consistency*, *scope*, *utility*, *progressiveness*, and *expediency*), reduce them to more basic EIDIP effects, and reveal the connection between them; (*simplicity*, and *elegant*);
- (2) The EIDIP effects are fundamentally falsifiable because they have the multi-singularities signatures inherited from the quantized-singularity of the underlying MWEPs (*predictability*, and *falsifiability*);
- (3) The 10+ EEPTs can be reproduced by existing empirical data (*consistency*), and the plain EIDIP effects equations and MATLAB programs provided in this paper; (*verifiability*, *simplicity*, and *elegant*)
- (4) Plain EIDIP effects equations; the MWEP to the EIDIP mathematical derivation reveals a *parent-child* relationship between gravity and other fundamental-or-not or anomalous forces (*expediency*, *simplicity*, *verifiability*, and *simplicity*), the main reason why conventional peer-to-peer approaches have troubles to unify them; (*predictability*)
- (5) The EIDIP framework has a long list of falsifiable hypotheses (TABLE XI), and salient predictions and implications (section X.C); (*predictability*, *falsifiability*, *fairness*, *scope*, *utility*, *expediency*, and *simplicity*)
- (6) The non-perturbative EIDIP framework can gain insights from the 10+ three-variable EEPTs that perturbative or high variable count models cannot (*progressiveness*). The gained insights have provided coherent first-order rationales for additional non-classical physical phenomena beyond the Newtonian limit (section X.D). (*predictability*, *falsifiability*, *fairness*, *progressiveness*, *scope*, *utility*, *expediency*, and *simplicity*).

theory should enable us to make predictions about future events. *Falsifiability* refers to whether a hypothesis can be disproved. *Fairness* implies that all data must be considered when evaluating a hypothesis [55].

¹⁶⁹ *Accuracy*: (quantitative) accuracy of explanatory ability and prediction. *Simplicity*: “the simplest answer is the one most likely to be correct” of the Occam's Razor, the one with the fewest assumptions, rationalizations, and particularly special cases, or the most elegant idea. *Consistency*: be consistent with relevant concepts that have already been accepted; note that in this paper the *consistency* mean can consistently describe the relevant physical *behaviors* that have already been described by the accepted models. *Scope*: a broad explanatory power that inspires

B. Nulling EIDIP's existence has 5+ sigma statistical significance level

Because of unknown future discoveries, all known physical phenomena cannot be treated as a complete sampling space to prove a hypothesis or theory. E.g., although the existence of the EIDIP effects functions is objective,¹⁷⁰ the physical phenomena described by them can be coincidental; hence, the 10+ EEPTs cannot *prove* the underlying EIDIP's existence. However, the evidence revealed in the 10+ EEPTs can yield a qualitative confirmation. E.g., the logical probability of the EIDIP's existence can be calculated by a null hypothesis testing node (NHTN) method.

The purpose of null hypothesis testing is to give a quantitative estimate to accept or reject the null hypothesis that the EIDIP underlying the EEPT does not exist (i.e., the good fit of the EEPT is just coincidental).¹⁷¹ The null hypothesis testing method used in this paper comprises these components:

- (1) Because the *three*-variable EEPTs can yield insights into areas those high variable count models cannot, the 10+ EEPTs produced 60+ fitting elements that are uncanny enough to be the NHTNs. Statistically, the probability of a *single shaping-parameter nonlinear* EIDIP effect function can by chance describe an unrelated *nonlinear* physical phenomenon is very low; i.e., statistically, the EIDIP effects underlying these EEPTs are more likely to exist than not. Even with that, each NHTN is artificially assigned with a conservative 50% probability for the null hypothesis;
- (2) Those physical phenomena involved in the 10+ EEPTs are not *selective* samples statistically because they cover subatomic-to-interstellar anomalous-or-not physical phenomena; i.e., they are likely representative samples such that the computation of the nulling EIDIP significance level likely avoids the selective-sampling pitfalls;
- (3) On the other hand, although the physical phenomena are described by mostly unrelated conventional models or as anomalies, the EEPTs have revealed the EIDIP connection between them; i.e., these physical phenomena are not compound (unrelated) samples such that the computation of the nulling EIDIP significance level avoids the compound-statistic pitfalls;
- (4) With # number of NHTNs, the significant

confidence through its ability to find order in formerly disparate types of observations. *Progressiveness*: the capability to disclose new phenomena or previously unnoted relationships among those already known. *Utility*: pragmatic and useful to a wide range of physics field. *Expediency*: the capability to provide solutions to open issues and irreconcilable conflicts between disparate conventional models.

¹⁷⁰ Because the math operators and MATLAB program, from which the EIDIP effects functions are generated, are objective.

¹⁷¹ In statistics, we generally don't make claims that require us to believe a very unusual event happened. If the evidence we have collected shows the null hypothesis is unlikely, we reject our null hypothesis [43].

probability that *all* the NHTNs are true is $0.5^\#$ or the confidence probability of at least one NHTN nulling the null hypothesis is $1 - 0.5^\#$; i.e., the # number of NHTNs all affirming that the EIDIP effect does *not* exist has a $0.5^\#$ significant probability or at least one NHTN affirming that the EIDIP effect *does* exist has a $1 - 0.5^\#$ confidence probability;¹⁷²

- (5) Because EIDIP effects have deterministic relationships with the EIDIP, one confirmed EIDIP effect also confirms the EIDIP and consecutively, all other EIDIP effects derived from it. Hence, the $1 - 0.5^\#$ confidence probability of at least one NHTN affirming that the EIDIP effect (does exist) can express the confidence probability of the EIDIP (does exist) because the EIDIP effect's existence is a Boolean-valued function (either exists or not).

The 60+ NHTNs are partitioned into primary and secondary lists based on their relationship, direct or indirect, with the EIDIP effects; the significant probability of the null hypothesis is conservatively calculated with the primary NHTNs alone. With the 35+ primary NHTNs listed in the following section, nulling the EIDIP's existence has a 0.5^{35+} significant probability or 5+ sigma statistical significance level, or that at least one primary NHTN affirming the EIDIP's existence has a $1 - 0.5^{35+}$ confidence probability or 5+ sigma confidence level.¹⁷²

The EIDIP framework is built on the EIDIP. The fact that nulling the EIDIP has a 5+ sigma statistical significance level, and the EIDIP effects can describe a wide range of physical phenomena as shown in the 10+ EEPTs, affirm the EIDIP framework has high statistical confidence.

1 Primary null hypothesis testing nodes

The 10+ EEPTs produced these 40 primary NHTNs, refer to the EEPTs' distance and magnitude formula summary table (TABLE V),

- (1) The 15 EEPTs themselves are primary NHTDs because those single shaping-parameter nonlinear EIDIP effects can phenomenological fit to those complex empirical figures or datasets are uncanny;¹⁷³
- (2) The 10 NSTEE region EEPTs with integer DSU distance scalers are primary NHTDs because they can scale the single shaping-parameter NSTEE curves to fit those complex physical phenomena;¹⁷⁴
- (3) The 15 EEPTs inter-domain coupling T_c are

¹⁷² Presume the 35+ NHTNs constitute a fair sample pool.

¹⁷³ Also shown in TABLE V with #158 footnote. Note that those multiple sub-cases with the same EIDIP effects are counted as one primary NHTD.

¹⁷⁴ Also shown in TABLE V with #159 footnote. Note that even though some EEPTs have integer DSU distance scalers, they are excluded from the primary NHTD pool because these EEPTs are in the linear or slow changing EIDIP effects regions where the distance scalers are not sensitive.

primary NHTDs because that they can fit these subatomic to astronomic range EEPTs with only two values, $(32\pi)^{1/4}$ and 32π .¹⁷⁵

Note that the maximum number of primary NHTNs extracted from each EEPT is three (3); i.e., the maximum significance probability contribution from each EEPT is 0.125 regardless of the size of its data.¹⁷⁶

2 Secondary null hypothesis testing nodes

The EEPTs also produced 20+ secondary NHTNs; some of them are:

- (1) The ESC, NCD, EEC, and EMC EEPTs reveal the intimate relationship between the residual-strong, strong, electrostatic, and magnetic couplings;
- (2) The EEC EEPT reveals the relationship between the irrotational $P_d^\infty r^2$ and $k_e e^2$; whereas the EMC EEPT reveals the relationship between the rotational P_r^∞ , and the fine structure α and reduced Planck \hbar constants;
- (3) The two IACF EEPTs affirm matter does possess the quantized singularity MWEP; hence, the IACF measurement method has the potential to be a simpler indirect way to measure the gravitational constant.
- (4) The SF, NNP, NCD, and PCD EEPTs operate in the same Dc2.5-domain;
- (5) The AEAAN effects, not gravity, can explain different shapes of the CMWRC, SMWRC, and LMWRC (section VIII.G.3);
- (6) Different EIDIP effect and gravity OCFs ratios produce different gradients in the second segment of the QG-MWRCs which can be used to fit additional galaxies' rotation curves (FIG. 58);
- (7) The EIDIP effects induced gravitational force ripples (GFR) can induce galactic rings' formations, e.g., turnover rings; in such cases, the galactic rings' radii can be used to estimate the faster-than-light speed of the underlying high-order gravity effects (section VIII.F.4).
- (8) The NBE EEPT magnitude formula revealed the relationship between the internucleon EIDIP and the Higgs-boson-like mass H_{Mc}^0 that is comparable to the ATLAS and CMS measurements; these Higgs-boson-like masses, H_{kg}^0 and H_{Mc}^0 , not only appear throughout the 10+ EEPTs' magnitude formulas but also reveal the connections between the EEPTs;¹⁷⁷

¹⁷⁵ Also shown in TABLE V with #161 footnote. Note that apart from the Bohr radius and NBE EEPTs, the rest of EEPTs share the same T_c values of $(32\pi)^{1/4}$.

¹⁷⁶ E.g., the NBE, SMWRC, and LMWRC EEPTs are based on fairly large empirical data sets (2436 nuclei and 16146 stars), but they are still assigned with the same 50% null probability.

¹⁷⁷ E.g., although the original NNP EEPT is in MeV unit, and the H_{Mc}^0 to H_{kg}^0 conversion helps to reveal that the converted SI base unit NNP

- (9) The NBE EEPT distance formula revealed the lower bound inter-elementary-particle distance $R_u = 1/c^2$ that is one of the main parameters of the EPNCR-SEFs' constructions; e.g., as the slope of the baseline NCR $24R_u$ and the NCR sub-shell thickness $3R_u$;
- (10) The maximum neutron-neutron attraction potential radius R_{NNP}^{max} deduced from the NNP EEPT and the maximum strong interaction radius R_{SF}^{max} deduced from the SF EEPT are major components of the NCR-SEFs of these light nuclei: proton (muonic and electronic), neutron, Deuteron, and Helium-4.

The EEPTs also produced 15 more secondary NHTNs (shown with the #160 footnote in the magnitude formulas column of TABLE V) which can be cataloged as:

- (1) The magnitude formulas of these gradient-EEPTs: NP, NGCD, EEC, EMC, and IACF are isomorphic¹⁷⁸ and have shared the $2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3$ term in the SI base unit;
- (2) The EEC and EMC have shared the same $4H_{kg}^0 / (32\pi)^{2.5}$ or $(2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3) 2_{Dc2.5}$ magnitude scaler term;
- (3) The EEC and EMC magnitude formulas contain the $2_{Dc2.5}$ whereas the SF magnitude formula contains the complementary $2_{Dx2.5}$; these terms reveal their Dc2.5 origin;
- (4) The NNP and NBE magnitude formulas in the eV base unit have shared the $(H_{Mc}^0 c^2) \times R_0^2$ term;
- (5) The subatomic quadratic NCD and astronomic SG-MWRC EEPTs have shared the same rP_r' effect;
- (6) The subatomic quadratic PCD and astronomic QG-MWRC EEPTs have shared the same P_E^2/r effect;
- (7) The astronomic PSAA and PG-MWRC EEPTs have shared the P_r effect and 2_{Dc2}^2 ;
- (8) The subatomic SF and astronomic PSAA EEPTs have shared complementary E-domains' DSU square terms; the subatomic NBE EEPT and astronomic PSAA EEPT also operate in the complementary Dc2 and Dx2 E-domains; these operating E-domains affirm the MEP hypothesis.

3 NHTN's 50% probability assignment is conservative

Statistically, I conjecture that the probability of a single shaping-parameter *nonlinear* EIDIP or derived function can describe a *nonlinear* physical phenomenon by chance is close to zero. The artificial 50% probability of the null hypothesis is conservative in the sense that it is an exaggeratedly higher probability than the reality to get a conservative significance probability calculation. Note that the EIDIP effects underlying the 10+ EEPTs are single

shaping-parameter nonlinear functions of distance whereas those NSTEE induced physical phenomena either cannot be or are described by much more complex functions in conventional models.¹⁷⁹

Even with the assumption that the underlying physical phenomenon has a single shaping-parameter *nonlinear* function, statistically, the probability of a single shaping-parameter *nonlinear* EIDIP function can fit a single shaping-parameter *nonlinear* physical phenomenon and not be *causative* is very low. Furthermore, although the fitting probability increases with the physical phenomena variable count (a reversed fitting),¹⁸⁰ the probability of a single shaping-parameter *nonlinear* function can fit a multi-variable physical phenomenon and not be *causative* is still much lower than the conservative 50% probability.

C. EIDIP framework's falsifiable predictions and implications

The 10+ EEPTs have shown that EIDIP effects can describe and unify a wide range of physical phenomena without form factors. Because the EIDIP effects functions are single shaping-parameter nonlinear functions of distance, they have semi-rigid shapes and are nonperturbative; which enable the EIDIP framework to gain insights from the 10+ EEPT that perturbative or high variable counts methods cannot. In this section, we discuss some of the EIDIP framework predictions and explanatory hypotheses; for a full list of EIDIP framework hypotheses refer to TABLE XI.

1 EIDIP multi-singularities signature implications

The EIDIP effects induced phenomena have falsifiable multi-singularity signatures inherited from the quantized singularity of the underlying MWEP. E.g., the EIDIP framework predicts that the NNP and IACF curves have additional singularities in the repulsive regions. Furthermore, the EIDIP effects near the singularities (aka NSTEEs) are so turbulent that they cannot be covered by conformal region models and require additional models to describe them; i.e., to cover the full range of EIDIP effects would require the disparate conventional models, a type of OEIA.

2 NSTEEs lead to disparate conventional models

The 10+ EEPTs have revealed that the NSTEE region and conformal region EIDIP effects are described by separated conventional models; i.e., they have revealed the EIDIP effects connections among the physical phenomena described by disparate conventional models (TABLE VI).

Although most of the orderly conformal EIDIP effects

magnitude formula shares the same scaler $2H_{kg}^0 H_0^3$ term as the NGCD, EEC, and IACF EEPTs.

¹⁷⁸ With these effective masses: $M_{kg}^{NNP} \cong [1]_{eV/c^2}$, $M_{kg}^{IACF} \cong [10^{-6}]_{kg}$, and $M_{kg}^{NGCD} = [1]_{kg}$.

¹⁷⁹ The probability is extremely low that the observer or nature has fine-tuned the complex physical phenomenon to behave like the single-parameter nonlinear EIDIP effect function.

¹⁸⁰ E.g., observed galaxy rotation curves have various shapes which indicate there are multiple variables underlying these shapes.

have been well described by classical physics models, some relatively low-intensity astronomical EIDIP effects induced physical phenomena are beyond the Newtonian limit and remain to be anomalies; e.g., PSAA and MWRC. Furthermore, the current physical models have trouble to link the turbulent EIDIP effects near the singularities with the stable conformal-region EIDIP effects induced physical phenomena. E.g., describing the strong force's asymptotic and confinement behaviors currently require separate models and consolidating them remains problematic. The ESC, ERC, EMC and EEC EEPTs have also revealed the EIDIP effects connections between these couplings that are currently described by separate models.

Another example, conventional residual-strong force models comprise multiple forces. Although they can describe part of the residual-strong force behaviors, they do not have the saturation segment in the repulsive region described in the following section.

The 10+ EEPTs have affirmed the SCXEE hypothesis that those cE-domain EIDIP effects should have their xE-domain counterparts (TABLE VIII). The ESC, ERC, EMC and EEC EEPTs have also revealed that these effective couplings are connected by the NSTEE and conformal regions EIDIP effects. With that, the SCXEE hypothesis implicates that those cE-domain effective couplings should have their astronomical xE-domain NSTEE and conformal counterparts such that they likely produced the observed gravitoelectromagnetism (section X.D.16). E.g., the gravitoelectromagnetism underlying the astrophysical jets [28] is produced by the xE-domain EIDIP effects of which the cE-domain counterparts also produce the hadron jets (section X.D.4).

TABLE VI. Conformal and NSTEE region cE- ($D_{c\#}$) and xE- ($D_{x\#}$) domains EIDIP effects induced physical phenomena.¹⁸¹

	Short-range NSTEE	Long-range conformal
D_{c0}	Interatomic covalent force (IACF) (P_d^\pm), Bohr radius (P_r^\pm); <i>Photon antibunching</i> ;	Gravity (\hat{G}_{MGA}) Gravitational constant ($[2R_0]_{m^3/s^2}$), Newtonian gravitational constant deviation (NGCD) ($r^2 P_d^\infty$);
D_{c2}	Reference nuclear binding energy BE_{ref} (P_E^\pm);	
$D_{c2.5}$	Effective strong coupling (ESC) (P_r^\pm),	Effective magnetic coupling (EMC) (P_r^∞),
$D_{c\#}$	Effective residual-strong coupling (ERC) ($r^2 P_d^\pm$), Strong force (SF) (P_r^\pm), Residual-strong force, neutron-neutron potential (NNP) (P_d^\pm), Neutron charge distribution (NCD) (rP_r' , $P_E P_d$),	Effective electrostatic coupling (EEC) ($r^2 P_d^\infty$);

¹⁸¹ Italic texts denote the EIDIP framework's predictions or implications discussed in section X.D later.

Proton charge distribution (PCD) (P_E^2/r);
Relativistic time dilation and direction,
Hadron jets,
Elementary particle generations;

D_{x0}	<i>Near-Earth flyby anomalies</i> (P_r^\pm , P_d^\pm), <i>Gravitational time dilation measurements</i> (P_r^\pm , P_d^\pm);	
D_{x2}	Pioneer 10/11 spacecraft's sunward acceleration anomaly (P_r^\pm);	<i>Extended Pioneer 10/11 spacecraft's sunward acceleration anomaly</i> (P_r^∞);
D_{x5}	Milky Way and other galaxies' rotation curves anomalies (P_E^2/r , rP_r' , etc.); <i>Galactic rings</i> , <i>Linear frame-dragging</i> (P_d^\pm), <i>Rotational frame-dragging</i> (P_r^\pm), <i>Gravity wave</i> , <i>Astrophysical jets</i> , <i>Gravitostrong coupling</i> (P_r^\pm), <i>Gravitoresidualstrong coupling</i> ($r^2 P_d^\pm$);	<i>Galaxy structure</i> , <i>Linear frame-dragging</i> (P_d^∞), <i>Rotational frame-dragging</i> (P_r^∞), <i>Gravitational lensing</i> , <i>Gravitomagnetic coupling</i> (P_r^∞), <i>Gravitoelectric coupling</i> ($r^2 P_d^\infty$);

3 Repulsive residual-strong and covalent forces do not rise toward infinity

In contrast to the NNP and IACF curves of conventional models that the repulsive residual-strong and covalent forces rise toward infinity at the origin, the EIDIP framework predicts that these forces have additional singularities within the repulsive regions instead of at the origin because the underlying EIDIP effects have the multi-singularities signatures inherited from their MWEP's quantized singularity. E.g., the PSAA, SF, NNP, and IACF EEPTs have revealed that the PSAA and SF are the angular EIDIP induced phenomena whereas the NNP and IACF are the EIDIP-gradient effects induced phenomena. Because the angular EIDIP's asymptotic segment (green curve left of red dashed line, FIG. 69) translates to the EIDIP-gradient effect's saturated segment (blue line left of red dashed line), the well-known SF's asymptotic behavior and the similar segment shown in the Pioneer 11 spacecraft's data affirm that the NNP and IACF curves also have the saturated segments.

FIG. 69. (Color online) Angular EIDIP asymptotic segment (green curve left of red dashed line) and EIDIP-gradient saturated segment (blue line left of red dashed line) relationship figure.

4 Multiple E-domain pairs hypothesis implications

The EIDIP framework posits that the cE- and xE-domain MWEPs are formed in pairs, aka the multiple E-domain pairs (MEP) hypothesis; and that the gravitational interaction around the cE- and xE-fermion radii are turbulent because of the EIDIP effects. The presented EEPTs affirms these claims as summarized in TABLE VII and FIG. 68. E.g., the internucleon Dc2-domain NBE EEPT can be paired with the Dx2-domain PSAA EEPT. Moreover, the Dc0-domain IACF EEPTs can be paired with the Dx0-domain EIDIP effects induced near-Earth-flyby (NEFB) anomalies.¹⁸² Note that all these EEPT are NSTEEs cases.

However, the Dx5-domain PG-MWRC and the Dc2.5-domain EEPTs (SF and NNP) have no complementary E-domain EEPTs yet; there are several possible outcomes implicated by the MEP hypothesis:

- (1) There are yet-to-be-identified Dc5-domain elementary particles inside regular matters or condensed plasmas in galaxy center black holes;¹⁸³
- (2) There are Dx2.5-domain astronomical gravitational anomalies yet-to-be-identified,¹⁸⁴ or the Dc2.5-domain phenomena operate in the harmonic of the Dc2-domain;¹⁸⁵
- (3) Otherwise, the SF and NNP could be Dc5-domain

¹⁸² The EIDIP framework predicts that the near-Earth-flyby anomalies are produced by the Dx0-MWEP interaction effects between the flyby objects, and Moon (mostly) and Earth.

¹⁸³ This outcome implies that black holes could comprise the Dc5-domain particle plasma that has a higher density than the quark plasma because the Dc5-domain DSU is five orders of magnitude shorter than the Dc2.5-domain DSU ($[1]_{Dc5}/[1]_{Dc2.5} = (32\pi)^{-2.5} \approx 10^{-5}$). Note that the higher the order of the particle's cE-domain, the higher the mass defect (aka the post-MWEP transformation residual tension) and the lighter the innate mass of the particles.

¹⁸⁴ This outcome implies that the Pioneer spacecraft sunward acceleration data collected beyond the 200 AU range would include the Dx2.5-domain EIDIP effects.

phenomena rather than Dc2.5-domain phenomena because of the OEIA in the constructed interquark radius;¹⁸⁶ in this case, the quarks are the yet-to-be-identified Dc5-domain elementary particles.¹⁸⁷

TABLE VII. cE- and xE-MWEP pairs table (italic texts denote the possible MEP hypothesis implications yet to be verified).

E-domain	Physical phenomena
D _{c0}	Interatomic covalent force and Bohr radius;
D _{x0}	<i>Near-Earth-flyby anomalies;</i>
D _{c2}	Internucleon nuclear binding energy; <i>Interquark strong and residual-strong interactions (D_{c2.5} is a harmonic of the D_{c2};</i>
D _{x2}	Pioneer sunward acceleration anomaly;
D _{c2.5}	Interquark strong and residual-strong interactions;
D _{x2.5}	<i>Astronomical gravitational anomalies;</i>
D _{c5}	<i>Yet-to-be-identified elementary particles; or SF and NNP are Dc5-domain phenomena, and quarks are Dc5-domain elementary particles;</i>
D _{x5}	Milky Way and galaxy rotation curve anomalies;

5 High-order gravities and EIDIP effects are faster than light

Newtonian gravity model posits that the speed of gravity is infinite whereas the GR posits that gravity travels at the speed of light. In the EIDIP framework, gravitational potential comprises multiple orders of cE-domains MWEPs, Dc0-domain mostly (99.43%). The zero-order MWEPs and EIDIP effects travel at the speed of light; whereas the high-order MWEPs and EIDIP effects travel faster than light at $[(32\pi)^{\#}c]_{m/s}$ with # denoting the E-domain order.

The 10+ EEPTs have revealed that regular matter does possess multiple-orders E-domain MWEPs, up to fifth-order based on the CMWRC, SMWRC and LMWRC EEPTs. With that, the high-order EIDIP effects, like those anomalous forces underlying the astronomical gravitational anomalies, can travel faster than light. E.g., the Dx5-domain EIDIP effects underlying the MWRC anomaly travel at $[2]_{Dx5} \approx [10^{10}c]_{m/s}$ which compares to the observed faster-than-light gravity speed $> [2 \times 10^{10}c]_{m/s}$ based purely on observed gravity-OCF from the

¹⁸⁵ Because of $(32\pi)^{0.5} = 10.0265 \approx 10$, it is possible that the Dc2.5-domain is a harmonic of Dc2-domain; on the other hand, the $T_c = (32\pi)^{1/4}$ Dc2.5-domain R_{NWP}^{max} and R_{SF}^{max} based light nuclei EPNCRSEFs (TABLE IV) produced NCRs matched their measurements.

¹⁸⁶ These fractional order Dc2.5 and Dx2.5 E-domains are also a bit at odds with the spherical MWEP transformation hypothesis because a $2 \times (4\pi \times 2^2) = (32\pi)$ DSU step between the consecutive order of E-domains is more intuitive.

¹⁸⁷ Refer to section X.D.10. This outcome implies that the NCRs of known nuclei also need to be updated.

solar system and binary stars [6]. Note that, because the gravity speed calculation of [6] did not account for the EIDIP effects, the OEIA induced the higher gravity speed calculation.

Although current measuring apparatus may not be able to detect the faster-than-light high order gravity (EIDIP) effects directly, it is possible that they can detect the zero-order interaction effects between the high-order gravity (EIDIP) effects and zero-order MWEPS; e.g., the astronomical gravitational lensing discussed later in section X.D.9.

Some astronomic phenomena can be used to measure the speed of underlying high-order gravity and EIDIP effects; of which the results can confirm they are faster than light. E.g., The bending or overshoot radii where galaxies' rotation curves change directions or reach a local maximum can be used to deduce the xE-domain of underlying EIDIP effects; e.g., the MWRC EEPTs' distance scaler $[4]_{Dx5}$ reveals the underlying EIDIP effects operate in the Dx5-harmonic. Galactic rings' radii can also be used to extract the xE-domain and speed of underlying EIDIP effects (refer to section VIII.G.4).

D. Rationales for future EIDIP framework developments and applications

A hypothesis that only accounts for the observations that inspired it has little value; progressive hypotheses are valued because of their exciting implications for a variety of new research directions [27]. Because the EIDIP effects functions are single shaping-parameter nonlinear functions of distance, they are nonperturbative and have rigid shapes; which enable the EIDIP framework to gain insights from the 10+ EEPT that perturbative and high variable counts methods cannot. E.g., The 10+ EEPTs have shown that EIDIP effects can describe and unify a wide range of physical phenomena without form factors, all energy entities (matter and photon) possess the MWEPE regardless of their size (aka AEMWEPE hypothesis). Taken together, these results suggest that some well-accepted physical models and constructed data could have sizeable omitting EIDIP effects induced artifacts (aka OEIA hypothesis).

Although it is counterintuitive to hypothesize that some well-accepted physical models and constructed data could have sizeable OEIAs, the EIDIP framework's high statistical confidence does give some credence and support for the coherent *first-order* rationales for the beyond-the-Newtonian-limit physical phenomena and the OEIAs hypotheses listed in this section. These EIDIP based rationales are fertile grounds for future EIDIP framework developments.

¹⁸⁸The galaxies' center-bulge sizes can also vary because galaxies' IMOJ compositions and mass distributions affect their Gravity and EIDIP effects crossover radius.

¹⁸⁹Some of these stars with small inclination angles can be held in place by gravity and AEAAN effects; whereas the centrifugal force of the rotating galaxy can pull those larger inclination angles stars away from center rotation plane-wise which would result in longer rotation plane

1 MWEPE possesses wave-particle duality

The wave-particle duality phenomenon has been shown to occur with photons, electrons, atoms and even some molecules [29]. These 10+ EEPTs have revealed that these objects: photon, quark, nucleon, electron, atoms, molecules, regular matter, and even astronomical objects possess the MWEPE such that their E-fermion cores produce the particle-behaviors whereas their E-boson fields exhibit the wave-behaviors.

2 EIDIP effects contributed to galaxy formations

Astronomical EIDIP effects contributed to galaxies' center-bulge, outer-disk, and spiral arm formations.

Galaxies' center-bulge-and-outer-disk formations result from the dynamic between the omnidirectional gravity, directional EIDIP effects OCFs, and centrifugal forces of the rotating galaxies. The PSAA and MWRC EEPTs have revealed that the xE-domain EIDIP effects are already noticeable in the interplanetary range and become dominant in the galactic range compared with gravity.

Galaxies have center-bulge formations because the EIDIP effects are neglectable in these center regions and the omnidirectional gravity would not alter the native omnidirectional star distributions.¹⁸⁸

In galaxies' outer regions, the EIDIP effects become more noticeable and even dominant. Because the AEAAN effects are functions of the inclination angle (e.g., equation (39)), they could nudge those stars below a certain range of inclination angles to lower inclination angles (i.e., toward the rotation plane);¹⁸⁹ and the remaining stars would fly away with time because of the centrifugal forces. The result of such is the galaxy disk formation in the outer region.

Astronomical EIDIP effects also contributed to galaxies' spiral arm formations. Because of the shorter distances between nearby stars, the inter-star gravity can be stronger than the inter-star EIDIP effects even if they reside in the galactic disk region where the systematic EIDIP effects dominate the GC-centric gravity. Hence, the inter-star gravity could pull the nearby stars to form clusters. At the same time, the GC-centric conformal (settle-to-constant) EIDIP effects in the galactic disk region could pull these clusters *radially* to form galaxy arms.

Furthermore, the heavier the inner clusters are, the stronger EIDIP effects OCF they possess to attract the outer clusters to form galaxy arms. Because of the distance-invariant EIDIP effects OCF, the longer the galactic radii of stars, the lower their angular velocities.¹⁹⁰ With time, those galaxy arms would have spiral arms formations.

radii for these stars with time. Combing with nondecaying ortho-radial AEAAN effects, they would decrease these stars' inclination angles and strengthen the AEAAN effects. With time, they would induce the galaxies' outer disk formations.

¹⁹⁰E.g., because of the $G_{APA}^{\infty} \propto cnst$, the induced angular velocity is $w \propto \sqrt{G_{APA}^{\infty}/r} \propto \sqrt{1/r}$.

3 EIDIP effects produced galactic rings

About one-fifth of all spiral disk galaxies include a ring-shaped pattern in the light distribution, and an additional one third appear to have broken or partial rings made up of spiral arms (pseudorings). These rings are a special problem in galaxy morphology with a direct bearing on the internal dynamics and evolution of disk galaxies. Optical rotation curves of ringed galaxies yield some curious coincidences; e.g., in the weakly-barred spiral NGC 7531, the very bright inner ring lies virtually exactly at the turnover radius [26].

The astronomical MWRC EEPTs have revealed that EIDIP effects are part of galaxies' internal dynamics and can induce GFRs or even NGF regions (FIG. 66 and FIG. 67). The GFRs can contribute to galactic rings' formations because they can induce star density ripples. E.g., the steeper the GFR's gradient, the denser the stars congregated near the maximum rotational velocity radius (aka the turnover radius); i.e., the steeper ascending segment of GFRs are also likely to induce turnover rings near the turnover radii. The turnover radii of rotation curves or galactic rings radii can reveal the speed of the underlying gravity and EIDIP effects (sections VIII.F.4 and VIII.G.4).

The relatively weaker (or negative) portion of the GFRs can nudge stars out of these regions and produce lower star-density (or empty) bands, and the relatively stronger portion of the GFR can nudge stars to stay put in these regions and produce higher star-density bands. The results of such are ring structures. Furthermore, these mass distribution ripples from these rings can trigger additional GFRs further out which can add more secondary rings to the galaxies.

4 EIDIP effects induced astrophysical and hadron jets

An astrophysical jet is a *narrow cone* or cylinder/semi-cylinder of outflows of ionized matter emitted along the axis of rotation.¹⁹¹ The PSAA and MWRC EEPTs have revealed that stars, galaxies, and astronomic flybys possess MWEPs; the interactions between them can produce highly attractive-and-repulsive xE-domain EIDIP effects (e.g., rP'_r and rP'_d) in the NSTEE jet region (e.g., the magenta box region in FIG. 70). The highly attractive EIDIP effects can pull in flybys near GCs and increase both the radial and the angular momentums of the flybys. As they get closer to the GCs, the highly repulsive EIDIP effects can then expel the flybys transversely and form astrophysical jets.

A hadron jet is a *narrow cone* of hadrons and other particles produced in high energy particle scattering experiments [30]. Hadron jets are the cE-domain counterpart of the xE-domain astrophysical jets. The highly attractive-and-repulsive EIDIP effects in the cE-domain NSTEE jet region can pull in and then expel the flyby projectiles. Furthermore, because the turbulent EIDIP magnitude correlates with the momentum of the

projectiles, some of them could gain such high momentums that the EIDIP effects are strong enough to produce the observed behaviors of the particle-antiparticle pairs.

FIG. 70. (Color online) Turbulent EIDIP effects in the NSTEE region (magenta box region, positive values: repulsive regions, negative values: attractive regions) examples: rP'_r (blue) and rP'_d (green) figure; which could induce the accelerating expansion of the universe and, through transverse momentum transfer, astrophysical and hadron jets, and influence black holes' structures.

5 OEIA in current astronomical data

The PSAA and MWRC EEPTs have shown that the EIDIP effects are already noticeable in the interplanetary range and even dominant in the intergalactic range. Hence, it is safe to assume Kepler's laws derived data would have sizable OEIAs in the intergalactic range and beyond.

The MWRC EEPTs have shown that the EIDIP effects contributions have profound effects in determining the MW mass. Because the EIDIP effects are noticeable and even dominant in galactic ranges, it is safe to assume that, in galactic ranges, Newtonian gravity and Kepler's laws constructed data contain the OEIAs.

Note that OEIAs can spread over codependent galaxy data; e.g., among position, velocity, and mass. Furthermore, the OEIAs can spill into the downstream data; e.g., the RAVE-DR2 data is constructed based upon the sun's galactic position and velocity; if it contained OEIAs, the downstream RAVE-DR2 data would also contain OEIAs.

6 OEIA as dark matter

Extensive analysis has concluded that the strength of a gravitational lens is similar to those (anomalous forces) underlying the rotation curves of spiral galaxies and more than 90% strength (of the force that produced the gravitational lensing) is from dark matter [31].¹⁹² The

¹⁹¹ "Geometrically, these jets are narrow (small opening angle) conical or cylindrical/semi-cylindrical protrusions" [44].

¹⁹² "The strength of a gravitational lens depends on the total mass contained within it. Extensive analysis of gravitational lensing by large

conclusion concurs with the findings of the hybrid gravity and EIDIP effects OCFs MWRC phenomenological tests that the EIDIP effect contributions can eliminate the dark matter requirements of gravity-OCF only MWRC models.

Newtonian galaxies masses contain sizeable OEIA because they were constructed with the exaggerated gravity-OCF to compensate for the unaccounted sizeable EIDIP-OCF. In turn, the exaggerated gravity-OCF leads to the exaggerated galaxy mass that requires the hypothetical dark matter distribution form factors to fit the observed astronomical phenomena. Furthermore, the data constructed from the Doppler redshift, even with relativistic adjustments, could still contain some OEIAs because the photon and matter interaction can produce and be affected by the EIDIP effects.¹⁹³

7 OEIA as inflationary dark energy in accelerating expansion of the universe

To explain the observed accelerating expansion of the universe, conventional inflation models require hypothetical dark energy and dark matters. In the EIDIP framework, apart from the contribution of the isotropic vacuum energy (aka the E-space), the unaccounted supergalactic EIDIP effects also contribute to the dark energy required by conventional models, i.e., the dark energy is an OEIA.

Supergalactic expulsive EIDIP effects can produce the accelerating expansion of the universe. Although the universe is found to be isotropic in general, it can still comprise of multiple subgroups such that each has its systemic MWEP with its directions (UCMM hypothesis).¹⁹⁴ As the astronomical range distance-invariant angular EIDIP effects and the AEAAN effects from them can produce the galaxies' center-bulge-and-outer-disk formations, their super-galactic range counterparts can also produce the relatively flat structure of our universe, and some super-galactic expulsive EIDIP effects can also produce the observed accelerating expansion of the universe.

I.e., the observed accelerating expansion of the universe could be these subgroups in the early stage of separation such that they are still in the repulsive super-galactic NSTEE region (e.g., the repulsive (positive) region in FIG. 70 but in supergalactic scales). I.e., the hypothetical dark energy required to explain the accelerating expansion of the universe is an OEIA.

8 OEIA as large deviation in Newtonian gravitational constant measurements

The large deviation between the Newtonian gravitational constant (NGC) measurements is an OEIA. The IACF EEPT has revealed that the IACF coupling is conformal (distance-variant) at a distance but turbulent

masses leads to conclusions similar to those suggested by the rotation curves for spiral galaxies. More than 90% of the mass contributing to the strength of large gravitational lenses is dark" [31].

¹⁹³ Refer to the OEIA in relativistic adjusted data discussed in section X.D.17.

(can even change signs) in the NSTEE region. The NGCD EEPT has also revealed that the conformal IACF coupling contributed to most of the NGC deviations. Hence, the IACF coupling alone could have muddled the NGC measurements. Furthermore, the experiment locations, deep underground or high above the ground, would bring in additional environmental cE- and xE-domains EIDIP effects. Because the distance and environmental variant EIDIP effects are beyond the Newtonian limit (i.e., OEIAs), they muddled the Newtonian gravitational constant measurements and induced the large deviation between them.

9 OEIA as photon antibunching and gravitational lensing

That the strength of a gravitational lens is similar to those underlying the anomalous rotation curves of spiral galaxies affirms that the gravitational lensing and galaxy rotation curve anomalies have similar sources [31]. The MWRC EEPTs have revealed that astronomical Dx5-domain EIDIP effects have produced the MWRC anomalies.

The 10+ EEPTs have also revealed that all energy entities including photons and astronomical objects possess the MWEP regardless of their size (aka AEMWEP hypothesis). Hence, Dc0-domain photons can interact with other various orders of MWEPs and produce EIDIP effects; e.g., the attractive and *expulsive* NSTEE can keep photons from bunching together whereas the astronomical range attractive and *expulsive* EIDIP effects can produce the attractive and *expulsive* gravitational lensing, aka the attractive and *expulsive* gravitational lensing (AXGL) hypothesis. I.e., the spiral galaxy RC anomalies, gravitational lensing, and photon antibunching are all are OEIAs.

10 OEIA in Coulomb scattering constructed data

The NCD and PCD EEPTs have revealed that the subatomic *charge* distributions are produced by the turbulent EIDIP effects *coupling* distributions in the NSTEE region. Because the Rutherford scattering (aka Coulomb scattering) constructed data is based on Coulombic *constant* coupling model, some of it would contain the OEIA.

Although the conventional electromagnetic models can describe the long-range conformal (settle-to-constant) portion of the G_{PGC}^{∞} and G_{APC}^{∞} , they cannot describe the turbulent G_{PGC} and G_{APC} in the NSTEE region without additional models and form factors. Because the projectile-target interactions in the Rutherford scattering have both the rotational and the irrotational components, the EIDIP effects produced by which have both components.¹⁹⁵ The

¹⁹⁴ The UCMM hypothesis comes with a falsifiable implication that the universe should have multiple sub-systemic moving directions, and could have super-galactic rings or wave formations.

¹⁹⁵ E.g., the composite EIDIP effects rP'_i underlying the NCD EEPT.

conventional frameworks require disparate models and form factors,¹⁹⁶ both are different types of the OEIA, to describe the NSTEEs.

Some data constructed from Coulomb scattering could contain sizeable OEIAs because of the underlying centripetal force models. E.g., in the conformal strong force strength measurement, the angular velocities constructed from Coulombic IDS-OCF and the G_{APA}^{∞} constant-OCF models could have one degree of radius power difference without form factor adjustments.¹⁹⁷

Note that the OEIA may be distributed among codependent constructed data; e.g., the derived angular velocity and impact parameter. How these OEIAs are distributed can affect the downstream constructed data; e.g., the interaction force magnitude and interaction radius.

11 OEIA in elementary particle generations' masses

There are three generations according to the Standard Model of particle physics. Each member of a higher generation has greater mass than the corresponding particle of the previous generation, with the possible exception of the neutrinos. E.g., the masses of electron, muon, and tau are $[0.511]_{MeV/c^2}$, $[106]_{MeV/c^2}$, and $[1777]_{MeV/c^2}$ respectively. The second and third generations of charged particles do not occur in normal matter and are only seen in extremely high-energy environments. [32]

EIDIP framework hypothesizes that the elementary particle generations represent the same type of particles operating in different E-domains (aka EPG hypothesis). The higher the particles' generations, the higher the cE-domains they operate. The higher the cE-domain, the higher post-MWEP-transformation residual membrane tension (RMT) energy (masse defects) and the shorter charge radius (because of shorter DSU). Because of the law of conservation of energy, the more energy spent on their mass defects, the lower innate mass the particles have. Note that the particles' E-domain and mass relationship inference contradicts the increasing masses of the electron, muon and tau particles.

However, the MEP and EPG hypotheses do concur with the fact that those higher generation particles are only seen in extremely high-energy environments; i.e., the higher the energy (generation), the higher the E-domain and the shorter the DSU. Furthermore, the EPG hypothesis does work well in producing electronic and muonic proton charge radii (TABLE IV) that matched the measurements. Taken together, they suggest that apart from the mass induced by the environmental extremely high-energy, the inter-domain transfer coupling (IDTC, T_c) effects and the much higher E-domain speed limit ($[(32\pi)^{\#}c]_{m/s}$) could have muddled the constructed elementary particle masses; i.e., the current elementary particle mass measurements could have included the OEIAs.

¹⁹⁶ E.g., quantum scattering models require the massive W bosons of the weak interaction, and modified interaction potentials or additional form factors (e.g., charge density).

12 OEIA as form factors

A form factor is a function measured experimentally to encapsulate the properties of a certain interaction without including all the underlying physics; e.g., the quantum field and elementary particle form factors, charge density, and dark matter distribution.

The NSTEE and conformal regions EIDIP effects have dramatically different behaviors such that the physical phenomena of these two regions are described by different conventional physical models (section IX.C, IX.D, and X.C.2). Hence, although conventional constant couplings models can describe the orderly conformal region EIDIP effects, they cannot describe the turbulent NSTEEs without separated models or additional form factors. These conventional form factors are likely OEIAs because the EIDIP effects have described these physical phenomena without them (section IX.C); in summary,

- (1) The ESC, SF, NNP, and upper bound of the NBE for almost all known nuclei without the quantum field or particle form factors;
- (2) The NCD and PCD without the electromagnetic or charge density form factors;
- (3) The IACF without the atomic form factors;
- (4) The PSAA and MWRC anomalies without the dark matter distribution form factors.

13 OEIA as neutron electric dipole moment problem and proton spin crisis

The SM posits that a tiny separation of positive and negative charge within the neutron leading to a permanent electric dipole moment. However, no neutron electric dipole moment (EDM), a measure for the distribution of positive and negative charge inside the neutron, has been found so far, aka the neutron electric dipole moment problem [33].

In the SM, a proton has three quarks; two of them have their spins parallel to the proton's, and the spin of the third quark is the opposite. However, in the European muon collaboration experiments, it is found that the number of quarks with spin in the proton's spin direction was almost the same as the number of quarks whose spin was in the opposite direction, aka the proton spin crisis [34].

Both the neutron EDM problem and the proton spin crisis are likely OEIAs. The PCD and NCD EEPTs have revealed that the measured PCDs and NCDs are distance dependent EIDIP effects *coupling* rather than *charges* distributions; i.e., there are *no* conventional sense positive and negative charges distributed inside protons and neutrons which can provide some rationales for the neutron EDM problem and proton spin crisis.

In the EIDIP framework, protons' spins and neutrons' EDMs are likely produced by the NSTEE region *rotational* ESC and *irrotational* ERC effects respectively in the

¹⁹⁷ The inverse distance square Coulomb-OCF construed angular velocity is $\omega_c \propto (k_e e^2 / r^3)^{1/2}$ whereas the EIDIP effect is $\omega_E \propto (G_{APA}^{\infty} / r)^{1/2}$; hence, $\omega_E / \omega_c \propto r$.

Dc2.5-domain; whereas the EM models and methods behind the neutron EDM and proton spin direction measurements are constructed from the long-range conformal behaviors of the EIDIP effects. That the distance-dependent NSTEEs cannot be reproduced in the conformal regions where the EM (EMC and EEC) model operates can provide additional clues for the neutron EDM problem and proton spin crisis.

Furthermore, the strength of the positive *irrotational* ERC (the positive area underneath the blue curve, FIG. 71) inside the proton core radius (blue vertical dashed line, FIG. 71) is very weak compared with the negative ERC.¹⁹⁸ The IDTC effect between the Dc0-domain measurement methods and these Dc2.5-domain elementary particle phenomena further reduces the magnitude of these subatomic phenomena. Refer to Appendix III for more details.

Both the proton's asymptotic EIDIP effect coupling (aka PCD) curve (red curve, FIG. 71;) and the rotational ESC (green curve, FIG. 71), presuming both were part of the proton's spin direction measurements, do not change signs within and beyond the proton core (magenta vertical dashed line, FIG. 71). Hence, there are no distance-variant sign-change rotational EIDIP effects couplings within proton core that could have produced statistically unequal spin directions measurements.

FIG. 71. (Color online) Neutron's irrotational ERC curve (blue line), rotational ESC curve (green line) and proton's EIDIP effect coupling curve (red line) figure (blue vertical dashed line: neutron core radius, magenta dashed line: proton core radius).

14 OEIA as weak interaction

Unifying the EM force and the weak force into an electroweak force in SM requires the force-carrying boson to be massless; which contradicts the SM's massive W boson assertion and requires the Higgs mechanism, the massive-massless boson contradiction of the conventional

¹⁹⁸ Refer to section V.C.1; the electronic proton NCR: $[0.872816]_{\text{fm}}$, neutron core radius: $R_c^N = [0.592361]_{\text{fm}}$, proton core radius: $R_c^P = [0.134846]_{\text{fm}}$, and neutron core radius: $R_c^N = [0.592361]_{\text{fm}}$. Note that the areas of the positive and negative ERC within the neutron core in FIG.

electroweak unification methods.

Although the 10+ EEPTs presented did not cover the weak interaction directly, they have shown EIDIP effects can unify the EM and weak interaction without the contradiction of electroweak unification. The 10+ EEPTs have revealed that

- (1) Internucleon binding energies, with which beta decays have causal connections, are internucleon EIDIPs;
- (1) The NCD and PCD are EIDIP effects couplings curves; the weak interaction phenomena between the proton and neutron transformation can be described by EIDIP effects couplings transformations without the massive-massless bosons contradiction;
- (2) The EIDIP effects difference between the rP_r' -NCD and $P_E P_d$ -NCD curves resemble the neutrinos' behaviors: weak, short-range, and do not participate in the strong interaction.

Taken together, they suggest that the EIDIP effects are likely to unify the EM and weak interactions without the massive-massless boson contradiction and deserve further investigations. Refer to Appendix IV for detailed discussions.

15 OEIA in Standard model

The EIDIP effects can describe the behaviors of these elementary particles: *gluon, quark, photon, electron, and graviton* (section IX.D). Hence, it is also likely that the EIDIP effects, especially the short-range NSTEEs, can describe the behaviors of other SM elementary particles without SM's force carrying massless and massive bosons.

The SM posits that those interactions involving the massive bosons die off as the distance between elementary particles grows, and those interactions involving the massless bosons can't decay and follow the standard IDS law. The long-range conformal (settle-to-constant) EIDIP effects couplings induced IDS forces can describe the IDS behaviors of massless bosons; whereas the short-range NSTEEs can describe the behaviors of massive bosons and the LCEN effects further limit their ranges.

E.g., the rP_r' -NCD, effective couplings EEPTs have revealed that the NSTEE region irrotational $P_d r^2$ and rotational P_r can describe the ERC and ESC without gluon. Whereas the long-range conformal (settle-to-constant) $P_d^\infty r^2$ and P_r^∞ can describe the constant EMC and EEC without photons. Furthermore, the NCD and PCD EEPTs have revealed that positive and negative charge are EIDIP effects couplings and that the neutrinos and massive W bosons phenomena of the weak interaction during the proton to neutron transformation are part of the EIDIP effects $d(P_E)/dr \leftrightarrow P_E/r$ transformation.

71 are approximately equal such that neutrons have no net "electric charge"; i.e., the neutron core radius derived from the NCR EEPT should match the net-zero ERC radius.

16 OEIA as gravitational frame-dragging and gravitational time dilation measurements

The 10+ EEPTs have revealed that photons, atoms, and even astronomical objects possess MWEPs (aka AEMWEP hypothesis). The attractive EIDIP effects between a gravitating mass and a nearby object could have produced the nonclassical gravitational frame-dragging phenomena, i.e., the frame-dragging phenomena are OEIAs. Furthermore, the AEAAN effect between two rotating gravitating objects can make their orbits precess and produce the rotational frame-dragging phenomena; whereas the irrotational EIDIP effects between two non-rotating gravitating masses can change the linear momentum of nearby objects and produce the linear frame-dragging phenomena.

The interactions between the atomic clocks' oscillating atoms, rotating Earth, and especially nearby orbiting Moon produce angular EIDIP effects;¹⁹⁹ of which the AEAAN effect can nudge the precessions and orbital circumferences of the oscillating atoms on the microscopic scale such that they change the atomic clocks' time unit. I.e., the AEAAN could have produced the observed gravitational time dilation measurements.

17 OEIA as relativistic time dilation and direction

The time dilation and direction required to explain some quantum behaviors are also likely to be OEIAs. To describe the NSTEEs, the conventional models need to employ variable time durations (aka time dilation) or directions to keep up the constant coupling models that work well in describing the long-range interactions.²⁰⁰ Although relativistic *monochromatic* time dilation adjustments can approximately describe the initial *monochromatic* deviation between the NSTEEs and conventional constant couplings, they still cannot fully describe the turbulent and sign changing NSTEEs that would require form factors or time reversal hypotheses to fully describe them. E.g., the $1/(1 - (v/c)^n)$ relativistic adjustment, where the value increases with a higher velocity, can describe the initial descending (increasing in magnitude, ignoring the sign) $rP_d \propto r^{-1}$ and $rP_r' \propto r^{-1}$ curves approaching the NSTEE region (FIG. 70) but not the direction and sign changing NSTEEs as the distance (energy) gets shorter (higher).²⁰¹ Furthermore, the relativistic adjustments that reach singularity at the speed of light cannot accurately described the behaviors of the faster-than-light high-order E-domain EIDIP effects

The observed cold-to-hot heat transfer quantum phenomena between entangled particles that required a

reverse-arrow-of-time explanation under conventional models [35] could also be OEIAs. Because the systemic EIDIP effects could have multiple local-stable inter-object locations (section IV.D.4), under some circumstances, some of the entangled particles could have tunneled from the longer (cooler) to the shorter (hotter) local-stable locations and produced the strange cold-to-hot heat transfer phenomena.

18 EIDIP effects induced quantum decoherence and entanglement behaviors

The 10+ EEPTs have revealed that all energy entities possess the MWEP regardless of their size; the interaction between targets and measuring apparatuses produces the EIDIP effects. Hence, for those targets that possess spins, the AEAAN effects, especially those produced by the local minimum and maximum of both rotational and irrotational NSTEE (e.g., FIG. 70), can coerce their physical possibilities (e.g., spin directions) into a single possibility (e.g., preferred spin direction) and give the appearance of wave function collapse, aka the quantum decoherence.²⁰²

Because entangled particles possess opposite spin directions, the maximum direction separation allows the *local* AEAAN effects to recover the complementary spin directions statistically in the distances; of which the results can be perceived as *at-a-distance* entangled measurements. I.e., the *local* AEAAN effects can provide the rationale for the strange quantum entangled measurements in-distance.

Furthermore, the faster-than-light high-order EIDIP effects and the conformal settle-to-constant EIDIP effects can provide the rationale for the long-range faster-than-light quantum entanglement.

19 OEIA as gravitoelectromagnetism

Gravitoelectromagnetism, abbreviated GEM, refers specifically to the kinetic effects of gravity in analogy to the magnetic effects of moving electric charge. The main consequence of the gravitomagnetic field is that a moving object near a massive rotating object will experience acceleration not predicted by a purely Newtonian (gravitoelectric) gravity field [28].

The ESC, ERC, EMC and EEC EEPTs have revealed that these effective couplings can be connected by the cE-domain's NSTEE and conformal regions EIDIP effects. The 10+ EEPTs have revealed that the cE-domains EIDIP effects also exist in the xE-domains (TABLE VIII), aka the SCXEE hypothesis, such that these cE-domain effective couplings should also have their xE-domain counterparts: the turbulent astronomical rotational gravitostrong

¹⁹⁹ Because the Dx0-domain angular EIDIP effect G_{APA} is asymptotic and peaks at $[2.16]_{Dx0} = [3.24 \times 10^8]_m$ which is close to the time-averaged distance between the Earth and the Moon centers $[3.85 \times 10^8]_m$. Refer to section X.D.22 EIDIP effects induced near-Earth flyby anomalies for the Earth and the Moon induced G_{APA} -OCFs comparison.

²⁰⁰ E.g., to maintain the coupling per time unit to be the same as the long-range constant couplings, one can also define a shorter domain time duration (DTU) to limit the E-domain speed limit (DSL) to the value of c.

²⁰¹ In a simplistic view, $v \propto \text{energy} \propto 1/r$ and $(v/c)^n \propto r^{-n}$.

²⁰² In analogy to the Schrödinger's cat thought experiment, assuming a cat has an appetite scale range from zero to ten, ten being starving and zero being well-fed, the AEAAN effect is the pungent and tasty poisoned food that *attracts* and *repels* the cats above and below appetite scale of five respectively toward the food (quantum decoherence). Putting a cat from a group of cats into a box with the poisoned food, the cat's fate is unknown until the box is open but only if the cats' appetite scale is unknown; i.e., the cat's fate is statistically known if the cats' appetite scale statistical distribution is known.

coupling (GSC) and irrotational gravitoelectric coupling (GEC) produced by the xE-domain NSTEEs and the stable astronomical rotational gravitomagnetic coupling (GMC) and irrotational gravitoelectric coupling (GEC) produced by the xE-domain conformal EIDIP effects (TABLE VI).

TABLE VIII. Symmetrical cE- and xE- domains EIDIP effects examples table.

	Short-range NSTEE	Long-range conformal
cE-	ESC (P_r^\pm), ERC ($r^2 P_d^\pm$), SF (P_r^\pm), Hadron jets;	EMC (P_r^∞), EEC ($r^2 P_d^\infty$);
xE-	GSC (P_r^\pm), GRC ($r^2 P_d^\pm$), PSAA (P_r^\pm), Astrophysical jets;	GMC (P_r^∞), GEC ($r^2 P_d^\infty$);

Note that the meaning of gravitomagnetic and gravitoelectric of the GMC and GEC differs from the conventional GEM terminology. In the EIDIP framework, the gravitomagnetic and gravitoelectric represent the astronomical rotational and irrotational EIDIP effects produced by the interactions of gravity fields (MWEPs in the EIDIP framework or gravitoelectric fields in the GEM); whereas in the GEM terminology, the gravitomagnetic fields represent the kinetic effects (i.e., EIDIP effects) of Newtonian gravity field [28]. The terminology differences reflect the fundamental relationship difference between gravity and other fundamental forces: the parent-child relationship of the EIDIP framework vs. the peer-to-peer relationship presumed by the conventional models.

The EIDIP effects' behaviors can explain the main consequence of the gravitomagnetic field on a moving object near a massive rotating object. Because the interaction between a moving object and a nearby massive rotating object produces both rotational and irrotational EIDIP effects, depending on the distance, the moving object will experience the turbulent or conformal EIDIP effects induced accelerations beyond the Newtonian limit and described by the GEM as the gravitomagnetic fields. E.g., indirect validations of gravitomagnetic effects have been derived from analyses of astrophysical jets [28], and the behaviors of astrophysical and hadron jets could be described by the xE- and cE- domains NSTEEs (section X.D.4). With that, the indirect validations of gravitomagnetic effects on the astrophysical jets also indirectly validate the SCXEE hypothesis. Furthermore, depending on the distance, the *rotational* GSC or GMC could have produced the observed *rotational* frame dragging phenomena; whereas the *irrotational* GRC or GEC could have produced the observed *linear* frame dragging phenomena.

The EIDIP effects' behaviors can give some clues for why the most common version of GEM is valid only far from isolated sources and for slowly moving test particles

[28]. Although the NSTEE regions have short ranges in terms of the xE-domain DSU [4]_{Rx#} approximately, their ranges are far in the common sense of distance; i.e., those xE-domain EIDIP effects that are conformal like the gravitomagnetic fields are far from the astronomical sources. Furthermore, the NSTEEs' behaviors (e.g., asymptotic) differ vastly from the conformal region (e.g., settle-to-constant); their strengths also increase with the test particles' velocities;²⁰³ and the higher the interaction body count, the more complicated the EIDIP effects. Hence, the most common version of the GEM is valid only for *far* from *isolated* sources and *slowly* moving bodies.

Taken together, they suggest that the xE-domain EIDIP effects produced the observed astronomical gravitoelectromagnetism. Which also exemplifies that the EIDIP framework does not contradict and can unify these disparate physics models: the gravitoelectromagnetism (general relativity) and Newtonian gravity, and the accumulated knowledge of the gravitoelectromagnetism can accelerate the future development of the astronomical effective couplings: GSC, GRC, GMC, and GEC of the EIDIP framework.

20 EIDIP effects on black hole structure

In the EIDIP framework, the mass composition and structure of GC regions differ vastly from the current black hole models, and the existence of event horizons is also in question.

The MWEP's quantized singularity differs from the at-origin-singularity Newtonian gravitational potential such that the zero-order E-domain G_{MGA} does not have the infinite strength to compact matter indefinitely. Furthermore, because all E-domains have limited energy densities and spatial units, even though GC region matters' gravity can compress their components to higher order cE-domain particles, GC region matters still have density limits regardless of their compositions. E.g., the NBE EEPT has revealed that the inter-quark distance has a lower bound ($R_u = 1/c^2$) such that even the GC regions composed of quark plasma still have density limits.

GC regions could comprise high order matters with high mass defects such that they have low innate masses to produce gravity. The higher the orders of particles' cE-domain, the higher post-MWEP-transformation residual membrane tension (RMT) energy (equation (10)) or mass defects. Because of the law of conservation of energy, the more energy spent on the mass defect, the lower the innate mass to produce gravity. I.e., apart from the quantized-singularities of MWEPs (gravitational potentials of various orders), the gravity produced by the innate mass of GC region matter has a limit.

Astronomical xE-domain NSTEE regions have large radii $[4]_{Dx\#} = [2(32\pi)^{\#}c]_m$ approximately (magenta box, FIG. 70) that can be much longer than the Schwarzschild

²⁰³ Apart from the direct hit cases, all off-center fly paths have angular components.

radius;²⁰⁴ and their turbulent behaviors (e.g., asymptotic and repulsive) differ vastly from the monochromatically increasing strength of Newtonian gravity way before the Schwarzschild radius. The high-order repulsive EIDIP effects (astrophysical jets, section X.D.4) can eject astronomic flybys way before they reach the Schwarzschild radius and prevent the mass build up in the GC region. The repulsive EIDIP effects strengths are proportional to the mass; the higher the GC region's mass, the higher the ejecting power.

Furthermore, the existences of black holes are based on the galactic and super-galactic Newtonian Keplerian data that are likely to have sizeable OEIAs. Because current measuring apparatus and models cannot directly detect the high order gravity and EIDIP effects from these high order components, these high order matters could appear to be black.

21 EIDIP effects induced gravity waves

Although current measuring apparatus may not be able to detect the high order gravity (EIDIP) effects directly, they can detect the zero-order interaction effects between the high-order gravity (EIDIP) effects and zero-order MWEPs; e.g., the bending of the Dc0-domain photons' direction in the astronomical gravitational lensing (section X.D.9).

The strengths of high-order gravities decay with the inverse distance square whereas the strengths of some high-order EIDIP effects decay less in distances (e.g., distance-invariant) than gravity such that their effects are more likely to be detected across super-galactic distances.²⁰⁵ Hence, in the EIDIP framework, the photons speed deviations in the gravity waves (GW) detectors were more likely produced by the interaction effects between the local zero-order photons and the high order EIDIP effects emitted from distant galaxies.

Both the Hanford and the Livingston LIGO gravity-wave datasets (GW150914-H1 and GW150914-L1) clearly show an up-sweep beat frequency amplitude (BFA) pattern on the frequency-time plane (figure 1 of [36]). In the GR model, the 0.8 second up-sweep BFA patterns depict a GW from a two-galaxy high-speed hit-and-merge encounter.

Note that the Hanford subfigure also shows a dimmer symmetrical down-sweep BFA pattern (FIG. 72, reproduced from figure 1 of [36]) but unnoticeable in the Livingston subfigure of [36]. However, with a different set of noise reduction filters and color bar configuration,²⁰⁶ the Livingston figure also shows a partial down-sweep BFA pattern right before the up-sweep (FIG. 73).

²⁰⁴ E.g., Milky Way Schwarzschild radius $[2.05 \times 10^{15}]_m \cong [0.0014]_{Dx5}$ is much shorter than the MW's Dx5-NSTEE region radii $[4]_{Dx5} = [6.1567 \times 10^{18}]_m$ revealed in the MWRC EEPTs.

²⁰⁵ The Dx2-NSTEE effects become notable beyond $[1]_{Dx2}$ as shown in the PSAA EEPT and become stronger than gravity beyond $[4]_{Dx5}$ approximately as shown in the MWRC RPPFs.

²⁰⁶ Filter type = ellip; notch filter (in "filter note frequency, strength;" pair)=[36.70, 1; 37.30, 1; 40.95, 1; 60.00, 1; 120.00, 1; 179.99, 0.5]; band

FIG. 72. (Color online) The EIDIP astronomical range SASDE curve (orange dashed curve) Vs. GW150914-H1 (Hanford) beat frequency amplitude (Z: in green color gradient) on frequency (Y)-time (X) plane figure.

FIG. 73. (Color online) GW150914-L1 (Livingston) partial down-sweep (between 16.25 and 16.34 sec) and up-sweep (between 16.34 to 16.42 sec) BFA on frequency (Y)-time (X) plane figure.²⁰⁶

With the extremely low galaxy density of our universe, it is safe to assume that the chance of two galaxies glide-by encounters is higher than the hit-and-merge encounters. In the EIDIP framework, for an encounter between galaxies of similar mass, the observed GWs are likely produced by the high-order xE-domain systemic EIDIP effects ripples produced by the astronomical glide-by encounters. E.g., the approximately symmetrical BFA patterns of GW150914-H1 (Hanford), which clearly shows a glide-in and glide-off pattern, can be phenomenologically fitted by the second-order angular system-differential-EIDIP (SASDE) $rP'_{r[D]}$ curve (FIG. 72).²⁰⁷

With the AEAAN effects, faster-than-light high-order EIDIP effects, and the accuracy limit of the triangulation of cosmic event's position, the GW's origin locations differ between the EIDIP framework and conventional models. E.g., the detected BFA intensities can vary depending on the angles between the glide-paths and detection planes because of the AEAAN effects; which can explain some of the intensity variations between segments and between detectors.

The galaxies' NSTEE region encounter duration ∂t_s

pass filter =[43, 260]; data source: GW-L1_LOSC_16_V1-1126259446-32.txt of [42].

²⁰⁷ This $T_c = (32\pi)^{0.25} rP'_{r[D]}$ curve (red, FIG. 27) is flipped vertically, combined with a horizontally mirrored glide-in curve, and shifted vertically to fit GW150914 data. Note that none of the EIDIP effects underlying the 10+ EEPTs were systemic EIDIP effects, this GW could be the physical phenomena to valid the systemic EIDIP effects.

differs from the detected BFA sweep duration ∂t_d because of the encounter directions. For explanatory purpose, consider a case that the GW detector is on the galaxies glide-by plane and the galaxies' NSTEE region encounter starting (glide-in) and ending (glide-out) positions are on the X-axis (the two intersections on the X-axis between the dotted circle and dotted purple arrow line, FIG. 74).

For a detector with an inclination angle θ to X-axis (yellow dot 1, FIG. 74), assuming $\Delta d_{se} = D_s - D_s \cong \Delta d_x \cos \theta$, the time difference between the glide-in and glide-out GW's arrivals, the detected BFA sweep (DBS) duration, is approximately

$$\partial t_d = |\partial t_s \pm \Delta d_x \cos \theta / v_w|, \quad (82)$$

with $\partial t_{\Delta d} \cong \Delta d_x \cos \theta / v_w$ and v_w as the GW's propagation velocity. Note that depending on the glide-by direction, the $\partial t_{\Delta d}$ can be additive or subtractive.²⁰⁸ It is also possible to detect reversed BFA sweep patterns in $\partial t_{\Delta d} > \partial t_s$ cases; hence, the absolute operator. Hence, with a subtractive $\partial t_{\Delta d}$ of which the value is close to ∂t_s , it is possible that some high-order EIDIP effects could have produced the $\sim [0.16]_s$ BFA sweep of GW150914-H1.²⁰⁹

Note that the GW's propagation velocity v_w does not affect the maximum $\partial t_{\Delta d}$ as it seems in equation (82) of this explanatory model. Although the high-order EIDIP effects have faster speed $v_w = [2]_{Dx\#/s}$ than the zero-order effects $v_w = [2]_{Dx0/s} = [c]_{m/s}$, they also have larger NSTEE region radii $\sim [4]_{Dx\#}$ to produce the higher maximum $\Delta d_x \cong [8]_{Dx\#}$ such that $\partial t_{\Delta d} \cong [8]_{Dx\#} \cos \theta / [2]_{Dx\#/s} = [4 \cos \theta]_s$ regardless the E-domains of the underlying EIDIP effects.

FIG. 74. (Color online) Galaxies' NSTEE region encounter duration ∂t_s differs from the detected BFA

sweep duration $\partial t_d \cong \Delta d_x \cos \theta / v_w \pm \partial t_s$ figure. (dotted circle: NSTEE region

Because the GW's propagation velocity, the GWs' arrival time, and the distances between detectors are used to estimate the locations of the GWs' sources, the $(32\pi)^\#$ time faster than the light speed of high-order EIDIP effects greatly affect the estimated GWs' source's distance; in turn, the estimated locations and their uncertainties. E.g., with arrival time difference $[\partial t_{D12}]_s$ and the distance $[k_{D12} \times c]_m$ between two detectors, the estimated distance difference between the GW source and two detectors is $[2 \times \partial t_{D12}]_{Dx\#}$ and the inter-detectors distance is $[k_{D12} / (32\pi)^\#]_{Dx\#}$ regardless the GW's xE-domains. Hence, for the triangulation based on three fixed location detectors, the higher the E-domain, the smaller the triangle area in DSU. With the same source-detector distances in DSU, the estimated GW source's distance and locations are different with different xE-domains underlying the GWs.

Because current instruments can only directly detect the zero-order EIDIP effects of the most expulsive event (e.g., astrophysical jet) produced locally by the faster-than-light of the high-order EIDIP effects afar, the elapsed time between them differ from conventional models abiding by the speed of light limit axiom. I.e., the local GW detection could be ahead of the observed Dc0-effects emitting events afar, and the elapsed time between them could provide clues of the distance of the GW's origin.²¹⁰

22 EIDIP effects induced near-Earth flyby anomalies

The near-Earth flybys' speed anomalies (NEFA) are likely to be produced by the Dx0-domain EIDIP effects; i.e., these NEFAs are likely OEIAs. The EIDIP effects between the flybys and nearby Earth and Moon have both the radial and the angular components; the angular EIDIP effects have asymptotic and conformal behaviors that are affected by the distances and inclination angles to Earth and Moon. Hence, the EIDIP effects between the flybys and the Moon could be higher than between the flybys and Earth. I.e., the interactions between the flybys and the Moon can play a dominant role in the NEFAs.

The Moon-OCF can be stronger than the Earth-OCF in the NEFAs even accounting for the mass ratio between Earth and Moon. E.g., the Dx0-domain angular EIDIP effect G_{APA} acting on the flybys has an asymptotic region near the source (Earth and Moon) and peaks around $[3.24 \times 10^8]_m$ away from the source (FIG. 75). Because the time-averaged distance between Earth and Moon's centers is about $[3.85 \times 10^8]_m$, the flybys' near-Earth position would put them in the peak Moon-origin G_{APA} region and the asymptotic Earth-origin G_{APA} region.

Using the NEAR-flyby anomaly as an example, at the NEAR-flyby's minimum altitude position, the near-Earth

²⁰⁸ E.g., for the detector-1 and 2 in FIG. 74, their $\partial t_{\Delta d}$ are subtractive because of their $D_s > D_e$.

²⁰⁹ In this case, the BFA sweep of the GW150914 is only the glide-in and glide-out tips of the (SASDE) $rP'_{r|D}$ curve shown in FIG. 72.

²¹⁰ Note that the NSTEE region is approximately $[4]_{DSU}$ and their expulsive effects could peak in less than $[1]_{DSU}$ region (e.g., FIG. 70). The NSTEE strength and instruments' sensitivities affect the local NSTEEs' zero-order harmonics' detectable duration; i.e., these factors need to be taken into consideration when calculating the elapsed time.

distance put the NEAR-flyby at the asymptotic region of the Earth-origin G_{APA} (red vertical dashed line, FIG. 75). At the same time, it also experiences about six hundred times of the Moon-origin G_{APA} .²¹¹ Accounting for Earth and Moon mass-ratio of about 81.3, the Moon- to Earth-OCFs ratio drops to about 7.3.²¹² I.e., at the NEAR-flyby's minimum altitude position, ignoring the inclination angle effect, the Moon-OCF is the dominant source.

Note that these estimates neither account for the effects of the NEAR-flyby's dynamics (e.g., rotational and inclination angles) on the rotational G_{APA} nor other irrotational EIDIP effects. Furthermore, the estimated single digit ratio between the Moon-OCF to Earth-OCF of the NEAR-flyby case opens the door to explain other NEFAs (e.g., the MESSENGER NEFA) that experienced very low anomalous acceleration.

FIG. 75. (Color online) Earth-origin (red vertical dashed line) and Moon-origin (between green and blue vertical dashed lines) G_{APA} experienced by NEAR-flyby at minimum altitude figure.

XI. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

A. Discussion

Differing from the conventional phenomena-hypotheses-equations development sequence, the EIDIP framework has an unorthodox hypothesis-equations-phenomena-hypotheses development sequence: the MWEP hypothesis, EIDIP effects equations, 10+ EEPTs, and explanatory hypotheses.²¹³ Although the EIDIP framework is built on objective equations because math operators and MATLAB programming language are

²¹¹ In FIG. 75, the normalized $G_{APA}(P_r)$ magnitude ratio between the red horizontal dashed line (1.64×10^{-3}) and the green (0.98) or blue (0.97) horizontal dashed lines is about 600.

²¹² The estimated Earth- and Moon-OCFs are based on these parameters and assumptions: Earth mass: $[5.9751 \times 10^{24}]_{kg}$, Moon mass: $[7.3477 \times 10^{22}]_{kg}$, the time-averaged distance between the Earth and Moon centers: $[385000]_{km}$, the average Earth radius: $[6368.5]_{km}$, and the NEAR-flyby's minimum altitude: $[523]_{km}$ [47]; the Earth radius plus the NEAR-flyby's minimum altitude as the flyby-Earth distance, and the flyby-Moon distances of the in-line Moon-flyby-Earth and Moon-

inarguably objective, the unorthodox EIDIP framework presented in this paper employs the computational simulations reasonings rather than the conventional physics mechanics arguments, has unorthodox hypotheses and predictions, and claims it can be the cornerstone of Theory of Everything. Hence, the unorthodox EIDIP framework can lead to many questions. In this section, we discuss some of them.

1 Obstacles and pitfalls of an amateur physicist

There are a lot of obstacles or pitfalls an amateur physicist like me can have;²¹⁴ e.g., as pointed out in [37], in general,

- (1) Not aware of the prerequisite, culture and sociology requirement of physics research;
- (2) Lacking the required mathematical skills; hence, the desire to use simple math to explain all things;
- (3) Theoretical physics today has highly specialized sub-fields, each requires particular math skills or discovery of a whole new branch of mathematics;
- (4) Focused on well-known and published open issues;
- (5) Limited access to good quality empirical datasets; research relies on publicly available information and scientific paper depositaries.

During the EIDIP framework development, I have experienced and avoided some of the obstacles; e.g., that some of the references and empirical datasets and figures in this paper were from publicly available information and scientific paper depositaries may not meet the culture and sociology requirement of physics research. Furthermore, for some readers, the long list of physical phenomena that the EIDIP effects could provide coherent rationales for (section X.D) is a sign of the amateur's pitfall, the desire to use simple math to explain all things.

Despite the shortcomings, I believe the nascent EIDIP framework has avoided or mitigated the effects of these pitfalls, has shown that it can contribute to theoretical physics and is worthy of further investigations:

- (1) The EIDIP framework is built on the plain MWEP and EIDIP effects equations I discovered; with the computational tools like MATLAB, the EIDIP framework avoids the need for specific physics mechanics and highly specialized math. On the other hand, the EIDIP equation, although it looks simple conceptually, requires an unorthodox segmented dual-sphere volume integral;²¹⁵

Earth-flyby alignments as the minimum and maximum distances respectively.

²¹³ I discovered the MWEP and EIDIP equations prior to 2005; first few EEPTs and hypotheses were summarized and published to the internet on 2011/9 [52]. I also presented a nascent EIDIP framework summary poster at APS 2014 April meeting [54].

²¹⁴ I was a computer design architect/engineer and, inspired by a team of Harvard, Sandford, and Berkeley physicists I worked with between 2003-2005, became an amateur physicist.

²¹⁵ To implement the long-range segmented dual-sphere volume integral between two MWEPs with acceptable error is difficult in the

- (2) The public domain empirical datasets and figures used in the 10+ EEPTs are objective and precise enough to convey the explanatory power of the nascent EIDIP framework; also, the conservative 50% NHTN probability and the maximum of three primary NHTNs per EEPT in the 5+ sigma statistical significance level calculation should have accounted for the deficiencies;
- (3) The 10+ reproducible EEPTs included both the well-known open issues and the well-modeled physical phenomena; these EEPTs have revealed that the EIDIP framework can describe these anomalous-or-not physical phenomena and unify gravity with other fundamental-or-not forces;
- (4) The EIDIP framework possesses the major precepts of the scientific method: verifiability, predictability, falsifiability, and fairness; it is also more feasible, elegant, and simpler than the disparate conventional models (section X.A.);
- (5) Those 60+ NHTNs extracted from those three-variable EEPT have affirmed that nulling the EIDIP's existence has a 5+ sigma statistical significance level; which has also indicated that the EIDIP framework has high statistical confidence.

In short, if an amateur proposed EIDIP framework possesses the major scientific methods precepts, is based on plain EIDIP effects equations, can explain a wide range of anomalous-or-not physical phenomena, can unify gravity and other fundamental-or-not forces, and have high statistical confidence, the EIDIP framework can contribute to theoretical physics and is worthy of further investigations.

2 Feasibility of EIDIP framework

The 10+ EEPTs have shown that, with only three variables and without resorting to the aid of conventional form factors, the non-perturbative EIDIP framework can

- (1) Describe the strong force's asymptotic, conformal, and short interaction range without the quantum field or elementary particle form factors;
- (2) Describe the relationship between the long-range effective electric and magnetic couplings, and the short-range effective strong and residual-strong couplings;
- (3) Describe the relationships between the EIDIP effects and these physical constants: Coulomb's constant, elementary charge, the fine structure constant, and Planck constant;
- (4) Describe the neutron and proton charge distribution curves as the NSTEE couplings curves without charge density form factors;
- (5) Describe some weak interaction phenomena without the contradiction of electroweak unification;
- (6) Describe the distance-dependent repulsive-attractive behaviors of internucleon nuclear force and interatomic covalent force without the elementary particle and atomic form factors;
- (7) Describe the Bohr radius;
- (8) Describe both the steep-ascending and the slow-descending segments of the Pioneer 10/11 anomalies;
- (9) Describe the anomalous Milky Way rotation curve and provide clues for other galaxies rotation curves of various slopes without the dark matter form factor;
- (10) Explain the different shapes between the observed CMWRC and the collective RAVE-DR2 MWRCs through the astronomical AEAAN effects;
- (11) Explain galactic rings formations (especially the turnover rings) through the gravitational force ripples, with or without negative gravitational force (NGF) regions, induced by astronomical EIDIP effects;
- (12) Explain the large deviation between the Newtonian gravitational constant measurements as the OEIA on top of the EIDIP framework's gravitational constant $[2R_0]_{\text{m}^3/\text{s}^2}$;
- (13) Describe the upper bound of the nuclear binding energy for almost all known nuclei; the NBE-SEFs based on which are more accurate than the conventional liquid drop model based NBE-SEFs;
- (14) Formulate spherical-shell based NCR-SEFs for heavy nuclei and individual NCR-SEFs for light nuclei with physical parameters deducted from the SF, NNP and NBE EEPTs. The heavy nuclei NCRs produced by which are more accurate than the conventional sphere-volume based or Skyrme-Hartree-Fock-Bogoliubov based NCR-SEFs; whereas the electronic and muonic proton, neutron, and deuteron NCRs produced by which matched the empirical NCRs of these light nuclei.

Furthermore, the non-perturbative EIDIP framework can gain insights from the 10+ three-variable EEPTs that perturbative or high variable count models cannot. The gained insights from these EEPTs can provide coherent first-order rationales or additional clues for additional physical phenomena beyond the Newtonian limit (section X.D):

- (1) Wave duality of energy entities: photons, electrons, atoms, molecules, astronomical objects, etc.;
- (2) Hadron jets;
- (3) Neutron electric dipole moment problem;
- (4) Proton spin crisis;
- (5) Photon antibunching;
- (6) Quantum decoherence;
- (7) Quantum entanglement;

computational implementations; therefore, I believe, to implement it with conventional physics mechanics would be much harder.

- (8) Gravitational lensing;
- (9) Gravitational linear and rotational frame-dragging;
- (10) Relativistic time dilation;
- (11) Gravitational time dilation measurements;
- (12) Observed reverse-arrow-of-time cold-to-hot heat transfer quantum phenomena;
- (13) Galaxy structures: center-bulge-and-outer-disk, spiral arms, and galactic rings formations;
- (14) Dark matter and dark energy;
- (15) Accelerating expansion of the universe;
- (16) Astrophysical jets;
- (17) Astronomical gravitoelectromagnetism;
- (18) Black hole structures;
- (19) Gravity waves;
- (20) Near-Earth flyby anomalies.

3 Computational simulations based figurative reasonings

The NBE and NCR EEPTs included the statistical information between the empirical data and EIDIP effects which have shown that the EIDIP based SEFs produced NBE and NCR were comparable to, if not more accurate than, the values produced by the conventional Bethe-Weizsäcker NBE-SEF and Skyrme-Hartree-Fock-Bogoliubov based SWNCR-SEF (section V.B.2).

However, some EEPTs were based on the MATLAB simulated EIDIP effects curves manually overlaid on empirical figures rather than computationally plotted with the empirical data. Although great attention was taken to make sure their X and Y grids were closely matched between the simulation and empirical figures during manual overlays, the produced figures still contain some unavoidable manual operation induced errors. Furthermore, these figurative arguments are lacking statistical information between the empirical data and EIDIP effects.

With these deficiencies, some may find that the figurative reasoning method does not meet the culture and sociology requirement of physics research. However, these EEPTs' figures have clearly shown that the EIDIP effects can trace these anomalous-or-not physical phenomena; i.e., they are precise enough to show the explanatory power of the nascent EIDIP framework. Furthermore, the EIDIP's 5+ sigma statistical significance level computation employed the conservative 50% NHTN probability, and the maximum of three primary NHTNs was produced by each EEPT regardless of the EEPT's empirical data size, i.e., maximum 0.125 significance probability contribution. Hence, the significance level computation should have left enough margin to cover the statistical error brought by the deficiencies of the figurative reasoning.

²¹⁶ The Planck length is approximately $[1]_{Pk} \cong [0.519]_{Dc12} = [1.616 \times 10^{-35}]_m$ or $[2]_{Pk} \approx [1]_{Dc12}$.

4 Deterministic EIDIP framework does not conflict with uncertainty principle and observer effect

Although based on deterministic EIDIP effects equations, the EIDIP framework does not violate the quantum uncertainty principle because the MWEP underlying the EIDIP possesses the particle-wave duality (E-fermion and E-boson), and the uncertainty principle is inherent in the properties of all wave-like systems [38]. Furthermore, a physical measurement always takes part in certain E-domains that come with the energy resolution and DSU limit. Note that the Planck length is about one half of the $Dc12$ -DSU.²¹⁶

The EIDIP framework supports the physical observer effect that observing a phenomenon changes the phenomenon necessarily; this is because, in addition to the AEAAN effects and OSPD-misalignment oscillations, the short-range NSTEE effects between the target and test particles' close encounters will change the target's position and momentum and induce uncertainties in measurements.

5 High-order Gravity and EIDIP effects are faster-than-light

The EIDIP framework posits that the high-order gravity and EIDIP effects travel faster than light because they possess much higher residual tensions than zero-order effects. E.g., the CMWRC EEPT have revealed that the underlying EIDIP effects operate in the Dx5-harmonic and travel at Dx5-domain's speed limit $[2]_{Dx5/s} \approx [10^{10}c]_{m/s}$.

Although the faster-than-light assertion contradicts the well-accepted lightspeed limit axiom, it does concur with the faster-than-light gravity speed $> [2 \times 10^{10}c]_{m/s}$ based purely on observed gravity-OCF from the solar system and binary stars [6]. Because the gravity speed calculations of [6] did not account for the EIDIP effects, the OEIA could have produced the higher gravity speed of [6] (section X.C.5).

The time lag between the high-order GW source events observed afar and their local zero-order interaction phenomena observed at detectors can be used to check the faster-than-light of the high-order EIDIP effects hypothesis. Note that affirming the speed of high-order EIDIP effects can also give credence to the multiple E-domain pairs (MEP) and MWEP transformation hypotheses. Hence, they are fertile grounds for future discoveries and deserve further investigations.

6 Sizeable OEIA in well-accepted physical models and constructed data

I have hypothesized that some well-accepted physical models and constructed data could have sizeable OEIAs such that they can alter our understanding of physical phenomena and physical models (section IX.D and X.D). E.g., the likely OEIAs in the Newtonian Kepler's laws

produced data (e.g., galaxy masses, speeds, distances in the intergalactic range and beyond) can alter our understanding of astronomical phenomena and structures: rotation curves, galactic rings, black holes, etc.

Hence, those physical phenomena for which the EIDIP effects can provide coherent rationales and connections (section X.D) are fertile grounds for future discoveries. Although these rationales are unorthodox, the EIDIP framework's high statistical confidence does give credence to the rationales and support for further investigations.

7 Yet-to-be-identified elementary particles or astronomical phenomena

The EIDIP framework's multiple E-domain pairs (MEP) hypothesis have implicated the possible existence of yet-to-be-identified Dc5-domain elementary particles and Dx2.5-domain astronomical gravitational phenomena based on and the Dx5-domain MWRC EEPT and the Dc2.5-domain SF EEPT respectively (section X.C.4). Or, if there is no Dx2.5-domain astronomical gravitational phenomenon found, the SF and NNP could be the Dc5-domain or Dc2-domain harmonic phenomena rather than the Dc2.5-domain phenomena. These salient implications can falsify the MEP hypothesis and are fertile grounds for future discoveries.

8 EIDIP effects and fundamental physical constants

The effective couplings EEPTs: ESC, ERC, EMC, and EEC have revealed the connection between the EIDIP effects and these fundamental physical constants: vacuum permeability μ_0 , Coulomb's constant k_e , elementary charge e , reduced Planck constant \hbar , and the fine structure constant α .

However, the values produced by the EIDIP based EEC and EMC formulas have approximately 4.43% deviation from the values produced by the fundamental physical constants comprised formulas. I have hypothesized that the unaccounted EIDIP effects and the muddled elementary charge constant measurements by which could be the major deviation contributors (section VIII.E.4). The sources of the EEC and EMC deviations are fertile grounds for future discoveries and deserves further investigations.

9 Symmetrical cE- and xE- domains EIDIP effects embrace gravitoelectromagnetism and cross-pollination of accumulated knowledge

The 10+ EEPTs have shown that the EIDIP effects exist symmetrically in the cE- and xE- domains (FIG. 68 and TABLE VI) and can consistently describe the physical behaviors described by the conventional models such that it is likely that the xE-domain EIDIP effects have produced the astronomical gravitoelectromagnetism (section X.D.19). The symmetrical cE- and xE- domains EIDIP effects make possible for the cross-pollination of their accumulated knowledge such that the accumulated

knowledges of conventional models can also accelerate future EIDIP framework developments.

E.g., the accumulated knowledges of the subatomic effective couplings (ESC, ERC, EMC, and EEC) and astronomical gravitoelectromagnetism can accelerate the future discovery of the astronomical effective couplings (GSC, GRC, GMC, and GEC) and other xE-domain EIDIP effects such that they can accelerate the unification of the gravitoelectromagnetism (general relativity) and Newtonian gravity.

10 Generic EIDIP effects magnitude formula can provide insights into and connections between seemingly unrelated physical phenomena

The same type of EIDIP effect should have the isomorphic magnitude formulas regardless of their E-domains (aka ISOMF hypothesis, section IX.D). The gradient-EEPTs: IACF, NGCD, and NNP have revealed that they are likely to have isomorphic magnitude formula (equation (80)); however, the 10+ EEPTs have not provided enough information to construct the generic magnitude formulas for other EIDIP effects.

Because the EIDIP effects are perturbative with few variables, the generic formulas of the EIDIP effects can provide insights into the seemingly unrelated (e.g., cE- and xE- domains) physical phenomena and make the cross-pollination of their accumulated knowledge possible. Hence, researching these generic formulas can be fertile grounds for future discoveries.

E.g., the PSAA and SF EEPTs have revealed that both phenomena are produced by the angular EIDIP effect, and the ISOMF hypothesis posits that they should have an isomorphic magnitude formula (equation (81)). Assuming the PSAA data are more accurate than the SF data,¹⁶⁷ there could be a missing $1_{Dc2.5}$ term in the SF magnitude formula. However, adding the $1_{Dc2.5}$ term into the SF formula would reduce the conformal region SF's strength by 16 orders of magnitude ($1_{Dc2.5} \approx 3.27 \times 10^{-16}$). Such a large OEIA adjustment is too large to be inarguable; further research is required to find the generic angular EIDIP effect magnitude formula.

11 EIDIP framework possesses major scientific method precepts and has high statistical confidence

Theoretical frameworks cannot be proven but can be judged through these scientific method precepts: verifiability, predictability, falsifiability, fairness, accuracy, consistency, scope, simplicity, progressiveness, utility, and expediency. The EIDIP framework possesses these precepts (section X.A).

- (1) Simplicity: EIDIP effects have plain equations; the MWEP to the EIDIP mathematical derivation reveals a parent-child relationship between gravity and other fundamental-or-not or anomalous forces;
- (2) Verifiability: all 10+ EEPTs were based on and can be verified by the publicly available data;

- (3) Predictability, falsifiability: EIDIP framework has a long list of falsifiable predictions and implications (section X.C and X.D);
- (4) Falsifiability: the EIDIP effects are fundamentally falsifiable because they have the multi-singularities signatures inherited from the quantized-singularity of the underlying MWEs (e.g., section X.C.3);
- (5) Fairness, scope: those physical phenomena involved in the 10+ EEPTs cover a wide range of physical phenomena, from subatomic to interstellar and anomalous-or-not; i.e., the EIDIP framework is capable of finding the underlying EIDIP effects connections between anomalous-or-not physical phenomena;
- (6) Accuracy, simplicity: the EIDIP based ENBE-SEF is more accurate than the liquid-drop based Bethe-Weizsäcker NBE-SEF formula (section V.A.3); the heavy nuclei EPNCR-SEF produced NCRs were comparable to, if not more accurate than, the NCRs produced by the SWNCR-SEF of [11] (V.B.2); the light nuclei EPNCR-SEFs produced NCRs matched the recommended values of the CODATA and ADND13 and other empirical measurements (section V.C); the astronomical angular EIDIP effect traced the Pioneer spacecraft 10/11's steep ascending and slow descending anomalous sunward acceleration;
- (7) Consistency, utility, simplicity: the 10+ EEPTs have shown that the EIDIP effects can consistently describe the behaviors of a wide range of physical phenomena currently described by disparate models beyond the Newtonian limit. The EIDIP effects based EPNCR-SEF, which was originally constructed based on an older 2003 empirical NCR dataset, has sustained its accuracy against a newer ADND13 dataset (section V.B.2).
- (8) Progressiveness, scope, simplicity: The non-perturbative EIDIP framework can gain insights from the 10+ three-variable EEPTs that perturbative or high variable count models cannot; the gained insights have provided coherent first-order rationales for additional non-classical physical phenomena beyond the Newtonian limit (section X.D); i.e., the falsifiable EIDIP framework is capable of finding the patterns underlying these anomalous or nonclassical phenomena;²¹⁷
- (9) Expediency, utility, simplicity: EIDIP effects can unify gravity with other fundamental-or-not and anomalous forces, and these effective couplings: ESC, ERC, EMC, and EEC, and these physical constants: Coulomb's constant, elementary charge, the fine structure constant, and Planck constant (section VIII.E).

Furthermore, without taking the additional 20+

²¹⁷ A concept may be embraced even without falsifiability, if it is capable of finding elegance of pattern among anomalous observations [27].

secondary NHTNs into consideration, nulling the EIDIP (does exist) already has a 5+ sigma statistical significance level based on the 35+ primary NHTNs alone, and the significance level computation avoids the selective-sampling and compound-statistic pitfalls (section X.B).

The EIDIP framework is built on the EIDIP effects and their feasibility. The facts that nulling the EIDIP's existence has a 5+ sigma statistical significance level, and the EIDIP effects can describe a wide range of physical phenomena and provide coherent rationales for those beyond the Newtonian limit, taken together, they suggest that the nascent EIDIP framework has high statistical confidence and deserves to be developed further.

12 EIDIP framework can be the cornerstone of the Theory of Everything

The 10+ three-variable EEPTs have shown that the EIDIP effects can describe fundamental-or-not and anomalous forces and reduce a wide range of physical phenomena to more basic EIDIP effects without resorting to non-relativistic or relativistic form factors. They also have shown that the EIDIP framework does not contradict and can unify these disparate physics models such that the accumulated knowledge of which can accelerate the future developments of the EIDIP framework.

The mathematical derivation of the EIDIP function reveals the *parent-child* relationship between gravity and other fundamental-or-not forces; such a relationship is the main reason why the conventional peer-to-peer approaches have trouble in unifying gravity with other fundamental forces.

Because the nonperturbative EIDIP effects functions are single shaping-parameter nonlinear functions of distance, they have rigid shapes; hence, the EIDIP framework can gain insights from the 10+ EEPT that perturbative and high variable counts methods cannot, and provide coherent rationales for the physical phenomena beyond the Newtonian limit (section X.D).

The EIDIP framework not only possesses these major scientific method precepts: verifiability, predictability, falsifiability, and fairness, it is also simpler, more elegant, and more feasible than conventional models (section X.A). Under the principle of Occam's razor, among competing hypotheses that predict equally well, the simplest one with the fewest assumptions and variables should be selected [39]. With the intuitive simplicity and unifying capabilities of the nascent EIDIP framework has already shown, taken together, they have suggested that the EIDIP framework can be the cornerstone of the Theory of Everything and is worthy of further developments.

13 Future EIDIP framework developments

The 10+ EEPTs have shown that the EIDIP framework can reduce a wide range of physical phenomena currently

described by disparate conventional models to more basic terms and reveal the underlying EIDIP effects connections; and that the EIDIP framework does not contradict the observed physical phenomena's behaviors described by, and can unify, the currently disparate physics models. Even with the EIDIP framework's capability has shown, it is still in nascent development stage compared with the mature conventional models. However, the accumulated knowledge of the disparate conventional models can accelerate the EIDIP framework's future developments, and the high statistical confidence of the EIDIP framework does give support for its future developments.

Apart from various proposals for future EIDIP framework developments throughout this paper, items listed below are also worthy of further developments:

- (1) Verify the EIDIP framework hypotheses, predictions, and implications;²¹⁸
- (2) Improve those figurative EEPTs with actual empirical datasets;
- (3) Developing generic magnitude formulas for every EIDIP effects;
- (4) Developing higher-body-count interaction EIDIPs produced by more generic MWEPs and DSIC functions that may work better for some real-world physical phenomena;
- (5) Developing more generic dual-sphere interaction coupling (DSIC) function of the generic EIDIP functions;
- (6) Merge the EIDIP framework and disparate conventional models to form the Theory of Everything.

B. Conclusion

In this paper, I have shown through the 10+ three variables EEPTs that the gradational interaction produced EIDIP effects can unify gravity with other forces including those thought to be fundamental or anomalous and describe a wide range of anomalous-or-not physical phenomena beyond the Newtonian limit.

I have also shown that the non-perturbative EIDIP framework can gain insights from the 10+ three-variable EEPTs that perturbative or high variable count models cannot. The gained insights have provided coherent first-order rationales for additional non-classical physical phenomena beyond the Newtonian limit.

I have shown through the statistical NHTN method that nulling the EIDIP's existence has a 5+ sigma statistical significance level and that the EIDIP framework possesses these major scientific method precepts and is also simpler, more elegant, and more feasible than conventional models.

I have shown that the EIDIP framework can describe the physical phenomena's behaviors described by the disparate conventional physics models and reduce those physical phenomena to more basic EIDIP effects. That the

accumulated knowledge of the disparate conventional models has assisted the nascent EIDIP framework's development suggests the accumulated knowledge can accelerate the future EIDIP framework's developments.

With the EIDIP framework's high statistical confidence, intuitive simplicity, unifying capabilities, and plain EIDIP effects equations presented in this paper, taken together, they have suggested that the EIDIP can be the cornerstone of the Theory of Everything and the EIDIP framework is worthy of further developments.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

Many people were involved in the preparation of this manuscript, whether for encouraging, discussing, or proof-reading: Keith Woodall, Judith Payne, Randy Presuhn, Dona Sauerburger, Michael Polignano, and Neir Eshel, to name a few. In particular, I would like to thank:

- Jean-Robert Bayard, Ph.D. for her inspiration, discussion, and advice;
- Dr. Dong-Min Chen for his inspiration, advice, and encouragement at the beginning.

REFERENCES

- [1] en.wikipedia.org, "Theory of everything," [Online]. Available: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Theory_of_everything. [Accessed 19 01 2017].
- [2] NIST.gov, "Newtonian constant of gravitation G (2014 CODATA recommended values)," CODATA, 2014. [Online]. Available: <http://physics.nist.gov/cgi-bin/cuu/Value?bg>. [Accessed 22 11 2016].
- [3] en.wikipedia.org, "Nyquist–Shannon sampling theorem," [Online]. Available: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Nyquist%E2%80%93Shannon_sampling_theorem. [Accessed 24 8 2016].
- [4] G. Wolberg, "Sampling, Reconstruction, and Antialiasing," [Online]. Available: <http://www-cs.cny.cuny.edu/~wolberg/pub/crc04.pdf>. [Accessed 24 8 2016].
- [5] B. M. Tissue, "Fourier-Transform (FT)," 2000. [Online]. Available: <http://www.tissuegroup.chem.vt.edu/chem-ed/data/fourier.html>. [Accessed 3 5 2017].
- [6] S. Carlip, "Aberration and the Speed of Gravity," 29 9 1999. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/gr-qc/9909087>. [Accessed 15 11 2017].
- [7] M. Y. Hwang, "EIDIP nuclear binding energy model with AME2012 update: An E-space Inter-Domain Interaction potential application model," 3

²¹⁸ E.g., those falsifiable predictions and implications discussed in section X.C and the coherent first-order rationales for the beyond-the-Newtonian-limit physical phenomena discussed in section X.D.

- 4 2014. [Online]. Available: https://www.academia.edu/33596773/EIDIP_NUCLEAR_BINDING_ENERGY_MODEL_EIDIP_nuclear_binding_energy_model_with_AME2012_update_An_E-space_Interaction_potential_application_model.
- [8] A. Collaboration, "Observation of a new particle in the search for the Standard Model Higgs boson with the ATLAS detector at the LHC," 31 7 2012. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1207.7214>. [Accessed 1 9 2012].
- [9] C. Collaboration, "Observation of a new boson at a mass of 125 GeV with the CMS experiment at the LHC," 31 7 2012. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1207.7235>. [Accessed 1 9 2012].
- [10] I. Angelia and K. Marinova, "Table of experimental nuclear ground state charge radii: An update," *Atomic Data and Nuclear Data Tables*, vol. 99, no. 1, p. Pages 69–95, January 2013.
- [11] N. Wang and T. Li, "Shell and isospin effects in nuclear charge radii," *PHYSICAL REVIEW C* 88, 011301(R), vol. 88, no. 1, 17 July 2013.
- [12] Peter et al, "Direct measurement of interatomic force gradients using an ultra-low-amplitude atomic force microscope," 2001. [Online]. Available: <http://citeseerx.ist.psu.edu/viewdoc/download;jsessionid=46443C97C6194A454BA71CA4D9C2108F?doi=10.1.1.487.4270&rep=rep1&type=pdf>. [Accessed 1 10 2012].
- [13] S. Aoki, T. Hatsuda and N. Ishii, "Nuclear Force from Monte Carlo Simulations of Lattice Quantum Chromodynamics," 24 10 2008. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/pdf/0805.2462v2.pdf>. [Accessed 18 10 2012].
- [14] o. c. Fritsch, "Behaviour of the strong force," 2011. [Online]. Available: http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Strong_interaction. [Accessed 7 2011].
- [15] en.wikipedia.org, "Bohr radius," [Online]. Available: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Bohr_radius. [Accessed 3 8 2016].
- [16] physics.nist.gov, "Fundamental Physical Constants: Bohr Radius," NIST, [Online]. Available: <http://physics.nist.gov/cgi-bin/cuu/Value?bohrada0>. [Accessed 3 8 2016].
- [17] Slava el al., "Support for the thermal origin of the Pioneer anomaly," 11 Apr 2012. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/abs/1204.2507>.
- [18] en.wikipedia.org, "Solar mass," [Online]. Available: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Solar_mass#cite_note-2. [Accessed 5 10 2016].
- [19] M. M. Nieto and J. D. Anderson, "Using Early Data to Illuminate the Pioneer Anomaly," 4 10 2005. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/pdf/gr-qc/0507052v2.pdf>.
- [20] DOE/NSF Nuclear Science Advisory Committee, "The Frontiers of Nuclear Science A long range plan: The Spatial Structure of Protons and Neutrons," 12 2007. [Online]. Available: <http://arxiv.org/ftp/arxiv/papers/0809/0809.3137.pdf>. [Accessed 3 4 2013].
- [21] A. Deur, "Spin sum rules and the strong coupling constant at large distances," Thomas Jefferson National Accelerator Facility, March 2009. [Online]. Available: http://www.jlab.org/conferences/spin_structure09/talks/Friday/deur.pdf. [Accessed 15 10 2012].
- [22] N. Strobel, "Deriving the Galactic Mass from the Rotation Curve," Bakersfield College , 9 May 2013. [Online]. Available: <http://www.astronomynotes.com/ismnotes/s7.htm>. [Accessed 20 4 2017].
- [23] Y. Sofue, "A Grand Rotation Curve and Dark Matter Halo in the Milky Way Galaxy," 25 8 2012. [Online]. Available: www.iaa.su-tokyo.ac.jp/~sofue/papers/rc/2012-pasj-GrandRC.pdf. [Accessed 12 4 2017].
- [24] astro.caltech, "Formation of Galaxy Spheroids and Dynamics of Stellar Populations; History and Formation of Our Galaxy:," 2004. [Online]. Available: <http://www.astro.caltech.edu/~george/ay20/Ay20-Lec17x.pdf>. [Accessed 1 4 2013].
- [25] Centre de Données astronomiques de Strasbourg astronomical Data Center Breddels+, "J/A+A/511/A90 RAVE DR2 distance catalogue," 2010. [Online]. Available: <http://vizier.cfa.harvard.edu/viz-bin/VizieR?-source=J/A%2BA/511/A90>. [Accessed 7 8 2012].
- [26] R. B. a. F. COMBES, "Galactic Rings," *Fund. Cosmic Physics*, vol. 17, pp. 95-281, 20 7 1996.
- [27] R. D. Jarrard, "Chapter 7: Evidence Evaluation and Scientific Progress," Dept. of Geology and Geophysics, University of Utah, 2001. [Online]. Available: <http://www.emotionalcompetency.com/sci/sm7.htm>. [Accessed 07 10 2018].
- [28] en.wikipedia.org, "Gravitoelectromagnetism," en.wikipedia.org, 20 10 2018. [Online]. Available: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Gravitoelectromagnetism>. [Accessed 25 10 2018].
- [29] wikipedia, "Interference of individual particles," [Online]. Available: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Double-slit_experiment. [Accessed 31 7 2015].
- [30] en.wikipedia.org, "Jet (particle physics)," 6 2 2017. [Online]. Available: [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Jet_\(particle_physics\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Jet_(particle_physics)). [Accessed 1 6 2017].

- [31] M. Guidry, "Chapter 30 Newtonian Gravity and Cosmology," Physics dept, University of Tennessee, Knoxville, 16 8 2013. [Online]. Available: http://eagle.phys.utk.edu/guidry/astro616/lectures/lecture_ch30.pdf. [Accessed 27 7 2017].
- [32] en.wikipedia.org, "Generation (particle physics)," en.wikipedia.org, [Online]. Available: [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Generation_\(particle_physics\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Generation_(particle_physics)). [Accessed 29 8 2018].
- [33] en.wikipedia.org, "Neutron electric dipole moment," [Online]. Available: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Neutron_electric_dipole_moment. [Accessed 4 4 2018].
- [34] en.wikipedia.org, "Proton spin crisis," [Online]. Available: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Proton_spin_crisis. [Accessed 4 4 2018].
- [35] J. P. S. P. A. M. S. R. S. S. I. S. O. G. T. L. T. B. B. R. M. S. E. L. Kaonan Micadei, "Reversing the thermodynamic arrow of time using quantum correlations," 9 Nov 2017. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1711.03323>. [Accessed 9 1 2018].
- [36] Abbott et al, "Observation of Gravitational Waves from a Binary Black Hole Merger," LIGO Scientific Collaboration and Virg, 11 2 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://physics.aps.org/featured-article-pdf/10.1103/PhysRevLett.116.061102>. [Accessed 12 2 2016].
- [37] D. A. Bruce, "Can an "amateur" today make useful contributions to theoretical physics or mathematics?," 15 5 2014. [Online]. Available: <http://blogs.scienceforums.net/ajb/2010/06/28/can-an-amateur-today-make-useful-contributions-to-theoretical-physics-or-mathematics/>. [Accessed 1 3 2017].
- [38] en.wikipedia.org, "Uncertainty principle," 16 6 2017. [Online]. Available: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Uncertainty_principle. [Accessed 21 6 2017].
- [39] en.wikipedia.org, "Principle of Occam's razor," [Online]. Available: http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Occam%27s_razor. [Accessed 9 10 2014].
- [40] en.wikipedia.org, "Neutrino," [Online]. Available: <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Neutrino>. [Accessed 13 3 2017].
- [41] M. Y. Hwang, "EIDIP NSPR Semi-Empirical Nuclear Charge Radii Formula: An E-space Inter-Domain Interaction potential (EIDIP) application model," 5 11 2013. [Online]. Available: https://www.academia.edu/4998823/EIDIP_NSPR_Semi-Empirical_Nuclear_Charge_Radii_Formula.
- [42] LIGO open science center, "Data release for event GW150914," LIGO, 11 Feb. 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://lsc.ligo.org/events/GW150914/>. [Accessed 29 2 2016].
- [43] PennState Eberly College of science, "Hypothesis Testing," PennState, [Online]. Available: <https://onlinecourses.science.psu.edu/statprogram/node/136>. [Accessed 7 2 2017].
- [44] Elisabete M. de Gouveia Dal Pino, "ASTROPHYSICAL JETS AND OUTFLOWS," 2004. [Online]. Available: cds.cern.ch/record/741932/files/0406319.pdf. [Accessed 8 6 2017].
- [45] en.wikipedia.org, "Beta decay," [Online]. Available: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Beta_decay. [Accessed 13 12 2017].
- [46] en.wikipedia.org, "Double-slit experiment: Interference of individual particles," [Online]. Available: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Double-slit_experiment. [Accessed 31 7 2015].
- [47] en.wikipedia.org, "Flyby anomaly," [Online]. Available: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Flyby_anomaly. [Accessed 4 12 2017].
- [48] en.wikipedia.org, "Log-log plot," [Online]. Available: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Log%E2%80%93log_plot. [Accessed 29 7 2016].
- [49] en.wikipedia.org, "Milky Way," [Online]. Available: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Milky_Way. [Accessed 15 10 2016].
- [50] P. Mohr, B. Taylor and D. Newell, "CODATA recommended values of the fundamental physical constants: 2006," *Rev. Mod. Phys.*, vol. 80, no. Rev. Mod. Phys. 80, 633, p. 633., (2008).
- [51] Bernauer et al, "High-precision determination of the electric and magnetic form factors of the proton," 13 12 2010. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/1007.5076>. [Accessed 9 4 2013].
- [52] M. Y. Hwang, "EIDI model simulation vs empirical data figures," 26 9 2011. [Online]. Available: https://www.academia.edu/891656/EIDI_model_simulation_vs_empirical_data_figures.
- [53] "APS 2014-April meeting SlideDoc-Can an E-space Inter-Domain Interaction potential (EIDIP) be the missing block of the Unified theory," 4 2014. [Online]. Available: https://www.academia.edu/6643995/APS_2014-April_meeting_SlideDoc-Can_an_E-space_Inter-Domain_Interaction_potential_EIDIP_be_the_missing_block_of_the_Unified_theory.
- [54] "APS 2014-April meeting poster-Can an E-space Inter-Domain Interaction potential (EIDIP) be the missing block of the Unified theory," 4 2014. [Online]. Available:

https://www.academia.edu/6603022/APS_2014-April_meeting_poster-Can_an_E-space_Inter-Domain_Interaction_potential_EIDIP_be_the_missing_block_of_the_Unified_theory.

- [55] courses.lumenlearning.com, "The Scientific Method," courses.lumenlearning.com, [Online]. Available:
<https://courses.lumenlearning.com/boundless-psychology/chapter/the-scientific-method/>. [Accessed 17 9 2016].
- [56] M. Y. Hwang, "The EIDI nuclear binding energy model," 12 12 2012. [Online]. Available:
https://www.academia.edu/892093/The_EIDI_Nuclear_Binding_Energy_Model.

APPENDIX

I. ABBREVIATION TABLES

This section contains three abbreviation tables: general, EEPTs, and hypotheses.

TABLE IX. General abbreviation table.

Abbrev.	Remark
ADND13	The 2013 Atomic Data and Nuclear Data;
AEAAN	Angular EIDIP axis-asymmetric nudging (effect);
AEG	Angular EIDIP-gradient (effect);
AIRT	Angular isotropic residual tension;
AMDC	The Atomic Mass Data Center;
AME2012	The 2012 Atomic Mass Evaluation table, AME2012e: AME2012 with experimental values;
APA	Angular EIDIP induced acceleration, APC: APA coupling;
ATLAS	ATLAS is one of two general-purpose detectors at the Large Hadron Collider (LHC);
BFA	Beat frequency amplitude (of gravity waves);
CDEEC	Case dependent EIDIP effect curve;
CMS	The Compact Muon Solenoid (CMS) is a general-purpose detector at the Large Hadron Collider (LHC);
CODATA	Committee on Data of the International Council for Science;
DBS	BFA sweep;
DSIC	Dual-sphere interaction coupling, aka ZAIC: Z-axis interaction coupling;
DSU	E-domain spatial unit;
ECTRT	E-space contractive transformation residual tension (unit: ℓ/s^2), EXTRTS: EXTRT tensile stress (unit: $1/(\ell s^2)$), ECTRTI: ECTRTS intensity per unit area (unit: ℓ/s^2); ECTRTG: ECTRT radial gradient intensity, ECTRTGI: ECTRTG per unit area;
EDM	Electric dipole moment;
EEPT	EIDIP effects phenomenological test, aka EDPF: EIDIP and derived effects phenomenological fit;
EIDIP	E-space Inter-Domain Interaction Potential, aka IDGIP: inter-domain gravitational interaction potential or WEIDIP: warped E-space inter-domain interaction potential;
EM	Electromagnetic;
ESCX	Isotropic E-space membrane contractive and expansive (transformation);
EXTRT	E-space expansive transformation residual tension (unit: ℓ/s^2), EXTRTI: EXTRTS intensity per unit area (unit: ℓ/s^2),

	EXTRTS: EXTRT tensile stress (unit: $1/(\ell s^2)$), EXTRTG: EXTRT radial gradient intensity, EXTRTGI: EXTRTG per unit area;
GC	Galactic center;
GFR	Gravitational force ripple;
GMP	Galactic midplane;
GP	Galactic plane;
GR	General relativity;
GW	Gravity waves;
HMR	HMR-system: a high mass ratio interaction system;
IDF	Inverse distance function of which the value is inversely proportional to the inter-object distance;
IDS	Inverse distance square;
IDTC	Inter-domain transfer coupling, aka T_c ;
IELT	Isotropic E-space linear tension, IELTS: IELT tensile stress, IELE: Isotropic E-space linear energy;
IEM	Isotropic E-space membrane, IEMT: IEM tension, IEME: IEM energy;
IER	E-space's innate energy resolution;
IMOI	Interaction moments of inertia (MOI);
LCEN	Long-range composite EIDIP effects' neutralizing (effect);
MGA	MWEP gradient induced acceleration; MGC: MGA coupling;
MW	Milky Way
MWEP	Matter Warped E-space potential, aka PCXP: post ESCX transformation residual potential;
NGF	Negative gravitational force;
NHTN	Null hypothesis testing node;
NLU	Natural length unit;
NSTEE	Near-singularity turbulent EIDIP effects;
OCF	Origin centripetal force, e.g., gravity-OCF;
OEIA	Omitting EIDIP effects induced artifacts;
ORO	Inter-object orbital-radial oscillation;
PGA	EIDIP-gradient effect induced acceleration, PGC: PGA coupling;
QCD	Quantum chromodynamics;
QEGC	Quadratic EIDIP-gradient coupling (effect);
QERU	Quadratic EIDIP radial unit (effect);
QEM	QERU and mass effect;
QFT	Quantum field theory;
RAVE-DR2	CDS J/A+A/511/A90 RAVE DR2 distance catalogue [25];
RC	Rotation curves of galaxies;
RBAA	Radial bin-averaged absolute (MW stars' RC)
RCOS	Galaxy RC's GC- and reference-centric overshoots region (cross-line shaded disks, FIG. 59);
RMT	Residual membrane tension;
RQ	Radial-quadratic (galactic disk mass model);

RV	Rotational velocity;
SASCE	Second-order angular system-core-EIDIP;
SASDE	Second-order angular system-differential-EIDIP;
SCEP	System-core-EIDIP, SCEPG: SCEP gradient, ASDEP: angular SCEP;
SDEP	System-differential-EIDIP, SDEPG: SDEP gradient, ASDEP: angular SDEP;
SEF	Semi-empirical formula, ENBE-SEF: EIDIP based NBE-SEF, EPNCR-SEF: EEPT-parameters based NCR-SEF, SWNCR-SEF: Weizsacker-Skyrme mass model produced NCR-SEF of [11];
SEPC	Second-order EIDIP coupling rP_r' ;
SM	Standard model;
SMM	SMM-system: a similar mass and mobility interaction system;
SSG	spherical surface gradient (unit: ℓ), SSGS: SSG tensile stress per unit area (unit: $1/\ell$), SSGI: SSGS intensity per unit area (unit: ℓ); SSGT: SSG tension, SSGTI: SSGT intensity;
TRF	Thermal recoil forces (put forth by [17]);

TABLE X. EIDIP effects phenomenological tests (EEPTs) abbreviation table.

Abbrev.	Remark
EEC	Effective electrostatic coupling, GEC: gravitoelectric coupling;
EMC	Effective magnetic coupling, GMC: gravitomagnetic coupling;
ERC	Effective residual-strong coupling, GMC: gravitoresidualstrong coupling;
ESC	Effective strong coupling, GMC: gravitostrong coupling;
IACF	Interatomic covalent force;
MWRC	Milky Way rotation curve; RC: rotation curve; CMWRC: Circular MWRC (GMP-centric), aka the observed MWRC of [23]; LMWRC: Cylindrical MWRC (GP-centric) of RAVE-DR2 stars; SMWRC: Spherical MWRC (GC-centric) of RAVE-DR2 stars; QG-MWRC: Hybrid QERU- and gravity-OCFs produced MWRC; AG-MWRC: Hybrid AEG- and gravity-OCFs produced MWRC; PG-MWRC: Hybrid PSAA-like G_{APA} and gravity- OCFs produced MWRC; SG-MWRC: Hybrid SEPC- and gravity-OCFs produced MWRC;

²¹⁹ The AEMWEP hypothesis is aligned with the finding that the wave-particle duality phenomenon has been shown to occur with photons, electrons, atoms and even some molecules [46].

NBE	Nuclear binding energy;
NCD	Neutron charge distribution;
NCR	Nuclear charge radii;
NEFA	Near-Earth flybys' speed anomalies, NEAR: a case of near-Earth flybys;
NGCD	Newtonian gravitational constant deviation, aka GCCD: gravitational coupling constant deviation;
NNP	Neutron-neutron Potential, aka RSF: residual-strong force or nuclear force;
PCD	Proton charge distribution;
PSAA	Pioneer 10/11 spacecraft's sunward acceleration anomaly, aka SWAA: sunward acceleration anomaly
SF	Strong force;

TABLE XI. EIDIP framework hypotheses table (first section: framework hypotheses; second section: explanatory hypotheses)

Abbrev.	Remark
E-space	Energy space hypothesis: vacuum contains an isotropic E-space linear tension $R_0 \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} 1/(32\pi c)$ that is related to the speed of light;
ESCX	An E-space membrane can be transformed into the matter through a contractive and expansive (stretch) transformation MWEP transformation, aka MWEP transformation;
ISOMF	Isomorphic magnitude formulas of the same EIDIP effects between different E-domains;
MEP	Multiple E-domain pair hypothesis: E-domains exist in pairs with complementary DSUs;
MCGC	MGA coupling as the gravitational constant hypothesis: the Newtonian gravitational potential is a Dc0-domain MWEP; it has a quantized singularity and a $[2R_0]_{m^3/s^2}$ coupling constant;
AEMWEP	All energy entities (matter, elementary particles, photon, etc.) possess the MWEP regardless of their size; the E-fermion core behaves like a particle, and the E-boson field behaves like a wave; i.e., all energy entities possess the wave-particle duality; ²¹⁹
AXGL	Astronomical range attractive and expulsive EIDIP effects induced attractive and <i>expulsive</i> gravitational lensing.
EPG	Different elementary particle generation operates in different E-domains;
LBID	Lower bound internucleon or inter-elementary-particle distance $R_u = 1/c^2$; ⁸²
OEIA	Omitting the EIDIP effects induced artifacts;
OSPDMO	OSPD: Object- and systemic-EIDIPs preferred inter-object distance;

	OSPDMO: OSPD misalignment induces inter-object oscillations;
SCXEE	Symmetrical cE- and xE- domains EIDIP effects;
SSFR	Nuclei form additional sub-shell about every 100 mass-number; NCR needs a sub-shell formation radius (SSFR) adjustment $3R_u$ for each subshell;
UCMM	Universe comprises multiple subgroups, each possesses its MWEP-like energy structure;

II. MWEP EQUATION DERIVATIONS

The EIDIP framework posits that an isotropic E-space contains energy in a tension-equilibrium state. Because the E-space energy density decreases when stretched and increases when compressed, the E-space tensile stress also changes. Note that stretching (or compressing) in the orthogonal direction also decreases (or increases) the in-direction energy density and tensile stress.

I.e., if a square isotropic E-space is stretched and compressed with the same factor orthogonally, the at-point intensity (with unit area shrunk to a point) of the EXTRT (EXTRTI) and ECTRT (ECTRTI) remains the same (TABLE XII) as depicted in FIG. 76 (a) to (c) for the explanatory steps (not an actual sequence).

With that and equation (5), we can derive the post-ESCX transformation radial EXTRTI and ortho-radial ECTRTI, both scaled with the spherical surface area, are $[2]_{\ell/s^2} [4\pi 2^2]_{\ell^2} / [4\pi r^2]_{\ell^2} = [2 \times (2/r)^2]_{\ell/s^2}$ at the radius r ; and the ECTRT radial gradient intensity (ECTRTGI) is $[2 \times d(2/r)^2/dr]_{\ell/s^2} = [-2 \times (2/r)^3]_{\ell/s^2}$ (TABLE XIII).²²⁰

Note that the post-ESCX transformation MWEP spherical energy structure also possesses a radial spherical surface gradient (SSG) induced tension intensity (SSGTI) comprising the radial ambient IELE $[1]_{\ell^2/s^2}$ and the SSG intensity (SSGI) such that the SSGTI is $[2/r]_{1/\ell} [1]_{\ell^2/s^2} = [2/r]_{\ell/s^2}$ at the radius r .

With that, at the radius $[2]_{\ell}$, the radial EXTRTI, ortho-radial ECTRTI, and radial ECTRTGI have the same magnitude, twice the radial SSGTI's magnitude (TABLE XIII). I.e., all three post-ESCX residual tension intensities are in equilibrium and harmonize with the SSGTI at the radius $[2]_{\ell}$, the cE-fermion shell radius, where some of the post-ESCX transformation energy accumulates to form matter.

Note that the factor of two in TABLE XIII can be normalized to one by reducing the vertical segment length of FIG. 76 (a)-(c) by one half. With that, some of the post-ESCX transformation energy induced radial EXTRTI, ortho-radial ECTRTI, and radial SSGTI are in equilibrium at the cE-fermion shell radius $[2]_{\ell}$ (aka cE-wavelength)

(TABLE I).

Moreover, the magnitudes of these normalized ECTRTI, EXTRTI, and EXTRTGI are power functions of SSGTI. If we define a new NLU ℓ_x such that $[2]_{\ell_x} = [cH_0]_{\ell}$, aka the xE-fermion radius or xE-wavelength, the fourth $[cH_0]_{\ell}$ column magnitudes of TABLE XIII become the same under the new unit area ($[1^2]_{\ell_x^2} = [(cH_0)^2]_{\ell^2}$); i.e., some of the post-ESCX transformation energy induced radial EXTRTI, ortho-radial ECTRTI, and radial SSGTI are also in equilibrium state per ℓ_x^2 area at the xE-fermion radius (TABLE I).

TABLE XII. vertical and horizontal ECTRT, EXTRT, ECTRTI, and EXTRTI of FIG. 76(a)-(c) table.

Radius	FIG. 76 (a)	FIG. 76 (b)	FIG. 76 (c)
Vert. T.	$[H_0]_{\ell/s^2}$	$[H_0]_{\ell/s^2}$	$[cH_0]_{\ell/s^2}$
Hori. T.	$[H_0]_{\ell/s^2}$	$[H_0/c]_{\ell/s^2}$	$[H_0/c]_{\ell/s^2}$
Vert. TI.	$[1]_{\ell/s^2}$	$[1/c]_{\ell/s^2}$	$[1]_{\ell/s^2}$
Hori. TI.	$[1]_{\ell/s^2}$	$[1/c]_{\ell/s^2}$	$[1]_{\ell/s^2}$

TABLE XIII. Post-ESCX transformation SSGTI, ECTRTI, EXTRTI, and ECTRTGI of FIG. 76 (d) table.²²⁰

Radius	$[r]_{\ell}$	$[2]_{\ell}$	$[cH_0]_{\ell}$
SSGTI	$[2/r]_{\ell/s^2}$	$[1]_{\ell/s^2}$	$[2/(cH_0)]_{\ell/s^2}$
ECTRTI	$[2(2/r)^2]_{\ell/s^2}$	$[2]_{\ell/s^2}$	$[2^3/(cH_0)^2]_{\ell/s^2}$
EXTRTI	$[2(2/r)^2]_{\ell/s^2}$	$[2]_{\ell/s^2}$	$[2^3/(cH_0)^2]_{\ell/s^2}$
ECTRTGI	$[2(2/r)^3]_{\ell/s^2}$	$[2]_{\ell/s^2}$	$[2^4/(cH_0)^3]_{\ell/s^2}$

²²⁰ The $2 \times$ factor of the $2 \times (2/r)^2$ for EXTRTI and EXTRTI, and ECTRTGI reflects the ratio between the vertical segment length $[cH_0]_{\ell} = [32\pi]_{\ell}$ of FIG. 76 (c) and the spherical surface gradient at the radius $[2]_{\ell}$, $[8\pi 2]_{\ell} = [4\pi 2^2]_{\ell^2} [1]_{1/\ell} = [16\pi]_{\ell}$, of FIG. 76 (d). Note that the

spherical surface gradient intensity function is $[8\pi r]_{\ell} / [4\pi r^2]_{\ell^2} = [2/r]_{1/\ell}$ at the radius r .

FIG. 76. (Color online) Explanatory (not actual sequence) ECTRTI and EXTRTI transformation figures: (a) $[H_0]_{\ell^2}$ of isotropic E-space worldsheet with $[1]_{\ell/s^2}$ of IELT; (b) The E-space is stretched horizontally by a factor of c to $[cH_0]_{\ell}$; the strengths of both the IELT and the EXTRTI decrease by a factor of c to $[1/c]_{\ell/s^2}$; (c) The E-space is then compressed vertically by a factor of c ($[H_0/c]_{\ell} = [32\pi]_{\ell}$); the strengths of both the EXTRTI and the ECTRTI increase by a factor of c back to $[1]_{\ell/s^2}$; (d) The E-space is then transformed into a spherical MWEP; the radial EXTRTI, ortho-radial ECTRTI, and radial ECTRTGI are in equilibrium at the cE-fermion shell radius $[2]_{\ell}$ and the xE-fermion shell radius $[2]_{\ell_x} = [cH_0]_{\ell}$.

A. Normalized MWEP equation derivation

1 Constant E-fermion potential

Because of the cE-fermion's spherical shell energy structure, the potential within the cE-fermion remains constant; i.e., there is no residual energy within the cE-fermion to raise the potential. Although there is residual energy within the xE-fermion radius, it operates in different energy resolution (E-domain) and is insensitive to the xE-fermion; hence, the potential within the xE-fermion radius remains constant. The normalized cE- and xE-

fermions have unit potentials $[1]_{\ell^2/s^2}$ and $[1]_{\ell^2/s^2}$ with ℓ and $\ell' = [cH_0/2]_{\ell}$ denote the cE- and xE-domains NLU respectively.

2 E-boson potential is an inverse distance function

The potential in the E-boson region is an inverse distance function because the EXTRT is angular isotropic. The E-boson potential is the divergence of EXTRT at the point P, i.e., $P_M^b = \nabla \cdot [8/r^2]_{\ell/s^2}^{\text{EXTRT}}$. More precisely, it can be defined as the spherical surface integral of the EXTRT of a spherical surface region S_r divided by the region area $|S_r|$ as S_r shrinks to a point p such that region area is the same as the spherical surface element $r^2 \sin \theta$. I.e., the E-boson potential is

$$\int \left\{ \lim_{S_r \rightarrow \{P\}} \iint_{S_r} \frac{[4\pi^2]_{\ell^2} [2]_{\ell/s^2}^{\text{EXTRT}}}{[4\pi r^2]_{\ell^2}} \frac{1}{|S_r|} dS_r \right\} dr, \quad (83)$$

with $dS_r = r^2 \sin \theta d\theta d\varphi$. Because of the MWEP's spherical structure, this equation can be simplified to (ignoring the sign)

$$[P_M^b]_{\ell^2/s^2} = \int \left[\frac{8}{r^2} \right]_{\ell/s^2}^{\text{EXTRT}} dr = \left[\frac{8}{r} \right]_{\ell^2/s^2}. \quad (84)$$

With that, the E-boson potential at the E-fermion border $[2]_{\ell}$ is $[4]_{\ell^2/s^2}$. Because the normalized E-fermion has a unit potential $[1]_{\ell^2/s^2}$, the normalized E-boson potential must be scaled down by a factor of four to align with the normalized E-fermion potential.²²¹ Hence, equation (84) can be rewritten for the normalized E-boson potential as

$$[P_M^b]_{\ell^2/s^2} = \frac{[2]_{\ell^3/s^2}}{[r]_{\ell}} = \left[\frac{2}{r} \right]_{\ell^2/s^2}. \quad (85)$$

Combining the E-fermion and E-boson potentials, the normalized MWEP is

$$P_M(r) = \begin{cases} \left[\frac{2}{r} \right]_{\ell^2/s^2}, & r \geq [2]_{\ell} \\ [1]_{\ell^2/s^2}, & r < [2]_{\ell} \end{cases}. \quad (86)$$

B. Inter-domain MWEP equation derivation

The matter under measurement (target) possesses MWEPs with various innate energy resolutions (IER), so do real-world apparatuses (reference). The target- and reference-IERs define the E-domains in which they operate, and their IER-ratio affects the target-MWEP measurement; this is because these E-domains have their own DSU and that the inter-domain DSU ratio, named the inter-domain transfer coupling (IDTC or T_c), can affect the measured quantiles.

²²¹ The normalizing factor can be incorporated into other physical terms, e.g., mass, in the MWEP applications. The normalizing factor of

four can be eliminated by reducing the vertical segment length of FIG. 76 (a)-(c) by a quarter such that the EXTRT formula is $2/r^2$ instead of $8/r^2$.

Because in the inter-domain measurements, both the target- and the reference-centric quantiles reference the same unit area, the MWEP equation (86) can have mixed reference- and target-centric units in the inter-domain measurements. E.g., for the reference-centric measurement, equation (85) can be rewritten with reference-NLU for the target E-boson potential as

$$[P_M^b]_{\ell_f^2}^t = \left[\frac{2}{r} \right]_{\frac{1}{\ell_f}} [1^2]_{\ell_f^2} [1]_{\frac{\ell_t}{s^2}}^{\text{EXTRT}}, \quad (87)$$

and for the reference E-boson field as

$$[P_M^b]_{\ell_f^2}^f = \left[\frac{2}{r} \right]_{\frac{1}{\ell_f}} [1^2]_{\ell_f^2} [1]_{\frac{\ell_f}{s^2}}^{\text{EXTRT}}, \quad (88)$$

both reference the same reference-centric $[2/r]_{1/\ell_f}$ SSGI function and $[1^2]_{\ell_f^2}$ unit area.

By the IDTC definition $[1]_{\ell_t} \equiv [T_c]_{\ell_f}$, the target-centric EXTRT of equation (87) in reference-NLU is $[1]_{\ell_t/s^2} = [T_c]_{\ell_f/s^2}$.²²² Therefore, the MWEP equation (86) can be rewritten for the reference-centric target-MWEP as

$$P_M^t(r) = \begin{cases} \left[\frac{2}{r} \right]_{\ell_f} [T_c]_{\frac{\ell_f}{s^2}}^{\text{EXTRT}}, & r \geq [2T_c]_{\ell_f} \\ [1]_{\ell_f} [T_c]_{\frac{\ell_f}{s^2}}^{\text{EXTRT}}, & r < [2T_c]_{\ell_f} \end{cases}; \quad (89)$$

which can be simplified to

$$P_M^t(r) = \begin{cases} \left[\frac{2T_c}{r} \right]_{\frac{\ell_f^2}{s^2}}, & r \geq [2T_c]_{\ell_f} \\ [T_c]_{\frac{\ell_f^2}{s^2}}, & r < [2T_c]_{\ell_f} \end{cases}; \quad (90)$$

whereas for the reference-MWEP is

$$P_M^f(r) = \begin{cases} \left[\frac{2}{r} \right]_{\frac{\ell_f^2}{s^2}}, & r \geq [2]_{\ell_f} \\ [1]_{\frac{\ell_f^2}{s^2}}, & r < [2]_{\ell_f} \end{cases}. \quad (91)$$

Note that the reference-centric target-MWEP has a strange magnitude-discontinuity singularity at the target E-fermion border $[2]_{\ell_t} = [2T_c]_{\ell_f}$ whereas the reference-MWEP exhibits no magnitude-discontinuity at the singularity.

²²² Note that the target- to the reference-centric unit conversion factor T_c is applicable to the at-point operation “the region area $|S_r|$ as S_r shrinks to a point P” of equation (83).

C. Gravitational potential comprises multiple orders of cE- and xE-MWEPs

1 Paired cE- and xE-bosons have same effective couplings

Using the cE-domain NLU as the reference NLU $\ell_f = \ell_c$ and the xE-domain NLU as the target NLU $\ell_t = \ell_x$, the normalized E-boson formula $[2/r]_{\ell^2/s^2}$ (equation (85)) can be rewritten to reference the same unit area $[1^2]_{\ell_f^2}$ for the cE- and xE-bosons as

$$P_M^c(r) = \frac{[2]_{\ell_f/s^2} [1^2]_{\ell_f^2}}{[r]_{\ell_f}}, \quad (92)$$

$$P_M^x(r) = \frac{[2]_{\ell_t/s^2} [1^2]_{\ell_t^2}}{[r]_{\ell_t}}.$$

With the IDTC effect $[1]_{\ell_t} \equiv [T_c]_{\ell_f}$, equation (92) can be rewritten to show that the cE- and xE-bosons have the same effective formula.

$$P_M^x(r) = \frac{[2T_c]_{\ell_f/s^2} [1^2]_{\ell_f^2}}{[rT_c]_{\ell_f}} = \left[\frac{2}{r} \right]_{\frac{\ell_f^2}{s^2}} = P_M^c(r). \quad (93)$$

Note that, although the cE- and xE-bosons operate with complementary energy resolutions, they have the same coupling magnitude per reference-NLU square area; i.e., they have the same effective coupling.

2 Various orders E-bosons have same effective couplings

Using the zero-order cE-domain NLU as the reference NLU $\ell_f = \ell_{DC0}$ and the high-order cE-domain NLU as the target NLU $\ell_t = \ell_{DC\#}$, the *normalized* equation (93) can be rewritten to show that the *normalized* zero- and high-order E-bosons have the same effective formula.

$$P_M^\#(r) = \frac{[2T_c]_{\ell_f/s^2} [1^2]_{\ell_f^2}}{[rT_c]_{\ell_f}} = \left[\frac{2}{r} \right]_{\frac{\ell_f^2}{s^2}} = P_M^0(r). \quad (94)$$

Note that, although the zero- and high-order MWEPs operate with different energy resolutions, they have the same E-boson coupling magnitude per reference-NLU square area; i.e., they have the same effective E-boson coupling.

3 Alternative gravitational potential derivation

A way to derive the gravitational potential is from a volume angle point of view. As to the sound pressure is a

local pressure deviation from the ambient, the tension difference between the angular isotropic residual tensions (AIRT) flux and ambient isotropic E-space tension appears as the E-boson potential.

From a volume angle point of view, the AIRTs are constant whereas the ambient isotropic E-space tension is not; and it is the pressure between the radial ambient isotropic E-space linear tension (IELT) per unit area $[1^2]_{\ell^2} [1]_{\ell/s^2}^{\text{IELT}}$ and the radial spherical surface gradient intensity (SSGI) $[8\pi r/4\pi r^2]_{1/\ell} = [2/r]_{1/\ell}$ that produces gravitational potential. I.e., with the zero-order NLU $\ell = [R_0]_m$, the zero-order E-boson potential, aka gravitational potential, is

$$[P_M^b]_{m^2} = \left[\frac{2}{r} \right]_{\frac{1}{m}} [1^2]_{m^2} [R_0]_{\frac{m}{s^2}} = \left[\frac{2R_0}{r} \right]_{\frac{m^2}{s^2}}. \quad (95)$$

III. IDTC AFFECT NEUTRON ELECTRIC DIPOLE MOMENT AND PROTON SPIN MEASUREMENTS

In the EIDIP framework, protons' spins and neutrons' EDMs are produced by the *rotational* ESC and *irrotational* ERC effects respectively in the Dc2.5-domain NSTEE region; whereas the EM models and methods behind the neutron EDM and proton spin direction measurements are constructed from the long-range conformal behaviors of the EIDIP effects.

Because of the IDTC (T_c) effects revealed in the magnitude formula of the EEC and EMC EEPTs, in order to describe the neutron-EDM and the proton spin phenomena more accurately, conventional models need to lower their expected values; i.e., these high-order E-domain phenomena are much weaker than conventional models have expected. The IDTC effect can provide additional rationales for the proton spin crisis and the neutron EDM problem.

The IDTC between the Dc2.5- and Dc0-domains can make Dc2.5-phenomena almost undetectable by Dc0-domain measurement methods. E.g., the distance d_n between the maximum and minimum value positions of the $P_E P_d$ -NCD curve is approximately $d_n = [1.5804]_{Dc2.5} = [0.5175]_{fm}$ (FIG. 52). With that, the effective neutron-EDM is $[1.5804 \times e]_{e Dc2.5} = [-1.1403 \times 10^{-31}]_{e cm}$; which is five orders of magnitude lower than the current best upper limit $[3.0 \times 10^{-26}]_{e cm}$ [33]. Accounting for the IDTC of the d_n (i.e., the effective $d_n = [1.5804]_{Dc0}$ has a Dc0 DSU instead of Dc2.5 DSU),²²³ the neutron-EDM becomes $[1.5804 \times e]_{e Dc0} = [-1.1555 \times 10^{-26}]_{e cm}$; which is within the range of the current neutron-EDM upper limit.

²²³ The inter-domain transfer coupling between Dc0- and Dc2.5-domains is $T_c = Dc0/Dc2.5 = (32\pi)^{-2.5}$; hence, with that, the $d_n = [1.5804]_{Dc2.5} \times T_c = [1.5804]_{Dc0}$.

²²⁴ The probability of a nuclide decaying due to beta and other forms of decay is determined by its nuclear binding energy. The binding energies of all existing nuclides form what is called the nuclear valley of stability

IV. EIDIP EFFECTS CAN UNIFY EM AND WEAK INTERACTION WITHOUT CONTRADICTION OF ELECTROWEAK UNIFICATION

The SM posits that 1) the weak interaction involves the massive force-carrying W and Z bosons that die off as the distance between particles grows large; 2) the electrically charged W boson can change a proton into a neutron; 3) neutrino participates in the beta decay, a weak interaction phenomenon, during the proton to neutron transformation; and 4) neutrinos interact only through the subatomic weak force and gravity but do not participate in the strong interaction [40]. However, unifying the EM force and the weak force into an electroweak force requires the force-carrying boson to be massless; which contradicts the theoretical massive W boson assertion and requires the Higgs mechanism, the massive-massless boson contradiction of the conventional electroweak unification models.

Although the 10+ EEPTs presented did not cover the weak interaction directly, they have revealed that EIDIP effects can unify the EM and weak interactions without the massive-massless boson contradiction.

1 Internucleon EIDIP effects and beta decay have causal connections

The NBE EEPT has shown that beta decays and the EIDIP have a causal relationship. This is because 1) the beta decay probability of a nuclide is determined by its NBE position on the wall of the nuclear valley of stability,²²⁴ and 2) the trough of the valley (aka the line of beta stability) aligns with the internucleon EIDIP based reference NBE (BE_{REF}). The fact that the BE_{REF} -based NBE-SEF produced accurate results for all known nuclei affirms the causal relationship between the EIDIP and beta decay, a weak interaction phenomenon.

2 EIDIP effects transformation can describe weak interaction phenomena without massive-massless bosons contradiction

The quadratic $P_E P_d$ -NCD and P_E^2/r -PCD EEPTs have shown that the IMO structure transformation underlying the $d(P_E)/dr \leftrightarrow P_E/r$ transformation can describe the proton and neutron transformation, a phenomenon of weak interaction, without the short interaction range massive W and Z bosons.²²⁵ Whereas the EEC EEPT has shown that the long-range EIDIP effect can describe the EM interaction without the long interaction range massless boson. In addition, the SF and NNP EEPTs have shown that the short-range NSTEEs can describe these physical phenomena without the short interaction range massive

[45]. The line of stable nuclides down the center of the valley of stability is known as the line of beta stability.

²²⁵ I.e., the observed short-range massive W and Z bosons and small rest mass neutrino are the phenomena of the angular momentum transformations underlying the IMO structure changes.

bosons. The EMC and EEC EEPTs have shown that long-range conformal EIDIP effects can describe EM interactions.

These facts, along with the causal relationship between the EIDIP and beta decay described in the last section, suggest that short-range EIDIP effects transformations can describe the weak interactions whereas long-range EIDIP effects can describe EM interactions. I.e., they suggest that the EIDIP framework can unify the EM and weak interactions without the massive-massless boson contradiction.

3 EIDIP effects transformations resemble Neutrino's behaviors

The EIDIP effects difference between the rP'_r -NCD and $P_E P_d$ -NCD EEPTs could provide some clues for the neutrinos' behaviors: weak, short-range, and do not participate in the strong interaction.

The rP'_r -NCD curve has an obvious deviation between 0.8-2 femtometer (FIG. 51) whereas the $P_E P_d$ -NCD curve does trace the observed NCD curve (FIG. 52). The deviation of these two curves is short-range and relatively weak compared with the NCD's magnitude range; the behaviors of which concur with the weak aspect and short interaction range of subatomic neutrinos.

Note that the $rP'_r = P_d r^2 + P_r$ coupling curve comprises an irrotational residual-strong coupling $P_d r^2$ curve and a rotational effective strong coupling P_r curve. The $rP'_r \leftrightarrow P_E P_d$ deviation is not part of the effective strong coupling embedded in the rP'_r ; which concur with a neutrino's behavior that it participates in the weak interaction but not in the strong interaction.

Furthermore, because the observed neutrinos are likely to be part of the turbulent EIDIP effects in the NSTEE region $< [4]_{DSU}$, they travel at their E-domain speed limit $(32\pi)^\# c$ with $\#$ as the E-domain order number. Although the subatomic neutrinos have short interacting ranges, $[4]_{D\#} = [4R_0/(32\pi)^\#]_m$ approximately, because of the cE-domain DSU, the astronomic neutrinos have long interacting ranges, $[4]_{D\#} = [2c(32\pi)^\#]_m$ approximately, because of the astronomic xE-domain DSU.

V. RAVE-DR2 MW STARS' POSITIONS AND VELOCITIES DISTRIBUTIONS

1 Alternative SMWRC EEPTs

Note that, because of $rG_{QERU}^{MWRC} = (P_E H_{kg}^0)^2$, the EIDIP (P_E) effect portion of equation (73) can be rewritten for SMWRC as

²²⁶ $k'_M \approx 1$ for $k_E \gg 1$.
²²⁷ $M_{kg}^{RL} = M_{kg}^{ISO} (4_{Dx5}/8_{kpc}) (r/8_{kpc}) \cong (M_{kg}^{ISO}/40) (r/8_{kpc})$. For galaxies with spiral arms structures, the stars' distribution on the radial-

$$v_c^{QG} = P_E \sqrt{k'_M k_A (H_{kg}^0)^2 M_{kg}^{RQ}}. \quad (96)$$

with $k'_M = k_M k_E \cong 1/(1 + 1/k_E)$.²²⁶ Which can also be rewritten with an angular EIDIP (P_r) effect with a unit-steradian point (USP) mass model $M_{kg}^{USP} = M_{kg}^{ISO} (4_{Dx5}^2/8_{kpc}^2) \cong M_{kg}^{ISO}/40^2$,

$$v_{c(EIDIP)}^{QG} = P_r \sqrt{k'_M k_A (H_{kg}^0)^2 M_{kg}^{USP}}. \quad (97)$$

2 Alternative LMWRC EEPTs

Equation (75) can be rewritten with a second-order EIDIP coupling (SEPC) effect induced acceleration

$$G_{SEPC}^{MWRC} = -rP'_r (H_{kg}^0)^2, \quad (98)$$

with a radial-linear mass model $M_{kg}^{RL} = (M_{kg}^{ISO}/40)(r/8_{kpc})$.²²⁷ I.e., the LMWRC can also be described by a hybrid SEPC and gravity OCFs produced MWRC (SG-MWRC)

$$v_c^{SG} = \sqrt{rk'_M M_{kg}^{RL} (k_E k_A G_{SEPC}^{MWRC} + \frac{g_m}{r^2})}. \quad (99)$$

With $k_x = [4]_{Dx5}$, $k_A = 5.25$,²²⁸ the $k_E = 16$ SG-MWRC traces the RBAA-CgV_o (LMWRC) (FIG. 77).

FIG. 77. RAVE-DR2 MW stars' cylindrical ortho-radial RV (color dots), RBAA-CgV_o (LMWRC, magenta line), and SG-MWRCs ($k_E = 16$: blue line, $k_E = 1$: blue dotted line) along cylindrical galactic radius figure.

The LMWRC can also be described by a PSAA-like point mass model and angular EIDIP effect induced acceleration

angle plane (similar to the FIG. 4(b)) could show part of their mass distribution are more radial-linear than radial-quadratic.

²²⁸ k_A is set to this value such that both PG-MWRCs are approximately $[200]_{km/s}$ at sun's galactic radius $[8]_{kpc}$.

$$G_{APA}^{MWRC} = -P_r H_{kg}^0 Z_{Dc2}^2. \quad (100)$$

With an effective point mass (EPM) model $M_{kg}^{EP} = M_{kg}^{ISO} \cong 1.11M_{kg}^{sta}$, the LMWRC can be described by a hybrid PSAA-like G_{APA}^{MWRC} and gravity OCFs produced MWRC (PG-MWRC)

$$v_c^{PG} = \sqrt{rk'_M k_A M_{kg}^{EP} \left(k_E k_A G_{APA}^{MWRC} + \frac{gm}{r^2} \right)}. \quad (101)$$

With $k_x = [4]_{Dx5}$, $k_A = 4$,¹⁴⁵ the $k_E = 16$ PG-MWRC trace the LMWRC (FIG. 78).²²⁹

FIG. 78. (Color online) RAVE-DR2 cylindrical ortho-radial (color dots), RBAA- CgV_o (LMWRC, magenta line), and PG-MWRCs ($k_E = 16$: blue line, $k_E = 1$: blue dotted line) along cylindrical galactic radius figure.^{143,144}

Note that in this PG-MWRC EEPT, the G_{APA} to gravity OCFs ratio k_E does affect the shape of PG-MWRC because the P_r^∞ -OCF is approximately constant which differs from the inverse distance square gravity-OCF.

Including the k_A value, the G_{APA}^{MWRC} (equation (100)) can be rewritten to be like the magnitude scaling formula of the PSAA EEPT (equation (62)) but with a much lighter EPM $M_{kg}^{EP1} = M_{kg}^{ISO} \times 8(32\pi)^2/c \cong 1.9 \times 10^5 \times M_\odot$,

$$G_{APA}^{MWRC1} = -P_r H_{kg}^0 Z_{Dc5}^2 1_{Dx5}. \quad (102)$$

Note that the orders magnitude lower EPM also reduces gravity-OCF magnitude; hence, it produces different shapes of PG-MWRCs.

3 RAVE-DR2 MW stars' positions distributions

The subfigures of FIG. 79 depict the RAVE-DR2 MW stars positions distribution on galactic X-Y and Z-radius planes, their segmented first-order fitted lines, and radial-binned-averaged (RBA) positions and star count curves.

²²⁹ Although the radial-quadratic galactic disk model used in the AG-MWRC is more realistic than the effective point mass model, the PG-MWRC (FIG. 78.) traces LMWRC better in the short galactic radius

These figures show that

- (1) In addition to apparatuses' limitations on measurable ranges and directions, the stars distribution has voids because of line-of-sight obstructions; very few stars are in the positive galactic X region (the far side of galactic center);
- (2) The stars' galactic position uncertainties (dot color bands) increase approximately with their orthogonal distances to the galactic X-axis and galactic plane;
- (3) Assuming apparatus and models' observation ranges are symmetric about the galactic X-axis, the stars' galactic X-Y plane distribution boundary has an asymmetrical pattern that resembles a spiral galaxy arm section;
- (4) The stars' distribution and boundary on the galactic Z-radius plane show the stars are distributed toward the negative Z regions; the distribution imbalances are approximately uniform across the RAVE-DR2 stars' distribution range as shown by the distribution boundary (red dotted lines, lower subfigure of FIG. 79) which could indicate the current galactic X-axis may not be on the actual galactic midplane (GMP).

region than the AG-MWRC (FIG. 63). However, the improvement is not conclusive because of the low star count in this region.

²³⁰ Compared with the $G_{APA}^{PSAA} = P_r H_{kg}^0 Z_{Dc2}^2 1_{Fx2} \times M_\odot$ of the PSAA EEPT.

FIG. 79. (Color online) RAVE-DR2 MW stars distribution on galactic X-Y (upper), X-Z (middle) and Z-radius (lower) planes (dots colors show positions uncertainties) figures: RBA- stars distribution border (red dotted line) and positions curves (magenta line), and segmented MATLAB first order fitted lines (gray dashed).^{231, 232, 233}

4 RAVE-DR2 MW stars' velocities distributions

Because our solar system is not the center of MW, one may be surprised to find the MW stars' velocities distributions have heliocentric symmetries rather than galactic center (GC) centric symmetries (FIG. 80). However, the AEAAN effects can provide some explanations for these behaviors.

The subfigures of FIG. 80 depict the RAVE-DR2 MW stars' velocities distributions: galactic Z, cylindrical galactic radial, and ortho-radial velocities: gV_z , CgV_r , and CgV_o , their segmented first-order fitted lines, and RBA

²³¹ Figure title row shows the MATLAB generated linear fit equations and their parameters ratios (pr[#:#]), and fitting start, segment partition, and end galactic distances ([#:#]kpc) where the $[0.2]_{kpc}$ binned star counts are higher than 30.

²³² Dot colors show stars' galactic position uncertainties (clipped to $[3]_{kpc}$ for visual clarity); red dotted line depicts a $[0.5]_{kpc}$ binned, top or bottom 5 stars positions mean curve.

²³³ The gray dashed fitting curve is generated by MATLAB's polynomial curve fitting function based on the RAVE-DR2 stars' data reside in the galactic X $[-0.89: -12.25]_{kpc}$ or radius $[2.34: 12.4]_{kpc}$

velocities and star count curves. These figures show that

- (1) Unlike the uncertainties of the stars' galactic positions that approximately increase with their ortho-galactic radius distances, the uncertainties of the stars' galactic velocities increase approximately with their heliocentric distances;
- (2) The RBA- gV_z and first-order polynomial fitted lines along the galactic radii indicate the gV_z mean is low, approximately $[-1.66]_{km/s}$,²³⁵ at the sun's galactic radius $[8]_{kpc}$ where the star counts are high and the stars' gP_z distributions are continuous (aka HCDC region);²³⁴
- (3) The RBA- CgV_r and their first-order fitted lines are approximately symmetrical, share a 0.94 gradient ratio, and devalue with their heliocentric distances; that the approximately $[3]_{km/s}$ minimum in the HCDC region indicates the stars' mean CgV_r are low;
- (4) On average, ignoring the signs, the magnitudes of the CgV_o and their first-order polynomial fitted lines indicate they decrease approximately with heliocentric distances; the approximately $[-200]_{km/s}$ minimum in the HCDC region indicates that the measured CgV_o are relative to sun's CgV_o .

regions where the $[0.2]_{kpc}$ binned star counts are higher than 30 (the stars' distribution galactic radius range is $[1.42: 17.66]_{kpc}$). Thicker and thinner fitted lines depict in-range and extensional curves. The partition point of the two segments linear fitting is approximately at $[-7.87]_{kpc}$ or $[7.89]_{kpc}$ galactic X or radius axes respectively. The blue dashed line depicts a $[0.2]_{kpc}$ binned star count curve. The vertical red dashed line depicts sun's galactic radius $[8]_{kpc}$.

²³⁴ The region near the middle-line of an hour-glass shaped gP_z distribution where the gP_z distributions are not disrupted.

FIG. 80. (Color online) RAVE-DR2 MW stars' galactic velocities (color dots) along cylindrical galactic radii figures: gV_z (top), CgV_r (middle), and CgV_o (bottom); RBA-velocities curves (magenta lines) and segmented first-order fitted lines (black dashed lines ^{235,236}), ^{237,231,233}

Because our solar system is not the center of MW, one may be surprised to find the MW stars' velocities distributions have heliocentric symmetries rather than galactic center (GC) centric symmetries. However, the stars' positions distributions and the AEAAN effects can provide some explanations for these behaviors.

The two subfigures of FIG. 81 depict the AEAAN effects adjusted gV'_z ($k_i = 0.2$) and CgV'_r ($k_i = 0.24$) distributions (refer to equation (79)), ²³⁸ their *unadjusted* velocities redistribution (dot colors), adjusted RBA velocities, and first-order fitted lines. These AEAAN effects adjustments bring the ISO to OSO linear polynomial fit parameters ratios 2.33:2.26 and 0.4:0.5 (excluding signs) of the unadjusted gV_z and CgV_r (FIG. 80) to 1.00:1.06 of the adjusted gV'_z and CgV'_r (FIG. 81). I.e., both adjusted velocities now have similar fitted ISO and OSO equations (excluding signs). Note that even excluding the inertia adjustments ($k_i = 0$, not shown in

²³⁵ The gV_z^{OSO} line crosses zero approximately at $[8.22]_{kpc}$ and approximately $[-1.66]_{km/s}$ at sun galactic radius $[8]_{kpc}$, one of the base parameters from which the RAVE-DR2 data are constructed.

²³⁶ Note that the slopes of the first-order fitted lines shown are relative because the X and Y-axes have kilometer and kpc spatial units

FIG. 81), the AEAAN effects adjusted polynomial parameters ratios are still close to one: 1.08:0.13 and 0.88:0.94 for the gV'_z and CgV'_r respectively.

FIG. 81. (Color online) RAVE-DR2 MW stars' adjusted gV'_z and CgV'_r distributions (dot colors show unadjusted velocities), RBA- gV'_z and CgV'_r curves (magenta lines), segmented first-order fitted gV'_z and CgV'_r (black dashed lines), and full-range first-order fitted gV'_z (red dashed line) along cylindrical galactic radius figures. ^{236,231,233}

The stars distribute asymmetrically along the galactic radius in the ISO and the OSO regions (FIG. 79); hence, the gradients of the first-order ISO and OSO unadjusted fitted lines are expected to have different gradients. The facts that these AEAAN effects adjusted gV'_z and CgV'_r have the similar gradient first-order fitted lines and the adjusted RBAA- CgV'_o has a similar gradient as the MWRC of [23] could indicate:

- (1) The AEAAN effects adjustments remove some of

respectively. Taking the kpc to kilometer ratio 3.086×10^{16} into consideration, the gradients of these fitted lines are close to zero.

²³⁷ Dot colors show stars' galactic velocity uncertainties (clipped to $[300]_{km/s}$ for visual clarity).

²³⁸ These similar k_i values could indicate that they share most initial components.

- the stars' positional velocities influencers;
- (2) The involvement of the AEAAN effect and affirm their existence;
 - (3) The stars' velocities are influenced mostly by the G_{QEM} -OCF; the inverse distance square gravity-OCF would have added an additional $\cos \delta^{-0.5}$ adjustment term.¹⁵³
 - (4) Presume the stars' gV_z are distributed symmetrically with respect to the galactic midplane (GMP), the gradients of the full-range first-order gV_z' fitted line (red-dashed line, FIG. 81) and non-zero value ($\sim[-9.17]_{km/s}$) at sun galactic radius $[8]_{kpc}$, could indicate the actual GMP could be tilted or offset from the current GMP.

In addition to the inertial velocities, if the AEAAN effects are the only positional velocities influencers, the AEAAN adjusted velocities should have flat fitted lines (zero gradients). Although these fitted lines' gradients are close to zero (using the same spatial units), both the gV_z' and the CgV_r' adjusted means increase with heliocentric distances. I.e., the gradient of the adjusted velocities fitted lines are still not zero; which could indicate they still have additional positional velocities influencers.

One of the possible influencers is the imbalanced distribution between the upper and lower region of the current GMP (i.e., the misalignment between the actual and current GMPs); the directional AEAAN effects residual from the imbalanced distribution can produce the toward-GMP gV_z' mean line that expands over positive and negative regions.²³⁹ In addition, the accelerating expansion of the universe and the centrifugal force from MW's rotation can push the V shaped CgV_r' means lines into the positive (outward) region.

Note that taking the different spatial units of the X and Y-axes in these velocity figures (FIG. 80 and FIG. 81) into consideration, the gradients of the fitted lines of which are close to zero using the same spatial units. However, the ratios between the ISO and OSO linear polynomial fit parameters are not affected by the spatial unit differences

and can still carry the information about their positional velocities' influencers.

VI. EMPIRICAL FIGURE PHENOMENOLOGICAL TEST PROCEDURE

The empirical figure phenomenological tests were done with the following procedure:

- (1) The normalized EIDIP functions with various IDTC or T_c were numerically generated through MATLAB based on equation (23) to produce a dual-column (position and magnitude) look up table (LUT). They were then numerically translated into the EIDIP effect LUT as needed; e.g., using MATLAB built-in gradient function to generate the EIDIP-gradient function LUT;
- (2) Depending on the targeted physical phenomena, the selected EIDIP effect LUT was then scaled with a case dependent magnitude and distance scaling formulas to generates the case dependent EIDIP effect curve (CDEEC) LUT;
- (3) A selected range of the CDEEC was plotted using the MATLAB plot routine;
- (4) If needed, the CDEEC plot was then imported into the Microsoft Visio graphics editing tool where the CDEEC and the MATLAB figure X-Y grids were "grouped" to maintain their relationship during the scaling in the next step;
- (5) The grouped X-Y grids and the CDEEC was then manually scaled, and shifted if needed, to align with the empirical figure's X-Y grids to ensure they have the same X and Y scales;
- (6) The grouped X-Y grids and the CDEEC may be shifted vertically or horizontally to fit the empirical figure; in these cases, the original X- and Y-axis of the CDEEC would be shown to indicate the shift.

VII. MATLAB PROGRAM FUNCTIONS

A. Dual (numerical + symbolic) zones integration (INS2) EIDIP generation function

The target-centric EIDIP function look-up tables (LUT) used in this paper were generated by the APS_EIDIPgenINS2 function with these parameters: $|\alpha_f^b| = |R_f^m| = 2/T_c$, $|\alpha_f^m| = 1$, $|\alpha_t^b| = |R_t^m| = 2$, and $|\alpha_t^m| = T_c$; e.g., for $T_c=(32\pi)$ case, the EIDIP LUT is generated by the APS_EIDIPgenINS2 MATLAB function with these parameters: Rmt: $R_t^m = 2$, Rmf: $R_f^m = 2/(32\pi)$, Gbt: $\alpha_t^b = 2$, Gbf: $\alpha_f^b = 2/(32\pi)$, Gmt: $\alpha_t^m=(32\pi)$, and Gmf: $\alpha_f^m = 1$. To produce useable numerical integration results in the MATLAB, the longer the numerical integrations range, the lower error tolerance setting it requires. The error tolerance (MyTol) used for this paper are range from 10^{-8} for the short-range to 10^{-22} for the long-range EIDIP generations. To get more accurate EIDIP effect curve's minimum- or maximum-locations, the error tolerances were set to 10^{-12} or higher even or those short-range EIDIP generations.

²³⁹ I.e., shifted positional information can shift the calculations of the positional velocities' influencers' effects. The stars' distribution boundary (lower subfigure of FIG. 79) shows that they distributed toward the negative Z region (below the current GMP). With the hour-glass shaped

stars distribution with non-zero gradient mean lines, the shifted positional information can shift the calculations of positional velocities influencers like the directional QERU effects and produced these graded velocities means lines.

```

function [EIDIP]=APS_EIDIPgenINS2(Roft, Rmt, Rmf, Gbt, Gbf, Gmt, Gmf, MyTol)
% Numerical+symbolic integration zones EIDIP generation
% Roft: inter object offset radius ( $r_o$ )
% Rmt, Rmf: target ( $R_t^m$ ) and reference ( $R_f^m$ ) object's E-fermion region radius
% Gbt, Gbf: target ( $\alpha_t^b$ ) and reference ( $\alpha_f^b$ ) coupling constant in E-boson region
% Gmt, Gmf: target ( $\alpha_t^m$ ) and reference ( $\alpha_f^m$ ) potential in E-fermion region
% MyTol: MATLAB simulation error tolerance

Rstr=0; % EIDIP integration start radius
Rend=10^128; % EIDIP integration end radius

Tstr = 10^-7; % Theta Start; (0-realmin) induced lot of NaN results
Tend =pi/2; % Theta end

%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
% Numeric and Symbolic integration zone configuration
% Symbolic integration region excludes target and reference objects'
% E-fermion regions
%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
RdNS=max(Rmt, Roft+Rmf)+1; % +1 as buffer zone

RstrN = Rstr; % Numerical integration start radius
RendN = RdNS-realmin; % Numerical integration end radius

EIDIPnum = double(2*pi*dblquad(@APS_EIDIPgenNum, RstrN, RendN, Tstr, Tend, ...
    MyTol, [], Roft, Rmt, Rmf, Gbt, Gbf, Gmt, Gmf)); %2pi for azimuthal angle factor

%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
% Symbolic Integration Zone configuration
%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
RstrS = RdNS;
RendS = Rend;
EIDIPsym = double(2*pi*Gbt*Gbf*quad(@APS_EIDIPgenSym, Tstr, Tend, MyTol, [], ...
    Roft, RstrS, RendS)); % 2pi for azimuthal angle factor

EIDIP = EIDIPnum + EIDIPsym;

end

```

B. EIDIP numerical radial and polar angle integration function

```

function EIDIP=APS_EIDIPgenNum(r, Theta, Roft, Rmt, Rmf, Gbt, Gbf, Gmt, Gmf)
% Numerical integration for EIDIP generation
% r: Spherical integration radius  $r_t$ 
% Theta: Spherical integration polar angle  $\theta$ 
% Roft: inter object offset radius
% Rmt, Rmf: target ( $R_t^m$ ) and reference ( $R_f^m$ ) object's E-fermion region radius
% Gbt, Gbf: target ( $\alpha_t^b$ ) and reference ( $\alpha_f^b$ ) coupling in E-boson region
% Gmt, Gmf: target ( $\alpha_t^m$ ) and reference ( $\alpha_f^m$ ) coupling in E-fermion region

% Z-axis complementary integration points radii to the reference spheroid origin
Rfp = sqrt(Roft.^2-2*Roft*r.*cos(Theta)+r.^2);
Rfn = sqrt(Roft.^2+2*Roft*r.*cos(Theta)+r.^2);

EIDIP = (cos(Theta)).*...

```

```
((Gbt./r).*(r >= Rmt)+ Gmt.*(r < Rmt)).*...
((Gbf./Rfp).*(Rfp>=Rmf))+Gmf.*(Rfp<Rmf))-...
((Gbf./Rfn).*(Rfn>=Rmf))+Gmf.*(Rfn<Rmf));
```

```
end
```

C. EIDIP symbolic radial and numerical polar angle integration function

```
function EIDIP=APS_EIDIPgenSym(Theta, Roft, Rstr, Rend)
% Numerical (theta) with Symbolic (radial) integration for EIDIP generation
% Theta: target-centric polar angle of integration point
% Roft: distance offset between target and reference objects
% Rstr, Rend: Radial (r) symbolic integration range

% Numerical integration for (r >= Rmt)&&(Rfp>=Rmf)&&(Rfn>=Rmf) region
% Rfp = sqrt(Roft.^2-2*Roft*r.*cos(Theta)+r.^2);
% Rfn = sqrt(Roft.^2+2*Roft*r.*cos(Theta)+r.^2);
% EIDIP = (cos(Theta)).*((Gbt./r)).*((Gbf./Rfp)-(Gbf./Rfn));

% Symbolic integration conversion
% % **** Generated by MATLAB 2007a Maple math engine.
% % **** 2010a version can't produce the following symbolic solution ****
% r=Rstr..Rend
% Rfp = sqrt(Roft.^2-2*Roft*r.*cos(Theta)+r.^2);
% Rfn = sqrt(Roft.^2+2*Roft*r.*cos(Theta)+r.^2);
% EIDIP = int(EIDIPnum, r, Rstr,Rend)
% EIDIP =cos(Theta)*...
%(-atanh(( Roft+cos(Theta)*Rstr)/(2*Roft*cos(Theta)*Rstr+Roft^2+Rstr^2)^(1/2))...
%-atanh((-Roft+cos(Theta)*Rstr)/(-2*Roft*cos(Theta)*Rstr+Roft^2+Rstr^2)^(1/2))...
%+atanh(( Roft+cos(Theta)*Rend)/( 2*Roft*cos(Theta)*Rend+Roft^2+Rend^2)^(1/2))...
%+atanh((-Roft+cos(Theta)*Rend)/(-
2*Roft*cos(Theta)*Rend+Roft^2+Rend^2)^(1/2)))/Roft;
%
S0=cos(Theta).*Rstr;
S1=(2*Roft*Rstr).*cos(Theta);
S2=Roft^2+Rstr^2;

E0=cos(Theta).*Rend;
E1=(2*Roft*Rend).*cos(Theta);
E2=Roft^2+Rend^2;

EIDIP=cos(Theta)./Roft.*...
(-atanh((Roft+S0)./(S1+S2).^(1/2))...
-atanh((-Roft+S0)./(-S1+S2).^(1/2))...
+atanh((Roft+E0)./(E1+E2).^(1/2))...
+atanh((-Roft+E0)./(-E1+E2).^(1/2)));

end
```

D. EIDIP symbolic formula generation script

```
% EIDIP symbolic formula generation script for MATLAB 2007a
restoredefaultpath;
rehash toolboxcache;

clear all;
```

```

tic;
%
syms Rt Rstr Rend positive;
syms Theta positive;
syms RfP RfN positive;
syms MinRt MinRf Roft positive;
syms EIDIPnum EIDIPsym positive;
%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
% (Rstr > max(Roft+MinRf, MinRt))
%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
RfN = (Rt^2+2*Roft*Rt*cos(Theta)+Roft^2)^(1/2);
RfP = (Rt^2-2*Roft*Rt*cos(Theta)+Roft^2)^(1/2);

%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
% For the long-range (R+C-L) zone symbolic integration
%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%%
EIDIPnum = cos(Theta)*((1/RfP)-(1/RfN))/Rt;
EIDIPsym = int(EIDIPnum, Rt, Rstr,Rend)

% % **** Generated by MATLAB 2007a Maple math engine.
% % **** 2010a version can't produce following symbolic solution ****
% EIDIPsym =cos(Theta)/Roft*...
% (atanh((Roft-cos(Theta)*Rstr)/(-2*Roft*cos(Theta)*Rstr+Roft^2+Rstr^2)^(1/2))...
% +atanh((Roft+cos(Theta)*Rstr)/(2*Roft*cos(Theta)*Rstr+Roft^2+Rstr^2)^(1/2))...
% +atanh((-Roft+cos(Theta)*Rend)/(-
% 2*Roft*cos(Theta)*Rend+Roft^2+Rend^2)^(1/2))...
% -atanh((Roft+cos(Theta)*Rend)/(2*Roft*cos(Theta)*Rend+Roft^2+Rend^2)^(1/2)));

```